

HYPERMASCULINITY IN NOLLYWOOD FILMS (2015-2017)

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ABSTRACT

The study set out to examine the extent to which hypermasculinity traits are portrayed in Nigeria Nollywood films (2015-2017) and the various dimensions of their portrayal. The specific objectives of the study were, among others, to identify hypermasculinity traits projected in select Nollywood films; and identify the dominant framework of hypermasculinity projected in select Nollywood films. To achieve these objectives, five corresponding research questions were stated and three hypotheses proposed. The study was predicated on stereotype theory, social role theory and gender hierarchy theory. The explanatory sequential mixed method was adopted in this study: integrating both content analysis and in-depth interviews in a bid to link findings from quantitative and qualitative approaches. The code sheet was used to record depictions of hypermasculinity in 350 Nollywood films which were selected out of the 3863 films produced within the span of this study. The researcher was guided by the various content categories and units of analysis that are indicative of hypermasculinity in the selected Nollywood films. The quantitative data were analyzed using charts and tables, as well as regression Analysis and ANOVA. Regression was used because it suits the nature of this study as the researcher set out to predict the correlation between the demographics of the males and their tendency to exhibit hypermasculine traits; whereas the qualitative data were analyzed using the inductive approach. The discussion of findings was done by interspersing the analysis from the quantitative data with the inductive analyses of the qualitative data in relation to each of the five research questions. The research found that, among other things, Nollywood films significantly sold hypermasculine ideologies as a collective characteristic of the male human and the most prominent traits in Nollywood films are other *hypermasculine traits* (mean = 4.27 and std = 4.54) (*including aggression, impulsivity, risk-taking, ambition, egotistic, etc.*) and *toughness as emotional self-control*, and there were more gender equitable traits [$t(8953) = 234.952, P < .005$] than non-gender equitable traits [$t(1496) = 93.461, P < .005$] in the select films. Based on the findings, it was recommend that, among other things, Nollywood should enhance the quality of articulation and dialogue in the Nigerian films and avoid padding up some unnecessary actions to fill timeline and elongate the duration of the film, and by so doing, increasing the frequency of hypermasculine traits.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Contemporary research has revealed profound aspects of film's impact on society (Uhrig, 2005). Those studies have severally concluded that films reflect society, both present and past (Sherak, 2011) that have touched every segment of the society, dealt with every subject and has reached every audience in one way or the other (Onabanjo & M'bayo, 2009). They have a uniquely powerful ubiquity within human culture; the direct economic impact of which is clear, but the effect to the wider economy is also significant. They have become a powerful vehicle for culture, education, leisure and propaganda (Shah, 2011).

Generally, the media has a powerful influence on the way we think (Ukozor & Nwodu, 2015). Compelling images, symbols and narratives employed by the media form the basis of so much of what we know, care about and aspire to (Idakwo, 2015; Santos, 2015; Dunu & Ugbo, 2015; Adewoye et al., 2014; Chukwumah, 2013; Couldry, 2000; etc). The mass media have come to play crucial roles in the socialization and conditioning of members of the society to accepted or expected roles and behaviour. Researchers seek to understand how this media power reflects, influences and perpetuates negative identities, roles and relations. For instance, the mass media has been argued to play a crucial role in constructing and transmitting gender ideology, thereby influencing gender attitudes, values, and beliefs (Lukas, 2002; Mosher & Tomkins, 1988).

Ekwenchi and Duru (2016) insist that of all media, the most glaring stereotype gender representation, needless to say, is to be seen in the audio-visual media, whether television or films. Sandman, Rubin and Sachsman (1976) cited in Ekwenchi and Duru (2016) explain that the power of audio-visual media in gender representation is because of the outstanding communicative strength of this class of media over print and audio-alone media. In the same vein, Chari (2007) asserts that films and videos have the obvious advantage in that they transcend language barriers and their audio-visual nature give them an upper hand over print in terms of shaping opinion.

In recent years, Nigerian researchers have been monitoring media portrayal especially with respect to social roles relating to gender. In particular, most of the attention had focused upon media

portrayal of women. For instance, several textual, content and discourse analyses of Nigerian films (Ejem, 2015, Rinre, 2015; Dunu & Ugbo, 2015; Ukozor & Nwodu, 2015; Adewoye et al., 2014; Duru, 2008; Azeez, 2008; McKenna, 2006; Ogunleye, 2003; Okunna, 1996, Ezeigbo, 1996, etc) have argued that Nigerian films portray and position Nigerian women stereotypically and negatively.

In line with a feminist ideological perspective of the media, the researchers argue that the films position women at the bottom of the power hierarchy in a way that reinforces their domination, objectification and suppression. Ekwenchi and Duru (2016) suggest that gender studies and women are synonymous. The motif of genderisation and social themes in most studies is the female gender. It is always about the female gender (Ogunyemi, 2014). The issue of female representation in the media was (and still is, in some countries like Nigeria) been so over-studied that we often forget that there are two genders, the male and the female. For the reason that studies on gender perspective and gender mainstreaming had too often ignored the gender of men and boys, the application of a more sophisticated gender analysis that also includes men and youth has been argued (Baker & Ricardo, 2005).

However, in recent years there has been a great flowering of empirical research on masculinities (a research idea that was actually invested in by Cornell, 1995). Connell (2001) gave an account of why there has been an upsurge of concern with issues about men and boys. She notes that in the public realm there have been social movements focused on the reform or restoration of masculinity. Godfrey (2010) contends that academic interest in masculinity has grown considerably across a number of disciplines including literature, cultural studies, and sociology as well as film and media studies.

Many of the studies, which are mostly of foreign origin, have great sophistication and complexity, and are not easy to summarize. The major problem of early masculinity research is that of definition. Hearn (1998) spelt out the very diverse and to some degree incompatible, positions that have been adopted in men's theorizing of men. Clatterbaugh (1998), working through definitions of masculinity has found them mostly vague, circular, inconsistent, or in other ways unsatisfactory.

Attempts have however been made by some authors to define masculinity. The only snag is that most of the definitions are old and are of foreign origin. It has been said that masculinity refers to social and cultural roles, personal traits, and behaviours, such as aggression and dominance, which are deemed acceptable for men (Godfrey, 2010; Mosher & Tomkins, 1988). According to the Women's Commission for Refugee Women and Children (2005), masculinity means the many socially constructed definitions for being a man; a construction which can change over time and from place to place. The term relates to perceived notions and ideals about how men should or are expected to behave in a given setting.

When masculine ideology becomes over-valued by a man, hyper-masculinity may result (Mosher & Sirkin, 1984; Mosher & Tomkins, 1988). That is, hyper-masculinity consists of an exaggerated expression of masculine gender ideology; the exaggeration of male stereotype behaviours, derived from the constellation of masculine stereotypes that are readily drawn on as a frame for gender comparison (Hickey, 2016). Hyper-masculinity is an extreme form of masculine gender ideology that is comprised of four traits, namely, calloused attitudes toward women, violence as manly, danger as exciting, and toughness as emotional self-control (Zaitchik & Mosher, 1993). Other characteristics central to hyper-masculinity include toughness, strong disdain for 'inferior' feminine traits and effects, and lack of emotional expression other than anger (Mosher & Tomkins, 1988).

In a more recent study, NerdLove (2013) explains that we are regularly bombarded with messages in mainstream media selling the idea that masculinity is violent, physically aggressive and sexually domineering and that anger and stoic toughness are the only appropriate emotions for men to display. As a result, it seems that many men look to popular culture for sources of information about what male behaviour is supposed to be and how they are supposed to display it. Ukozor (2011) asserts that a certain image of men is created as an insensitive, wicked and uncanny group of people which does not augur well for societal growth. She insists that there seems to be discrimination or marginalization in terms of excluding the voices of men that are ordinary or poor. In the same vein, Ukozor (2011) quotes Baber (2002), who questions the representation of men in population and the under-discussion of men's right. Baber accused media elites as being feminists or are afraid of offending women, which accounts for the lot of attention that women receive in

popular culture at the expense of men. However, one of the landmarks of gender studies in the 21st century is that the scope of gender studies has significantly broadened to not only be about women, but also include men and multiple other ideas, like race, ethnicity, sexuality and ability (Bondy, 2011).

There is scarcely a shred of empirical evidence to confirm the hypermasculine ideologies or representations of media content in Nigeria and Africa at large. UKaid (2014) stresses that what exist are mere theoretical postulations based on the implications of the patriarchal African society. Nigeria film industry emerges as a particularly significant case to study the hypermasculinity tendencies because men have traditionally been in power in the Nigerian film industry, thus theorists believe that their camera showed us the world through the stereotyped eyes of the 'male gaze' (Lovey, 2004). Based on that, it was suggested that film producers/directors churned out films in line with a domineering male status that emanate from the patriarchal school of thought (Olujinmi, 2008).

However, the 21st century has been marked by greater involvement of women in the nation's movie industry: a lot of women in the industry have moved from just being actresses into the more technical areas of scripting, videography, directing and production among other things. That is to say, there is a gradual break-down in the male domination of the industry which means that it cannot be entirely said that the camera shows us the world only through the stereotyped eyes of the 'male gaze.'

Consequently, concerns are mounting on how men are projected in Nollywood films, so much that there have been series of arguments and suggestions in various media platforms that these films are increasingly exaggerating male stereotype behaviours (Fea, 2018). This study therefore will attempt to provide empirical evidence to confirm or invalidate hypermasculinity in Nigerian films.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Few studies on gender and masculinities exist in African countries. There are even fewer studies that analyse representations of men and masculinities in the mass media (UKaid, 2014). Researchers have in the past expressed concern on the paucity of studies relating to the projection or portrayal of men in the media. Baker & Ricardo (2005) argue that given the extent of gender

inequalities in sub-Saharan Africa, an almost exclusive focus on women and girls has been appropriate. However, a gender perspective and gender mainstreaming have too often ignored the gender of men and boys. Huff Post (2016) explains that the majority of discourse on gender oppression is made up of the female experience. However, to encompass the entirety of the topic we must also widen our attention to those less associated with gender issues: men. Therefore, change in direction in gender studies has become necessary, and that has necessitated this study.

Gray and Ginsberg (2007) insist that women's rise in power in various sectors of the economy has created a crisis in gender studies and inspired insight into masculinity all over the world. At present, scholars and activists are increasingly recognizing the importance of explicitly investigating men as gendered beings (Peretz, 2016). Fea (2018) inquires that it is not news that the media misrepresents women and society largely accepts this fact, but, other than mere arguments and suggestions in some media platforms and in academic discourse, have we given enough practical thought to how men are portrayed?

Considering the above premises, especially in the context of the Nigerian film industry, one question comes to mind: in a typically patriarchal society like Nigeria, how do Nollywood films portray hypermasculine ideologies?

1.3 Research Objectives

The aim of this study was to analyse the extent and dimensions of portrayal of hypermasculinity in Nigerian Nollywood films (2015-2017). But the specific objectives were to:

1. identify hypermasculinity traits projected in select Nollywood films;
2. find out the frequency of occurrence of hypermasculinity in select Nollywood films;
3. identify the dominant framework of hypermasculinity projected in select Nollywood films;
4. ascertain the relative amount of gender equitable and non-gender-equitable masculinities in select Nollywood films; and
5. examine the ways that hypermasculinity is predicted by the demographics of the male characters in the select Nollywood films.

1.4 Research Questions

The researcher was guided by the following questions:

- 1 What are the hypermasculinity traits projected in the select Nollywood films?
- 2 How frequently did the hypermasculinity traits occur in the select Nollywood films?
- 3 What is the dominant framework of hypermasculinity projected in select Nollywood films?
- 4 How did the amount of gender equitable masculinities compare with non-gender-equitable masculinities in the select Nollywood films?
- 5 In what ways did the hypermasculinity in the select films relate to the demographics of the male characters in those films?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

The following were the hypotheses:

- H_i1: There is a significant correlation between the demographics of the male actors and depictions of hypermasculinity traits in the select Nollywood films.
- H_i2: The frameworks of hypermasculinity are evenly responsible for the various hypermasculinity traits depicted in select Nollywood films.
- H_i3: The non-gender-equitable masculinity traits are significantly higher than the gender equitable masculinity traits in the select Nollywood films

1.6 Scope of the Study

This is an explanatory sequential mixed method study of hypermasculinity in selected Nollywood films produced between 2015 and 2017. Various trends and landmarks informed the choice of the time frame; and they would be discussed in the population of the study. But the key landmark is that it is in the 21st century that the scope of gender studies significantly broadened to not only be about women, but also include men and multiple other ideas, like race, ethnicity, sexuality and ability (Bondy, 2011). Also, the database of films produced between 2015 and 2017 are available and would be used as the sampling frame.

Not all Nollywood films produced between 2015 and 2017 are of interest in this study, rather those feature-length Nollywood films that have males in their leading and supporting roles. It is the understanding of the researcher that the same way that selection and placement of stories can help to set agenda in the traditional media, so can the role played by actors determine their perception by the audience. More prominent roles are assumed to set more agenda for how an actor is perceived.

Only films which record is found in the website of the Nigerian Film and Video Censors Board are selected to ensure that they are registered films.

1.7 Significance of the Study

The findings of this study would be of immense use to the following categories:

To academic/researchers, this study will provide a springboard for future research on hypermasculinity in Nigeria. This is because there are few studies on gender and masculinities in African countries and even fewer that analyse representations of men and masculinities in the mass media.

Also, this study will help sociologists and psychologists understand the potential influence of the Nigerian film industry on the perceptions and behaviours of boys, men, women and girls. More so, understanding the representations of men and masculinities in Nigerian films could help in predicting the influence of the images of men in the films on gender identity and behaviours of male audiences.

It is also hoped that the findings of this study would deepen understanding and knowledge on the role of films in promoting gender equality and, in particular, in shaping perceptions of masculinities.

To professionals: film producers (all the people who handle the technical aspects of film production) and relevant government agencies, the findings of the study should inform any future initiatives to integrate gender equitable approaches to the production of films. Various players in Nollywood would understand how to project a fair and balanced image of men and women, and become aware of their role in facilitating gender equality or, at least, tolerance. Nollywood would

by the findings of this study assess the place of gender representation as a thematic obsession in the industry. Often times, the producers are not aware of the fact that they are blowing certain gender representations out of proportion. They only care about the storyline. Studies like this would make them become aware of it.

To society/governance: The film regulators could be inspired by this study to fashion regulatory frameworks towards the promotion of gender equitable images and messages in films. The attention of the National Films and Video Censor's Board (NFVCB) would be drawn to the extent of hypermasculinity in the films, and if they are projected in an uncomfortable proportion, NFVCB might consider including gender portrayal as a rating category, aside from Violence, Nudity and Strong Language.

It is also expected that traditional institutions would find the result of this study useful as it is given that gender attitudes and practices are deeply rooted in cultural beliefs and perceptions. So any gender campaign effort demands a systematic effort that crosscut all areas of society, starting from the traditional institutions.

To the body of theories: The findings of this study will provide a more fundamental and empirical basis for hypermasculinity theories and other gender theories, and add to the argument about what the dominant framework of masculinity in a typical patriarchal society is: is it biological determinism, gender role socialization or social constructionism?

1.8 Limitations of the Study

This study was not without glitches, the prominent of which was the problem of sampling: there were some difficulties in getting all the sampled films to watch and code them. Sixty-two (62) of the selected 350 films were not seen, especially in 2017. The researcher addressed that by randomly choosing other 62 available films to replace them.

Next, this study used an explanatory sequential mixed method approach that combined content analysis (quantitative) and in-depth interview (qualitative). The limitation inherent in the use of content analysis is that it does not provide views of film viewers about hypermasculinity in the films. While content analysis is appropriate to examine hypermasculinity objectively in the selected Nollywood films, it did not give room to gauge the open-ended opinions of a

representative sample of men. It would have been important to do so, because what the researcher would consider as non-gender equitable masculinities, for instance, might not be seen as such by the men. The researcher tried to get around this particular limitation by linking data from the content analysis and the in-depth interviews.

More so, the use of explanatory sequential mixed method approach increased the complexity of the planning, conduct and analysis in this study. The said complexity delayed the pace of this thesis.

1.9 Operational Definitions of Terms

1. **Demographics:** the age, social status, marital status, occupation and family life of the male characters which hypothetically have the tendency to influence the extent to which the male characters exhibit hypermasculine traits.
2. **Equitable masculinities:** Positive traits identified with men in the feature-length films.
3. **The framework of hypermasculinity:** How the masculine traits were acquired. By birth (biological essentialism), learned (gender role socialization) or societal expectations (social constructionism)
4. **Hypermasculinity:** misguided representations of masculine traits such as violence, force against women, meanness, seeing danger as a 'man thing' etc., in the feature-length films.
5. **Men:** The male actors in the feature-length films who played leading or supporting roles.
6. **Nollywood Films:** Feature length films produced by Nigerians between 2015 and 2017.
7. **Non-gender equitable masculinities:** Negative projection of the manliness or negative traits identified with men in the feature-length films.
8. **Portrayal:** Extent and manner of representations of hypermasculinity in the feature-length films.
9. **Traits:** Actions or behaviours that reveal hypermasculinity in the Nollywood films

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter reviews existing knowledge about concepts in the thesis, explores the theoretical frameworks that support this study and also reviews empirical studies related to the work. The essence is to help in any way to illuminate the problem in hand (Edeani, 1995), provide “empirical-cum-theoretical insight into the study in view” (Nwodu, 2006, p. 219) and put the study in perspective.

2.1 Conceptual Review

In this section, the researcher reviews some of the relevant concepts in the thesis and brings to light some of the views of the various authors regarding them.

2.1.1 The Concept of Hypermasculinity

In recent years there has been a great flowering of empirical research on dimensions of masculinities, especially hypermasculinities. Researchers have however expressed that among the problems of masculinity research are problems of definition because of the complexity of the concept. Hearn (1996, 1998) has raised doubts about the usefulness of the concept of masculinities, and has spelt out the very diverse, and to some degree incompatible, positions that have been adopted in men's theorizing of men. Clatterbaugh (1998) in Connell (2001) found definitions of masculinity to be mostly vague, circular, inconsistent, or in other ways unsatisfactory.

Series of attempts have however been made in some quarters to conceptualize masculinity but the most seemingly comprehensive is that masculinity is seen as a set of qualities, characteristics or roles generally considered typical of, or appropriate to, a boy or man. It consists of the characteristics of the male sex and the traits of behaving in ways considered typical for men. It is a concept that refers to social and cultural roles, personal traits, and behaviours, such as aggression and dominance, which are deemed acceptable for men (Mosher and Tomkins, 1988). Masculinity is made up of both socially defined and biologically created factors (Wijngaard, 1997; Martin, 2010 & Dunphy, 2000 in Siddhanta & Singh, 2015). Sometimes, masculinity is also referred to as manliness or manhood. Traits traditionally cited as masculine include courage, independence, and

assertiveness (Murray, 2000) competition, logic and rational thinking, strength, boldness and aggressiveness (Jordan, 2014). These traits associated with masculinity vary depending on location and context and are influenced by a variety of social and cultural factors (Witt, 2010). When masculine ideology becomes over-valued by a man, hyper-masculinity may result (Mosher & Sirkin, 1984; Mosher & Tomkins, 1988; Zaitchik & Mosher, 1993).

Hypermasculinity is a psychological term for the exaggeration of male stereotypical behaviour such as an emphasis on physical strength, aggression and sexuality while exhibiting emotional self-control as a sign of toughness as well as composure and impassiveness in times of great stress (Siddhanta & Singh, 2015). It is the misguided concepts of manhood: the gender-based ideology of what it means to be a man, when carried out in an exaggerated way (Zaitchik & Mosher, 1993). According to Zaitchik and Mosher (1993), hypermasculinity is an extreme form of masculine gender ideology, often comprising of a cluster of beliefs that includes toughness, violence, dangerousness, and calloused attitudes toward women and sex.

While the concept of masculinity is a bit older, the term hypermasculinity first appeared in a 1984 study by Donald Mosher. He argued that hypermasculinity consists of three factors: callous sexual attitudes towards women; the belief that violence is manly and; the experience of danger as manly. He explained that men are regularly associated with danger and violence and are expected to be very aggressive and apathetic to get their point across. He developed the Hypermasculinity Inventory (HMI) designed to measure the three core components of hypermasculinity explained above. There have continued to be scholarly reviews of the characteristics central to HM. Mosher and Tomkins (1988) mentioned toughness, strong disdain for 'inferior' feminine traits and affects, calloused attitudes towards women and sex, violence and aggression, lack of emotional expression other than anger, and danger and sensation seeking. In a subsequent revision of the concept following a study by Zaitchik and Mosher (1993) the concept of hyper-masculinity as an extreme form of masculine gender ideology was said to be comprised of four traits, namely, (a) calloused attitudes toward women, (b) violence as manly, (c) danger as exciting, and (d) toughness as emotional self-control.

The four characteristics of hypermasculinity as described by Mosher and Tomkins (1988) cited in Siddhanta and Singh (2015) are as follows:

1. Violence as manly: the attitude that violent aggression is an acceptable expression of masculine power and dominance;
2. Calloused attitudes towards women/sex: the attitude that intercourse with women is a source of male power and female submission, and that sex is acceptable without empathic concern for the female's subjective experience;
3. Toughness as emotional self-control: the belief that anger is the only legitimate male emotion, and that expression of emotions, particularly 'feminine' emotions such as sensitivity and empathy, are a sign of weakness; and
4. Danger as exciting: the attitude that survival in dangerous situations is manly.

There have been other studies to buttress the conception and propositions of hypermasculinity. According to Dennehy and Ben-Zeev (2012), hypermasculinity exhibits emotional self-control as a sign of toughness as well as composure and impassiveness in times of great stress or emotion and hypermasculine pattern leads to competition, rather than connection between persons (Scheff, 2006). In the same vein, Vokey, Tefft and Tysiaczny (2013) explain that hyper-masculinity is a gender-based ideology of exaggerated beliefs about what it is to be a man. That is, it is the ideology of exaggerated male traits as the epitome of masculine identity.

NerdLove (2013) describes hypermasculinity as the portrayal of violence and physical aggression as “manly ideas”; promoting a world where “all of male life is a struggle of dominance of others”, where sex is seen as a matter of power and female submission rather than one of intimacy and mutual pleasure and that any feminine emotions are to be repressed. Behaviours such as acting tough and fighting are the only acceptable reactions to fear because the rules of masculinity do not permit expression of pain and vulnerability.

The hypermasculine male is characterized by the idealization of stereotypically masculine traits, such as virility and physicality, while concurrently rejecting traits seen as feminine and thus perceived as antithetical and even inferior to machismo, such as compassion or emotional expression (Zaitchik & Mosher, 1993; Scharrer, 2005). According to Connell (2000), hypermasculinity is a “widespread belief that it is ‘natural’ for men to be violent. Males are inherently more aggressive than women, the argument goes. ‘Boys will be boys’ and cannot be

trained otherwise; rape and combat – however regrettable – are part of the unchanging order of nature” (p. 22).

Describing it as the idealization of masculine stereotypes, Ruminawi (2016) adds to already stated conceptualization of hypermasculinity as the exaggeration of masculine traits; some of its ideals are devaluation of emotion, low tolerance for those who violate traditional gender roles, and high physical body standards. NerdLove (2013) adds that hypermasculine ideology reinforces a culture that permits a very narrow expression of male identity. The message carried by the imagery is that men are defined by conflict and violence. Every interaction between men is one of a struggle for dominance. There are no equals, only the dominant and the submissive. He concludes that hypermasculine ideas reinforce the belief that to be a man is to be a satyr, rampantly virile and voracious in appetite. A man is defined by his steely hard-on as much – if not more – than by his muscles or his toughness. In addition, the life of a man is a physical one, with minimal investment or worth given to any life path that doesn't involve hunting, ranching or building.

There are some researchers who believe that hypermasculinity is a concept that is opposed to feminism. That is, it is a divergent concept which does not tolerate feminine emotions. Huff Post (2016) explains that hypermasculinity is the belief that in order to be a man you must in no way resemble a woman; being even remotely feminine strips you entirely of your masculinity. Consequently, typically feminine traits such as tenderness, compassion and empathy are strictly off limits. Therefore, in order to be a man you cannot display evidence of harbouring any of these aspects. Instead, the man determined to be perceived as a man by society must alienate themselves from all emotion that is considered feminine. In place of these feminine emotions men are permitted characteristics such as lust to present sexual prowess, rage to show off strength, and bravado to display courage.

The mass media are understood to play a crucial role in constructing and transmitting gender ideology, thereby influencing gender attitudes, values, and beliefs (Lukas, 2002; Mosher & Tomkins, 1988). In that regard, researchers explained hypermasculinity as a media construction of masculine ideology. It is explained as an exaggerated image of hegemonic masculinity (*to be reviewed later in this chapter*), mainly in the media which overemphasizes the ideals, such as physical strength, aggression and sexuality set out for men, thereby reinforcing them. It is an alpha

male ideology that suggests everyday men should embody an extraordinary standard of ruggedness, emotional self-control, dominance, and operate as cavalier womanizers. Charles (2013) suggests that media may be subconsciously encouraging negatively audacious behaviour and aggressive attitudes in young men.

Owing to the great sophistication and complexity of the studies on hypermasculinity, Connell (2000) provides a summary of the body of research as follows:

- a. Multiple masculinities. Different cultures, and different periods of history, construct gender differently. In multicultural societies there are likely to be multiple definitions of masculinity. Equally important, more than one kind of masculinity can be found within a given culture, even within a single institution such as a school or workplace.

Implications: Violent, aggressive masculinity will rarely be the only form of masculinity present, in any cultural setting. The variety of masculinities that are documented in research can provide examples and materials for peace education. Education programmes must recognize diversity in gender patterns, and the tensions that can result from social diversity.

- b. Hierarchy and hegemony. Different masculinities exist in definite relations with each other, often relations of hierarchy and exclusion. There is generally a dominant or “hegemonic” form of masculinity, the centre of the system of gendered power. The hegemonic form need not be the most common form of masculinity.

Implications: Large numbers of men and boys have a divided, tense, or oppositional relationship to hegemonic masculinity. Clear-cut alternatives, however, are often culturally discredited or despised. The most powerful groups of men usually have few personal incentives for gender change. Other groups may have stronger motives for change.

- c. Collective masculinities. Masculinities are sustained and enacted not only by individuals, but also by groups, institutions, and cultural forms like the mass media. Multiple masculinities may be produced and sustained by the same institution.

Implications: The institutionalization of masculinity is a major problem for peace strategy. Corporations, workplaces, voluntary organizations, and the state are important sites of action. Collective struggles, and the reshaping of institutions, are as necessary as the reform of individual life.

- d. Bodies as arenas. Men's bodies do not fix patterns of masculinity, but they are still very important in the expression of masculinity, which constantly involves bodily experience, bodily pleasures, and the vulnerabilities of bodies.

Implications: Peace education may often be too much "in the head". Health, sport and sexuality are issues that must be addressed in changing masculinity.

- e. Active construction. Masculinities do not exist prior to social interaction, but come into existence as people act. Masculinities are actively produced, using the resources available in a given milieu.

Implications: The process of constructing masculinity, rather than the end state, may be the source of violence. No pattern of masculine violence is fixed, beyond all hope of social reform. Equally, no reform is final. It is possible that gender reforms will be overthrown and more violent patterns of masculinity reintroduced.

- f. Division. Masculinities are not homogeneous, but are likely to be internally divided. Men's lives often embody tensions between contradictory desires or practices.

Implications: Any pattern of masculinity has potentials for change. Any group of men is likely to have complex and conflicting interests, some of which will support change towards more peaceable gender patterns.

- g. Dynamics. Masculinities are created in specific historical circumstances. They are liable to be contested, reconstructed, or displaced. The forces producing change include contradictions within gender relations, as well as the interplay of gender with other social forces.

Implications: Masculinities are always changing, and this creates motives for learning. However, as any agenda for change is likely to be against some groups' interests, controversy and conflict are to be expected.

Therefore, from the views of various researchers, hypermasculinity is abstracted to mean inflation of stereotypic masculine attitudes and behaviors involving callous attitudes toward women, and the belief that violence is manly and danger is exciting (Mosher & Sirkin, 1984); inflated valuation of status, self-reliance, aggressive activities, dominance over others, and devaluation of emotion and cooperation (Burk, Burkhart & Sikorski, 2004); linked to aggression towards women,

aggression to men who violate gender norms, increased risk taking behavior (drugs, alcohol, larger numbers of sexual partners, depression, poor coping skills (Corprew, 2014).

2.1.2 Frameworks for Conceptualizing Hypermasculinity

There are different hypotheses on the causation of hypermasculinized traits. Some scholars say that hypermasculinity stems from hormonal irregularities (i.e., higher levels of prenatal testosterone). Many studies claim that low levels of prenatal androgens can lead to male homosexuality while the opposite is true for those who exhibit hypermasculinized tendencies, often having a higher likelihood of committing crime, and having aggressive attitudes. High testosterone levels can also be linked to a lack of empathy and moral judgments (Montoya, 2013 in Siddhanta & Singh, 2015) which could lead to the hypermasculinized tendencies (Subramanian, 2014; Brannon, 2000; O'Shaunnesey & Stadler, 2005; Courtenay, 2000; Cosgrove, 2000).

However, three major frameworks of gender have been used to conceptualize the causes and factors responsible hypermasculinized traits, namely biological determinism, gender role socialization, and social constructionism (Vokey, 2008; Vokey, Tefft & Tysiaczny, 2013).

2.1.2.1 Biological Essentialism

Biological essentialism has been in the explanation for men's aggression. It is one of the earliest frameworks used to conceptualize masculinity (Cosgrove, 2000). Biological determinism or genetic determinism is the belief that human behaviour is controlled by an individual's genes or some component of their physiology, generally at the expense of the role of the environment, whether in embryonic development or in learning (Taylor, Whittier, & Rupp, 2012). It is defined as a general theory, which holds that a group's biological or genetic makeup shapes its social, political, and economic destiny (Subramaniam, 2014).

The fundamental essence of biological determinism is the belief that we are "how we are" because of our genetic makeup, including race and sex (FactCheckMe, 2009). This is an appeal to biology, with testosterone in particular, the so-called 'male hormone', as a catch-all explanation for why men exhibit aggressive tendencies. Biology is said to be responsible for gender differences in socially proscribed traits, behaviours, and roles.

Chandler and Munday (2011) explain biological determinism or essentialism as the belief that ‘human nature’, an individual's personality or some specific quality (such as intelligence, creativity, homosexuality, masculinity, femininity, or a male propensity to aggression) is an innate and natural ‘essence’ (rather than a product of circumstances, upbringing, and culture). The concept is typically invoked where there is a focus on difference, as where females are seen as essentially different from males.

Some researchers however insist that biological differences between the sexes are insufficient to account for the large differences in observed gender roles (Cosgrove, 2000). An important criticism of biological essentialism is that it naturalizes patriarchy, gender differences and gender inequality (Cosgrove, 2000). Patriarchy is a social structure in which the father or a male figure is the leader, family descent is determined through the male line, and masculine power and authority dominate social, political, and economic institutions (Brannon, 2000; O’Shaunnesey & Stadler, 2005).

2.1.2.2 Gender Role (Sex Role) Socialization

Gender role socialization theory was the second framework to become widespread for researching masculinity (Courtenay, 2000). Gender roles are defined as those behaviours, values, and personality characteristics expected of girls/women and boys/men, which act as a model or script for behaviour (Brannon, 1998; Cosgrove, 2000). According to this framework, boys and girls learn to be masculine and feminine in a way similar to how all behaviours, values, and attitudes are learned, namely through the differential social expectations imposed on them by family, peers, and societal institutions.

Gender role socialization has been criticized for focusing on gender ‘roles’ as if they were fixed and mutually exclusive components (Connell, 1998; Ridgeway & Correll, 2004). This is because focusing exclusively on gender roles fails to account for the vast differences in gender displayed, both within and between, groups of men and women.

2.1.2.3 Social Constructionism

The third concept for conceptualizing masculinity is known as social constructionism, social constructivism, social construction of reality or social concept. A key focus of social constructionism is to uncover the ways in which individuals and groups participate in the construction of their perceived social reality. It involves looking at the ways social phenomena are developed, institutionalized, known, and made into tradition by humans. The framework questions widely held assumptions about inherent qualities of items, concepts, or issues, and instead brings attention to the dependence of such qualities upon the contingent rationale of our social sense. According to a report on UK Essays (2017), social constructionism argues that human perceptions of reality and the world, of things, concepts and ideas, are shaped by deliberate human choices and linguistic reinforcement, rather than by natural laws or divine intention.

Social constructionism argues that language does not simply describe reality but plays a role in creating ideas about human societies (Cosgrove, 2000; O'Shaunnesey & Stadler, 2006). The premise of this masculinity framework is that all societies have different ways of organizing the world, including different rituals, customs, values, and beliefs (ideology) that societal members use to make sense of the world. Essentially, societies construct the world and construct reality, and systems of communication, particularly those that reach large audiences like the mass media, are crucial in constructing and transmitting gender ideology. Hypermasculinity, for instance, can often be adopted by young men due to their exposure to TV commercials or magazine advertisements showing man often having hypermasculinity. Ultimately, the reality constructed by society tends to become normalized through the habitual, repetitive organization of society according to this constructed structure. As this occurs, it becomes 'taken for granted' by those within the society as just the way things are. People tend to forget that reality has been constructed or that it could be organized differently (Cosgrove, 2000; O'Shaunnesey & Stadler, 2006).

Good (2008) explains that social constructivism is an ontological viewpoint harboring the basic idea that the world has a social foundation suggesting that the world is socially constructed. This is about the social order on how people perceive the world and how they distinguish between right and wrong.

The framework of social constructionism examines the development of jointly constructed understandings of the world that form the basis for shared assumptions about reality. It centers on the notions that human beings rationalize their experience by creating models of the social world and share and reify these models through language (Leeds-Hurwitz, 2009). That means characteristics typically thought to be immutable and solely biological—such as gender, race, class, ability, and sexuality—are products of human definition and interpretation shaped by cultural and historical contexts (Subramanian, 2010).

It concerns the meaning, notion, or connotation placed on an object or event by a society, and adopted by the inhabitants of that society with respect to how they view or deal with the object or event. In that respect, a social construct as an idea would be widely accepted as natural by the society, but may or may not represent a reality shared by those outside the society, and would be an invention or artifice of that society (Gale, 2008). Burr (2003) maintains that knowledge of constructionism enables individuals to adopt critical attitudes towards their conventional lenses for perceiving and understanding the world and their own selves. It provides humans with fresh ways of assessing ideas and things that are otherwise considered to be commonplace and accepted without demur.

2.1.3 Effects of Hypermasculinity

The effects of hypermasculine messages have been highlighted by many researchers. Hypermasculinity is theorized to have a number of effects of sub-groups and certain demographics have been found to be more susceptible to hypermasculinity. Also, there has been considerable number of research showing a positive association between hyper-masculine beliefs and a host of social and health problems, such as dangerous driving, drug use and violence towards women.

Scholars have continually linked hypermasculinity with aggression towards women. (Mumen, Wright & Kaluzny, 2002; Parrot & Zeichner, 2003). In a study by Parrot and Zeichner (2003), it was found that adherence to hypermasculine traits is linked to a host of social and health problems in North America, such as dangerous driving and violence toward women. Siddhanta and Singh (2015) maintain that researches from all over the world have found that hypermasculinity is associated with sexual and physical aggression towards women.

In one of the earliest studies on hypermasculinity, it was confirmed that young men and men with low social-economic power are most vulnerable to hyper-masculinity (Zaitchik & Mosher, 1993; NerdLove, 2013; Hess, 2013). They variously conclude that young men are vulnerable because adolescence and young adulthood are developmental periods when peer group support for hyper-masculine behaviours is high. NerdLove (2013) assert that the role and meaning of masculinity is especially strong in younger men – men in their late teens and early twenties – as they strike out to find their own place in the world. Hess (2013) says that masculinity is pitched to young men.

Research shows that hypermasculine imagery was predominantly aimed at two audiences: younger men (adolescents and men in their early 20s) and older working-class men without college educations. Hypermasculine gender ideology is most likely to be enacted during adolescence and young adulthood, the developmental periods during which peer group support for hypermasculine behaviours is believed to be high (Zaitchik & Mosher, 1993). During adolescence, boys start to identify more strongly with the masculine stereotypes than they did during childhood (Vokey, Tefft & Tysiaczny, 2013). The younger men are more often the ones seeking out their identity. They are more likely to look to others for ideas of gender presentation, and thus they are the ones whose behaviour is more likely to be influenced by media and reinforced by their peer group.

Vokey, Tefft and Tysiaczny (2016) also found out that hypermasculinity is mostly a concern to young men because they are still learning appropriate gender behaviors, and their beliefs and attitudes can be subtly shaped by images that the mass media repeatedly represent. It was also found in the study that men with limited social and economic power are more likely to adopt a tough persona and to use violence to gain respect. Hypermasculinity portrayals send a message that these traits are acceptable.

NerdLove (2013) found out that people who lack popular indicators of social value such as financial success or social influence are more likely to look for alternative means of gaining respect and influence from one's peers – physical toughness, macho behavior, violence and aggression. He continues that hypermasculinity is also prevalent among the younger men and older men: the younger men are trying to find their place in the world and are seeking guidance as they work towards how to be men; meanwhile the older men are often feel as though they have been cheated

and that others are benefiting from something that has been denied to him, thus they want to re-establish their manhood.

As a proof of the connection between hypermasculinity and crime, it is understood that prisoners and criminals often tend to have higher hypermasculinity scores than control groups (Beesley & McGuire, 2009). Hypermasculinity is a concept that impacts on a man's behaviour. That is why Siddhanta and Singh (2015) explain that high masculinity or hypermasculinity can reinforce the risk in one's own behaviour as well as the persons connected to them. Scharrer (2010) explains that psychological research evidence reveals serious, harmful implications for the intersection of macho personality and criminal behavior in individuals.

On the wider effects of hypermasculinity in the media on society, Vokey, et al (2016) conclude that the widespread depiction of hyper-masculinity in men's magazine advertising may be detrimental to both men and society at large; although, theoretically, men as a group can resist the harmful aspects of hyper-masculine images, the effects of such images cannot be escaped completely.

Studies have also shown that black people seem to express more hypermasculine traits than other races (Royster, 2011). Scholars assert that colonizers' perception of the colonial black subject as an uncivilized, primitive, irrational non-subject served as justification for the traumas inflicted on them, and that the legacy of such a perception is still evident in today's society. As a means of resistance, black men project hypermasculinity in order to combat the feelings of powerlessness that are imposed on them. Corprew (2014) asserts that hypermasculinity is also tied to homophobia and lack of tolerance towards men that do not fit into hypermasculine standards.

2.1.4 Media and Projection of Hypermasculine Traits

Various researches have shown that the media are powerful agents for the projection and propagation of hypermasculine tendencies because hypermasculine archetypes abound in the mass media, especially action films, advertisements, and a plethora of popular culture media (Dill & Thill, 2007; Scharrer, 2010; Iwamoto, 2003). Graig (1999) insists that through entertainment, news programming and advertising, mass media around the world projects images that associate manhood with dominance, efficiency, violence and control (the attributes of hypermasculinity).

It is severally argued that many men look to popular culture for sources of information what male behaviour is supposed to be and how we are supposed to display it. Hypermasculine contents in the media show men as violent, physically aggressive, hypersexual or participating in “dangerous” activities for the thrill of it all.

Ben-Zeev, et al (2012) point toward images in the media as the most important factor that influence hypermasculine behaviour. NerdLove (2013) explains that we are regularly bombarded with messages selling the idea that masculinity is violent, physically aggressive and sexually domineering and that anger and stoic toughness are the only appropriate emotions for men to display. She concludes that hypermasculinity can often be adopted by young men due to their exposure to TV commercials or magazine advertisements showing man often having hypermasculinity.

Kareithi (2014) explains that one key source of construction of hegemonic masculinity is the American movie industry, which feeds the global culture with an endless stream of violent male icons. Tens of millions of people, disproportionately young males, flock to theatres worldwide or rent videos of what Katz (2011, p. 261) calls the ‘action-adventure’ films of male icons such as Arnold Schwarzenegger, Sylvester Stallone, Jean-Claude Van Damme, Bruce Willis, Christian Bale and Matt Damon. Local or regional equivalents of the male icons created by Hollywood now dominate local and regional film and television industries in other parts of the world – from India’s Bollywood to Nigeria’s Nollywood. Adding to this inventory of images are the music video industry and the widespread practice in advertising to stress gender difference, implicitly and even explicitly reaffirming the ‘natural’ dissimilarities of males and females. And then there are the inescapable military and sports symbolisms proliferate in all forms of media including video games, all enhancing the association of muscularity with ‘ideal masculinity’.

Kareithi (2014) insists that in many parts of the world, magazine and television advertisements aimed at men are rife with advertisements featuring violent male icons, such as football players, big-fisted boxers, military figures and leather-clad bikers. Men’s sports magazines and televised sporting events carry millions of dollars’ worth of military advertisements. And the past 20 years has seen a mushrooming of advertisements for products designed to help men develop muscular physiques - from weight training machines to nutritional supplements and services to enhance their

muscles or their penis sizes. These advertisements exploit men's feeling of not being big, strong or violent enough by promising to provide them with the products that will enhance these qualities.

Hypermasculinity ideas and beliefs are circulated repeatedly through language and texts of social institutions, particularly the mass media. This happens because institutions, such as the media are owned and controlled almost exclusively by the dominant groups of society. Hegemony theory holds that subordinate groups internalize the values and beliefs of the dominant group, accepting their less powerful status in society (Prillettensky & Nelson, 2005).

Even in "dead" (animated) media like video games and cartoons, hypermasculinity has been expressed (Traudt, 2005). Also, Salter and Blodgett (2012) understands that in the gaming industry, hypermasculinity is experienced mainly through the fantastic and often violent situations presented in the gameplay, and as well by the typical design and character traits of the playable characters: often powerfully built, bold and full of bravado and usually armed.

Advertising is believed to play a role in constructing hyper-masculinity (Kilbourne, 1999). A study of advertisements and hypermasculine show that aggressive advertising may make for aggressive men (Krans, 2013). The study finds magazine advertisements may help promote troubling behavior in young men. Further analysis of the data showed that magazines with the highest proportion of hyper-masculine advertisements were those aimed at younger, less-affluent and less-educated men. It concludes that the widespread depiction of hyper-masculinity in men's magazine advertising may be detrimental to both men and society at large. Although theoretically, men as a group can resist the harmful aspects of hyper-masculine images, the effects of such images cannot be escaped completely

It has been said that media depictions perpetuate dominant ideologies of gender and unequal power relations (Femiano & Nickerson, 2002), and male stereotypes propagated by the media influence expectations of what men should and should not be like, presenting masculinity as a fixed, inevitable, natural state of being rather than a dynamic social and cultural process (Earp & Katz, 1999; Femiano & Nickerson, 2002).

Okafor (2013) reveals that media producers in Nigeria are aware of the potentials of the mass media to perpetuate attributes of hypermasculinity that is why they are now trying to promote

gender equitable images and messages in Nigerian media products and processes. But UKaid (2015) however insists that disparity still exists in media coverage and portrayals of women and men (who in general are much more visible) and this reinforces gender stereotypes and inequalities. He continues by saying that the problem is that the Nigerian media industry continues to be dominated by men and it is they who predominantly control the industry.

Visibility of the men in the media is a topic that has also been addressed by researchers. Men are said to be more visible in the media than women, and consequently hypermasculine traits are constantly projected by the media. Thompson and Zerbinos (1995) examined the rate and nature of male and female portrayals in children's programming and the research shows that male characters appear on the 30 screen more often, are more often engaged in activity, and are given more speaking roles than their female counterparts. These male characters were also more assertive, independent, athletic, and responsible than female characters.

With regard to the *dead* media, such as cartoons, Baker and Raney (2007) examined the number of males and females present in cartoon programming as well as the physical appearance, personality traits, and communicative behaviors of males and females. Their findings show that male characters were present 65.7% of the time compared to 34.4% for female characters, demonstrating that males occupy more lead roles and screen time than female characters in children's cartoon programming. Signorielli and Bacue (1999) in a related study also found that males receive more recognition than females on television shows, indicating higher values being held for males.

2.1.5 Gender Portrayal and Stereotypes in the Media

Understanding what gender means is usually the first impulse in the review of gender issues and portrayals. Scholars have often given simple definition of gender and tried to differentiate it sex because of the confusion that is often generated because of the two concepts. Adebayo and Olanisakin (2014) explain that gender is best understood in relation to sex. Sex is the biologically determined characteristics or functions of males and females, the physical and biological difference between male and female while gender means those characteristics and functions allocated to male and females. What it means is that although everyone is born with a certain sex—

either biologically male or female, except for inter-sexed individuals—no one is born with a gender as a part of one’s innate embodiment of personhood. Brand (1995) had explained that sex refers to the biological and anatomical features of an individual; gender refers to a socially constructed set of traits that are routinely given to men and women. Because gender is socially constructed, different gender performances may exist. Some performances of gender are more dominant than others.

From the moment a person is born, the formation of his or her gender identity begins. These gender identities are largely products of cultural values that are written on the “blank page” of the human body (Butler, 1990, p. 166). Gender distinctions shape the world, especially for the children who are still seeking gender identities. Bussey and Bandura (2004) assert that children learn that the world is largely organized around this differentiation and that their dress, skills, occupation, and daily activity will be governed by gender distinctions. Karinol, Reichman and Fund (2000) add that being labeled as a boy or girl “acts as a selective mechanism that assimilates gender-relevant information, objects, and behaviors” (p. 378).

Since gender is socially constructed, thereby subject to a cultural rulebook by which males and females are measured, then our conception of our own gender is heavily influenced by how our performance of being either a male or female matches up with the cultural norms. The cultural industries are constantly influencing the gender performance and building stereotypes by the way they portray each gender.

Many studies have been aimed at exploring the way men and women are portrayed in the media. Most of those studies point to a conclusion that women are described as sexual objects and passive participant, while positive characteristics of male are over-implied. But what exactly is stereotyping, what does it involve and how does it function? Stereotyping is a form of representation but a stereotypical representation will often be negative, inaccurate, limited and partial. A stereotype is a distorted, exaggerated or misleading representation of a person or group of people through the reduction of that person or group to a few essential characteristics (Hall, 2007). Stereotypes basically represent a set of ideas or a set of beliefs about people – an ideology – rather than people as they are. Itzin (1986, p. 128) notes that stereotypes are “deliberately misleading; they perform the function of creating attitudes which, by their very nature, are negative

attitudes.” They function as a form of propaganda; they are the language of ideology – the way it is communicated.’

Comprehensive gender studies which do not pay particular attention a gender but investigated how the media projected the two genders have found particular gender traits common in both television and film. Those kinds of studies are mostly of foreign origin, especially from developed economies. According to Wood (2000) there are four perennial themes of gender portrayal in the media. These themes demonstrate how media reflect and promote traditional arrangements between the sexes: women are caregivers and men are providers; men are the competent authorities who save women from their incompetence; women as subject to men’s sexual desire: women as victims and sex objects/men as aggressors; and women’s dependence and men’s independence.

Espinosa (2010) states that gender roles are prevalent in media, often portraying women as nurturing, gentle, cooperative, concerned with appearance, and sensitive to others; while men are viewed as logical, competitive, independent, assertive, financial providers, skilled in business. Women in media tend to be represented more negatively than men (Rouner, 2003). While men are perceived as hard workers, amusing, directive, and physically aggressive (Aubrey & Harrison, 2004), women are displayed as likeable, warm, submissive, passive, and weak (Dill & Thill, 2007; Ellis & Armstrong, 1989).

Women are also more likely than men to display empathic behaviors such as affection, sharing, giving, and concern for others (Glascock, 2001). Women are likely to be portrayed as sex objects in media (Morris, 2006 p. 78). According to Fareed (2012), the status of women in our society, especially in the cultural industry such as the media, has been very sympathetic since ages; they have never given the importance they deserved. Our male chauvinistic society has always been eager to use women but never ready to give them the high pedestal that they justify. Since the old ages women are defined as a commodity or an instrument of luxury. Sim and Suying (2001) state that the roles assigned to women in the media were most likely to be depicted as non-occupational, and that women are very often shown as being preoccupied with their personal appearance.

On television, male characters are more likely to be shown as having a job (Glascock, 2001; Signorielli & Bacue, 1999) and are more likely to be seen working (Signorielli & Kahlenberg,

2001). In addition to having jobs, male characters are also more likely than females to have leadership roles and power at work (Lauzen & Dozier, 2004). Female characters, in primetime programming are younger than their male counterparts (Gerbner, 1997; Glascock, 2001; Lauzen & Dozier, 1999; Signorielli & Bacue, 1999). Additionally, females are more likely than males to be married and/or have children (Glascock, 2001). Female characters in feature films are younger than male characters and are seen in more traditional roles, such as caregivers (Smith & Granados, 2009).

Talking about the social impact of media portrayal of gender, Lester and Ross (2003) and Gorham (2004) believe that stereotypes have the potential to produce hatred, violence, and misunderstanding. If we consider the number of media messages that are transmitted and consumed each day coupled with the assertion that media stereotypes actually reinforce and amplify personal stereotypes, there is certainly a huge probability that particularly harmful effects will ensue. In this way, the media can be said to exacerbate the problem of prejudice and discrimination. Concerning the portrayal of sex roles, Carter and Steiner (2004) note that past studies have found that the depiction of sex roles in the media have been incredibly narrow, with women often only being shown within the domestic private sphere, but with men being portrayed in a whole variety of different occupations within the public sphere.

Goode (1992) states that men enjoy an exploitative position that yields unearned profits in power, money and prestige. Furthermore, Hare-Mustin and Marecek (1994) maintain that men hold a dominant position in society that affords them control over meaning and the language of social definition. This has manifested itself in role definitions that limit the true choices available to women. These role definitions based on differential gender privileges serve to reinforce and maintain patriarchy as it is recreated perpetually in interactions in literature and in Nollywood video film culture. Patriarchy is a deep rooted societal ideology almost as old as time. By mental, social and cultural conditioning the female is framed into two extremes of a divide. On the one hand, there is the docile, submissive, accepting, never protesting, never questioning, and quiet model of a woman. This is the dream desire of man in a patriarchal society.

2.1.6 Major Issues in Masculinity Research

Connell (2000, 2001) explains that there have been growing library of studies from around the world, across a number of the social sciences, in which researchers have traced the construction of masculinity in a particular milieu or moment. Though each study is different, she identified common themes that are discussed in masculinity studies. Those theses form the bases of this sub-section.

2.1.6.1 Multiple masculinities

Connell (2001) states that historians and anthropologists have shown that there is no one pattern of masculinity that is found everywhere: different cultures, and different periods of history, construct masculinity differently. She cites that some cultures make heroes of soldiers, and regard violence as the ultimate test of masculinity; others look at soldiering with disdain and regard violence as contemptible. Some cultures regard homosexual sex as incompatible with true masculinity; others think no one can be a real man without having had homosexual relationships.

Large-scale multicultural societies there are likely to be multiple definitions of masculinity. More than one kind of masculinity can be found within a given cultural setting. Within any workplace, neighbourhood or peer group, there are likely to be different understandings of masculinity and different ways of “doing” masculinity. In the urban middle class, she continues, there is a version of masculinity organized around dominance (e.g. emphasising “leadership” in management), and another version organized around expertise (e.g. emphasising “professionalism” and technical knowledge).

2.1.6.2 Hierarchy and hegemony

This issue of hegemonic masculinity shall be more comprehensively discussed in the next section because of its significance in masculinity research. As a common theme discussed in major masculinity research, it is understood that different masculinities do not sit side by-side; there are definite relations between them.

Connell (2001) makes it clear that typically, some masculinities are more honoured than others. Some may be actively dishonoured, for example homosexual masculinities in modern Western

culture. Some are socially marginalized, for example the masculinities of disempowered ethnic minorities. Some are exemplary, taken as symbolizing admired traits, for example the masculinities of sporting heroes. The form of masculinity which is culturally dominant in a given setting is called “hegemonic masculinity”. She explains that “hegemonic” signifies a position of cultural authority and leadership, not total dominance; other forms of masculinity persist alongside. The hegemonic form need not be the most common form of masculinity.

Hegemonic masculinity is hegemonic not just in relation to other masculinities, but in relation to the gender order as a whole. It is an expression of the privilege men collectively have over women. The hierarchy of masculinities is an expression of the unequal shares in that privilege held by different groups of men.

2.1.6.3 Collective masculinities

The gender structures of a society define particular patterns of conduct as “masculine” and others as “feminine.” At one level, these patterns characterise individuals. Thus we say that a particular man (or woman) is masculine, or behaves in a masculine way. But these patterns also exist at the collective level. Masculinities are defined and sustained in institutions.

Masculinities are defined collectively in the workplace, as shown in industrial research; and in informal groups like street gangs, as shown in criminological research. Masculinity also exists impersonally in culture. Sociological research on sport has shown how an aggressive masculinity is created organizationally by the structure of organized sport, by its pattern of competition, its system of training and its steep hierarchy of levels and rewards. Images of this masculinity are circulated on an enormous scale by sports media; though most individuals fit very imperfectly into the slots thus created.

2.1.6.4 Active construction

Masculinities do not exist prior to social behaviour, either as bodily states or fixed personalities. Rather, masculinities come into existence as people act. They are accomplished in everyday conduct or organizational life, as patterns of social practice. A great deal of effort goes into the making of conventional masculinities. And this is true also of non-conventional masculinities.

2.1.6.5 Internal complexity

One of the key reasons why masculinities are not settled is that they are not simple, homogeneous patterns. Close-focus research on gender, both in psychoanalysis and ethnography, often reveals contradictory desires and logics. A man's active heterosexuality may exist as a thin emotional layer concealing a deeper homosexual desire. A boy's identification with men may coexist or struggle with identifications with women. The public enactment of an exemplary masculinity may covertly require actions that undermine it.

Masculinities may have multiple possibilities concealed within them. The complexity of desires, emotions or possibilities may not be obvious at first glance. But the issue is important, because these complexities are sources of tension and change in gender patterns.

2.1.6.6 Dynamics

From the fact that different masculinities exist in different cultures and historical epochs, we can deduce that masculinities are able to change. In the layering of masculinities we see one of the sources of change; and in the hierarchy of masculinities we see one of the motives. Historians have traced changes in masculinity as struggles for hegemony: for instance re-defining patterns of managerial masculinity in British manufacturing industry as economic and technological change re-arranged the balance of power (Roper, 1994).

According to Connell (2001, p. 146), to speak of the “dynamics” of masculinity is to acknowledge that particular masculinities are composed, historically, and may also be de-composed, contested and replaced. There is an active politics of gender in everyday life. Sometimes it finds spectacular public expression, in large-scale rallies or demonstrations. More often it is local and limited. But there is always a process of contestation and change.

2.1.7 The Concept or Theory of Hegemonic Masculinity

The concept of hegemonic masculinity has been used in gender studies since the early 1980s to explain men's power over women (Jewkes et al., 2015) as an analytical instrument to identify those attitudes and practices among men that perpetuate gender inequality, involving both men's domination over women and the power of some men over other (often minority groups of) men.

Hegemonic signifies a position of cultural authority and leadership, not total dominance; other forms of masculinity persist alongside.

The concept of hegemonic masculinity was formulated by Australian sociologist Raewyn Connell (1987) as part of the gender order theory to refer to those traits that various cultures ascribe to ‘real men’ and which not only set out such ‘real men’ from women and all other men, but also justify all men to generally be in a position of domination over women. On local and regional levels, hegemonic masculinity manifests itself in varying forms, and is constantly evolving, leading researchers to conceive the idea of multiple hegemonic masculinities. On a global scale, hegemonic masculinity is a representation of society’s ideal of how male behaviour should be. In reality, its function is to legitimate the social ascendancy of men over women in all aspects of life, which is evident in many societies all over the world.

Connell explains hegemonic masculinity as a practice that legitimizes men's dominant position in society and justifies the subordination of women, and other marginalized ways of being a man. Conceptually, hegemonic masculinity proposes to explain how and why men maintain dominant social roles over women, and other gender identities, which are perceived as “feminine” in a given society. Kareithi (2014) explains that hegemonic masculinity also emphasizes superiority of ‘manly’ men over the ‘not-so-manly’ men. This social ascendancy is often portrayed through religious practices, the mass media, business and even through government policies and practices.

Donaldson (1993) and Donaldson, Nilan and Howson (2006) argue that hegemonic masculinity derives from hegemony theory (Gramsci, 1971), which begins with the observation that power is unequally distributed in society between dominant, powerful groups, (the elite, comprised of mostly White, upper class, heterosexual men) and subordinate, less powerful groups (non-White, non-male, non-heterosexual, and non-upper class). This theory describes how the power of the dominant group is partly maintained and reproduced by the widespread circulation of ideas and beliefs that benefit the dominant group, called hegemonic (dominant) ideology.

It is clear that Gramsci’s (1971) hegemony theory only talks about the power relations between the dominant, powerful groups and the subordinate, less powerful groups but the hegemonic masculinity concept, according to Applerouth (2012) refers to “a pattern of practices that allows

men's dominance over women to continue" (p. 588). It is strictly an ideology that explains men's domination over women and the power of some men over other (often minority groups of) men. Connell and Messerschmidt (2005) describe hegemonic masculinity as "normative" and claim that hegemonic masculinity requires that all men position themselves in relation to it even if they cannot embody it (p. 832).

Connell (2005), in further explanation to the concept of hegemonic masculinity, proposes that there are different types of masculinities, which are related to each other in diverse ways (relations of hegemony, subordination, complicity, and marginalization). Among these, hegemonic masculinity emerges as a key concept. It is defined as the "configuration of gender practice which embodies the currently accepted answer to the problem of the legitimacy of patriarchy, which guarantees the dominant position of men and the subordination of women" (p. 2). In other words, it represents the ideal of what it is to be a man in a given society. However, it is not a static entity: it changes over time and is continuously challenged by men and women who oppose it (Connell & Messerschmidt, 2005).

Connell (1987) in Jewkes and Morrell (2012) explains hegemonic masculinity as a set of values, established by men in power that functions to include and exclude, and to organize society in gender unequal ways. It combines several features: a hierarchy of masculinities, differential access among men to power (over women and other men), and the interplay between men's identity, men's ideals, interactions, power, and patriarchy. Jewkes et al. (2015) clarify that hegemonic masculinity refer to those traits that various cultures ascribe to 'real men' and which not only set out such 'real men' from women and all other men, but also justify all men to generally be in a position of domination over women.

According to Connell (1995), at any time, one form of masculinity rather than others is culturally exalted. Hegemonic masculinity can be defined as the configuration of gender practice which embodies the currently accepted answers to the problem of the legitimacy of patriarchy, which guarantees (or is taken to guarantee) the dominant position of men and the subordination of women. Bederman (1995) calls manliness "a standard to live up to, an ideal of male perfectibility to be achieved" (p. 27). However, even if all men cannot embody the dominant form of masculinity, all men are assumed to benefit from it (MacKinnon, 2003; Malin, 2005).

Oates and Durham (2004) claim that hegemonic masculinity “serves to equate whiteness, heterosexuality, athleticism and (of course) males with power” (p. 23 303). In order to uncover hegemonic masculinity as a set of assumptions about what it means to be male, masculinity must be made visible and be understood as a social construction instead of natural (Pennell, 2002). Masculinity is therefore not just a set of stereotypes about men but is also a system of power that is conferred upon those who embody masculine identity. The distinction between power and masculinity can be difficult to make because being male and being masculine have long been the standard against which gender and social power are measured (Reynolds, 2002).

Jewkes et al (2015) explains that hegemonic masculinity is a cultural ideal of manhood, which is rewarded by women’s interests, attentions and efforts to replicate this ideal in their male relatives and associates. He continues that another understanding of hegemonic masculinity that has been debated and examined is that it is a problem not only for women, but also for men. The system that keeps men in a collectively dominant position over women and in competitive relations to other men comes at a cost for men in terms of their health and quality of life. They conclude that hegemonic masculinity identifies how gender power operates at multiple levels; it provides an overarching framework for understanding how gender inequalities are produced and reproduced, both in the long term and the quotidian. He identifies hegemonic masculinity as a concept that accommodates fluidity and dynamism, which is why it is not easy to recognize stasis or movement.

Hegemonic masculinity is a model that describes how men are expected to develop characteristics that demonstrate power, strength, bravery, fearlessness, virility, rationality and competitiveness (UKaid, 2015). According to the hegemonic masculinity model, men who adopt these traits can assert their (supposed) superiority over women and consolidate their general position of dominance over them (physically, intellectually and sexually). At the same time, men who do not ascribe to the paradigm of hegemonic masculinity or aspects of it, and who show ‘feminine’ characteristics (e.g. sensitivity, fearfulness, emotionality, subordination and passivity) are invariably ridiculed and viewed as inferior.

The essence of reviewing hegemonic masculinity in this study is to identify its contrast with hypermasculinity. Beasley (2008) stressed it is worth noting that hyper- and hypo-masculinity refer not so much to political legitimation as to the degree of particular characteristics that at any one

time may be associated with normative manliness. Thus it is possible for an individual or group to exhibit what is deemed hyper-masculinity but not to be constituted as an ideal, not to mobilize legitimation. Hegemonic masculinity “embodies the currently most honoured way of being a man, it requires all other men to position themselves in relation to it and it ideologically legitimates the global subordination of women to men” (Connell and Messerschmidt, 2005, p.832).

2.1.8 Gender-Equitable and Non-Gender-Equitable Masculinities

The historical and cultural frameworks of individual societies determine the measure to which specific aspects of hegemonic masculinity are deemed desirable (or not) and their subsequent expression. As a consequence, the assimilation by men of those norms associated with hegemonic masculinity leads to the development of non-gender equitable masculinities, encouraging men to feel superior over women and to be aggressive, dominating and violent towards women in particular. On the other hand, the expression of gender equitable masculinities (whose features may include sensitivity, tenderness, care giving and cooperation) is indicative of the rejection of the hegemonic masculinity paradigm and its harmful consequences (UKaid, 2015).

In his study on gender equitable boys in a gender inequitable world, Baker (2000) explains the desirable attributes of gender equitable norms to include being respectful and caring in one’s relationships with women or men, being involved in the lives of one’s children and not using violence toward a partner are all arguably positive influences in men’s lives. He continues that the term “gender equitable” to refer to young men who: are respectful in their relationships with young women and currently seek relationships based on equality and intimacy rather than sexual conquest and believe that men and women have equal rights, and that women have as much sexual desire and “right” to sexual agency as do men; seek to be involved fathers, for those who are already fathers, meaning that they believe that they should take financial and at least some care giving responsibility for their children. They have shown this involvement by providing at least some child care, showing concern for providing financially for the child, and/or take an active role in caring for their child’s health; assume some responsibility for reproductive health issues. This includes taking the initiative to discuss reproductive health concerns with their partner, using condoms or assisting their partner in acquiring or using a contraceptive method; and do not use violence against women in their intimate relationships, and are opposed to violence against

women. This may include young men who report having been violent toward a female partner in the past, but they currently believe that violence against women is not acceptable behavior, and who do not condone this behaviour by other men.

However, UKaid (2015) maintains that equitable and inequitable masculinities are not mutually exclusive in individual men. In some areas of life and relationships, with regard to violence for example, a man may manifest attitudes and behaviour that are gender equitable. The same man, however, on sexuality issues, may adopt some attitudes and behaviour that are non-gender equitable. Similarly, gender equitable attitudes related to a particular issue in an individual man, may not always be reflected in his behaviour. A man might consider violence against women to be wrong but simultaneously use emotional violence in his own intimate partner relationship, or decide not to intervene when faced with other men's violence against women. Likewise, life cycle stages and personal histories, as well as culture and religion, constantly influence the assimilation of gender equitable or non-gender equitable attitudes and behaviours.

2.1.9 Films

Film is an art of audio-visual storytelling; a medium of communication rich with social implications, created within different social, historical and cultural contexts (Career View, 2011). Also called a movie, motion picture, theatrical film, or photoplay, it is a series of still images that, when shown on a screen, create the illusion of moving images. This optical illusion causes the audience to perceive continuous motion between separate objects viewed in rapid succession. According to Neale (2000), the central to the practices of the film industry is the construction of a narrative image.

A film is created by photographing actual scenes with a motion-picture camera; by photographing drawings or miniature models using traditional animation techniques; by means of CGI and computer animation; or by a combination of some or all of these techniques, and other visual effects. The contemporary definition of films is the art of simulating experiences to communicate ideas, stories, perceptions, feelings, beauty or atmosphere by the means of recorded or programmed moving images along with other sensory stimulations (Severny, 2013).

Films were originally recorded onto plastic film through a photochemical process and then shown through a movie projector onto a large screen. Contemporary films are now often fully digital through the entire process of production, distribution, and exhibition, while films recorded in a photochemical form traditionally included an analogous optical soundtrack (a graphic recording of the spoken words, music and other sounds that accompany the images which runs along a portion of the film exclusively reserved for it, and is not projected).

Films are cultural artifacts created by specific cultures. They reflect those cultures, and, in turn, affect them. Film is considered to be an important art form, a source of popular entertainment, and a powerful medium for educating—or indoctrinating—citizens. The visual basis of film gives it a universal power of communication. Some films have become popular worldwide attractions through the use of dubbing or subtitles to translate the dialog into other languages. Some have criticized the film industry's glorification of violence (Rampal, 2001) and have perceived in it the prevalence of a negative attitude toward women (Simmons, 2017)

Film is a means of socialization, i.e. the process and experience that help the individual to become sensitive to the expectation of other members of the society, their values and culture. Film is an important tool in building cultural institutions, and reinforcing cultural pride. Film is a means of information, education and cultural development of the masses. It is a means of communication and comprehension. Film could be used to heal the psychological wounds created by slavery and colonialism and to provide moral upliftment. Film is like photography; it is not an accident but a concept. That is, film is a manipulation of the viewer through its language of images; it is the recycling of reality through the way it is presented.

2.1.10 Nollywood Films: An Overview

The word Nollywood is the generic name for the Nigerian film industry. It was coined following the style of Hollywood (the American film industry) and Bollywood (the Indian film Industry). According to Okome (2007), it is a designation that points to its similarities with Hollywood. Opeyemi (2008) says that by definition, Nollywood is Nigeria's movie industry by Nigerian production teams for the Nigerian people. Kunzler (2007, p. 1) explains that Nollywood is an

industry that “developed out of a context related to domestic and international cultural, economic, and political environments.” It is heterogeneous in nature and can roughly be divided into Yoruba, Hausa and Igbo video films which designate their production centers in the South-West, North and South-East of Nigeria respectively.

Talking about the strides of the film industry in Nigeria, Liston (2014) reports that Nollywood is Africa's largest movie industry in terms of value and the number of movies produced per year and The London Independent (May 15, 2010) ascribes Nollywood as the second largest film industry in the world in number of annual film productions, placing it ahead of the United States and behind only India; and the third largest in terms of overall revenue generated (Brown, 2014). Since the early 1990s, the Nollywood movie industry has churned out thousands of titles and has successfully brought to limelight many talented Nigerian actors and actresses. According to the Nigerian Films Video and Censors Board (2014), some 300 producers churn out movies at an astonishing rate—somewhere between 500 and 1,000 a year.

Nollywood films are produced mostly in English language. They are also produced in Igbo, Yoruba and Hausa languages as well as in some of the minority languages such as Ijaw, Efik, Itsekiri, etc. But, according to Ojukwu and Ezenandu (2012), the use of the English Language as the main communication tool and the marketing strategies has facilitated the expansion of Nollywood films beyond the shores of the African continent. Nollywood has over the years become a world phenomenon, as its movies are being sold in Ghana, Togo, Kenya, Uganda and South Africa as well as Jamaica, USA and the UK to name a few. The popularity of Nigerian films now stretches far beyond the country's borders.

Talking about the major themes of Nollywood films, Ojukwu and Ezenandu (2012, p. 22) stress that “through an amalgam of Nigerian narrative techniques (African storylines) and Western technology, the industry documents and re-creates sociopolitical and cultural events that occurred within and beyond the country borders.” Many Nollywood movies have themes that deal with the moral dilemmas facing modern Africans. Some movies promote the Christian and Islamic faiths, and some movies are overtly evangelical. Even though, the filmmakers make films essentially to make money, Akomfrah (2006, p. 282) argues that they are systematically being ‘guided by the tenets of African nationalism and cultural identity which help them address local concerns.’

Akangbe (2008 p. 207) posits that the Nigerian video film is “recreation of society, and a megaphone for projecting the failings, triumphs, sentiments, aspirations, history, changes, interests, idiosyncrasies, beliefs etc of the society.” It is clear that the mass media play crucial roles in the socialization and conditioning of members of the society to accepted or expected roles and behaviour. The Nigerian movie industry has continued to help in reflecting the ways of life of Nigerians. This, according to Ayakoroma (2008, p. 82), is an indication that “Nigerian video films are deep-rooted socially.”

Nollywood has grown in leaps and bounds over the years. It however has been criticized in terms of the techniques, prevalent themes and certain portrayals. Ogunleye (2003, p. 6) states that one of the major criticisms of this new industry is its thematic obsession with the occult world (juju, black magic, sorcery, ritual murder, witchcraft, etc.), obscenity, prostitution, and “money worship.” Nigerian video films, along with their Ghana counterparts, have been described as a mixture of “horror, magic and melodrama.” The wide range of subjects which Nigerian video films, in their social commitment deal with include politics, history, communality, family relationship and love affairs, to mention a few.

Ebewo (2007) focuses on the challenges the industry has faced for the thematic obsession and repetitive themes for storylines. He maintains that the Nigerian film industry is viewed in both positive and negative ways. Some find the plots to be highly repetitive and unrealistic, while others see them as expressions of the African culture. For many years, Nigerian films have been based on storylines showing –constant tragedy, romance, drama and comedy that arouses the viewers mind. Whether the main character is going through constant tragedy to end up triumphant or the characters are caught in a love triangle, there are always high drama plots to keep the audience interested. Within these themes many of the films include multiple storylines combined into one film. Also, widespread pirating of foreign and domestic videotapes discourages the entry of licensed distributors.

Researchers and commentators have also criticized Nollywood films for representations that portray Nigerians as “backwards.” Critics have also faulted Nigerian firms for their admiration of Western commercial values that are “often estranged from African realities and purposes. Nollywood has also been criticized for its conventional depictions of gender roles.

Nigeria's Nollywood is counted among the major business centres of film making in the world. Alamu (2010) remarks that Nigeria's Nollywood has been viewed as cultural products of the Nation, and the global attention currently enjoyed by it is due to efforts by producers to create a distinct film tradition. The industry has advanced by virtue of the individual efforts of dominant producers and marketers in spite of its burgeoning challenges such as the problems of unabated piracy and the indifference of the government which has denied it the status of a foreign exchange. The industry has also provided employment for the teeming Nigerian population especially the youth.

Ejinkoye (2009) highlights some of the challenges faced by Nollywood. First, the editing is poor. Then, techniques used to signal a transition from one location to another, such as the dissolve and superimposition, are blatantly abused, and the timing of the shots is wrong. The Nigerian industry lacks basic lighting equipment, and in many video films, very high or very low lighting affects the quality of the color. With no deliberate attempt to create a dramatic effect, a good number of the films contain shadows that could have been eliminated with proper lighting. Piracy is a serious problem for the Nigerian video filmmakers. The producers allege that the works are usually pirated, leading to low sales of the original copies.

The rising popularity of Nollywood, the Nigerian film industry, is increasing the level of scholarship with several researchers investigating the genres, production, distribution and challenges faced by the films within the country, region and Diasporas. They also highlight the revenue generated annually, the number of films produced, as well as the themes and storylines of Nigerian films (Ebewo, 2007; Haynes & Okome, 1998, Obayiuwana, 2011). Literature on Nollywood also ranges from the historical aspects of the industry to the themes, plots, production and distribution of films for local and global audiences. The films have been a source of scholarly expressing and understanding the Nigerian culture as well as an influence on the lifestyles of Nigerian people.

Despite the many perceptions Nollywood carriers, the industry manages to defy the odds with new thought provoking films and high production quality. Nollywood films are a staple in many African homes. Haynes and Okome (1998) discuss the evolution of Nigerian film production and its rise to popular culture. It has become a necessity for many African families and has grown into

popular media for the country. It is evident that films that include relatable scenarios and traditions of the country have influenced the lifestyle of many Africans. Filmmakers, for the most part, have been educated self-conscious artists who have social or political motivations that occasionally influence their films.

2.1.11 A Condensed History of the Nigerian Film Industry

There are so many versions of the history of the film industry in Nigeria. Beginning from the origin of the name, Nollywood has an uncertain origin. What is certain is that it was derived from acronyms such as Hollywood and Bollywood. Haynes (2005) highlights that the name, Nollywood, apparently appeared for the first time in print in an article by Matt Steinglass in New York Times in 2002. Nollywood, according to Ojukwu and Ezenandu (2012), grew from the rich traditional culture of Nigeria into a supposedly modern internationally recognized industry. Prior to the emergence of Nollywood in the early nineties, theatre and television stations were primarily the medium used by a lot of theatre artists.

Ekwuasi (1984) recounts that the Nigeria's first contact with cinema was in 1903, at the instance of Herbert Macaulay, a foremost nationalist who invited the Balboa and Company who was then doing an exhibition tour of silent films on the West African Coast to Nigeria. The films were shown at the Glover Memorial Hall, Lagos in August, 1903. The success of the Balboa venture paved the way for an influx of European film exhibitors to Nigeria. Itam (2000) notes that shortly after the exhibition tour of the Balboa venture, the colonial government took interest and brought in a lot of films. Similarly, Uchegbu (1992) states that the Nigerian audiences' first experience in film screening was in 1903 at the Glover Memorial Hall. Ekwuazi (1987) narrates that film was introduced in by a European merchant; but it took the combined efforts of the colonial administration and the church to sustain the industry.

According to Uwah (2011), there were a group of Nigerian filmmakers who carried out film production practice by themselves without Government sponsorship between 1960s and 1980s and due to the high cost of production had to give it up. For many years then, Nigeria remained without film productions and people resorted to stage dramas. Some of those filmmakers included Ola Balogun, Hebert Ogungbe, Eddie Ugboma, Ladi Ladebo, Ola Balogun, U.S.A Galadima, Wole

Soyinka, among others. However, with the oil boom, some of these individuals became involved again in the production of indigenous films. By 1970, the first indigenous feature film was produced in Nigeria: *Kongi's Harvest*. It was however directed by an American and it featured many foreigners as crew members.

According to Onabanjo and M'bayo (2009), the popular view is that the Nigerian movie industry actually started with the 1992 production of 'Living in Bondage' by Ken Nebue but the debate on whether a film industry exists in Nigeria or not, had already been going on. Today, video film production is a multi-billion-naira industry which provides a source of livelihood for many people both at home and abroad. The industry has also produced many "stars" as well as its own international events.

Liston (2014) reports that the Nigerian film industry is worth 853.9 billion naira (5.1 billion US dollars) as at 2014 and produces hundreds of home videos and films per annum. Nigerian cinema is Africa's largest movie industry in terms of value and the number of movies produced per year. Although Nigerian films have been produced since the 1960s, the rise of affordable digital and filming technologies has stimulated the country's film and video industry.

Essentially, it can also be argued that fundamental factors that gave inspiration to the rise of Nollywood are: 'citizen journalism'. This refers to the individual zeal of some Nigerians to empower themselves in order to make their voices heard by the general public (Okome, 2007). The success of this industry also comes from what Nwachukwu (2003) identifies as the drive for 'commercial viability.' This is because while the new video film industry places a high premium on entertainment, it also seeks the pleasure of viewers in order to recoup expenses from their sales by encoding what audiences desire to see. Nollywood's historical emergence according to Adesokan (2006) hinges on the neoliberal deregulations of many economies in Africa that brought changes in the use of technology, especially of the digital kind, which is open to reformatting in quite imaginative ways.

2.2 Empirical Review

Previous studies have successfully examined gender roles in many popular forms of media. Those studies are quite extensive and cover many different forms of media, for example: prime-time

television, movies, cartoons, music, games and much more recently the internet where new forms of media are being produced (Ottoson & Cheng, 2012; Okunna, 2002). However, past and ongoing theorizations and studies on gender in Nigeria, as the researcher found out in the literature review, have paid a lot of attention to the portrayal of women in the media. Ogunyemi (2014) observes that the motif of genderisation and social themes in most studies in the Nigerian intellectual space is the female gender, and the male gender has too often been ignored. UKaid (2014) also stresses that few studies on gender and masculinities exist in African countries and, amongst these; even fewer that analyse representations of men and masculinities in the mass media. This is backed up by the view of Baker and Ricardo (2005) who found that in most cases, gender studies in Africa are confined almost exclusively to the disadvantages that women and girls face.

For these reasons, this section reviews some previous studies mostly of foreign origin that were conducted on the portrayal of men and also includes some gender studies in Nigeria that pattern to the portrayal of women in the media. The essence is to show that this work, like every research work, is built from previous gender studies; it also highlights the lacuna that the researcher intends to fill in this study.

2.2.1 Media and Masculinities: The role of key media outlets in Nigeria in shaping perceptions of masculinities; Voices 4 Change, UKaid-sponsored study (2015).

The study set out to explore the influence of Nigeria's blossoming media on the perceptions and behaviours of boys, men, women and girls around masculinity and assess its impact on the continuing gender divisions that characterise so much of life in this country.

The study examines the links between the media's promotion of unequal gender power relations based on stereotypical images of men and women and men's expressions of dominance, control and violence in their everyday relationships with women and girls. It also explores media representations of men and women in decision-making and leadership roles. Finally, it identifies the factors that support or constrain media professionals in promoting gender equitable masculine images and profiles selected mass media programmes that endeavour to reflect and promote gender equality.

Various methods were used for the study: Individual in-Depth Interviews (IDI) and Focus Group Discussions (FDG) with editors, producers, presenters, reporters from major media outlets in Nigeria; Interpretative Textual Analysis (ITA) to identify and analyse gender social representations, particularly those portraying men, in advertisements on telecommunications, alcohol, beverages, and health in five newspapers during one month; Interpretative Textual Analysis of masculine messages and portrayal in “Mr & Mrs” cartoon series in the Vanguard Newspapers for one-month; Content analysis (CA) on articles on leadership and violence in five newspapers during one month; and Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) on seven Nollywood films: four which mention explicitly “man/men” in their title and three films among those considered best in 2014.

Key findings show that some media programmes in Nigeria mirror, or have the potential to mirror, gender equitable images of men, women and gender relations; gender equitable images of men and women in local media in Nigeria impact on audiences by providing role models considered worthy of emulation, inspiring them to overcome challenges and be successful in chosen career fields, encouraging them to assimilate equitable gender values, and attitudes and behaviours and shun non-gender equitable values; Nigeria’s local media news and entertainment outlets promote stereotypical and non-gender equitable images and messages about men and masculinities in a myriad of ways, from use of double standards when reporting on the gender of victims and perpetrators of Violence Against Women and Girls to promotion of dominant masculinities in advertisements; local media outlets promote representations that convey male dominance and leadership in Nigeria. They also tend to exclude women from decision-making and leadership in news reporting activities, and in media outlets’ hierarchies and environments; local media and entertainment portrayal of masculinity reflects and promotes unequal power relations between men and women by presenting Violence Against Women and Girls in news reports as isolated events rather than in relation to men’s power over and control of women, equating masculinity in cinema and in cartoons with the need for control and dominance, under-representing women in leadership news reports and using stereotypical images on gender and leadership to frame leadership stories; and media professionals are constrained from promoting gender-equitable masculinities by a range of factors that include: prevailing social norms, professional hierarchies and media political

economy. Meanwhile, legislative and regulatory frameworks dealing with gender equality issues in the media are weak and ineffectively enforced.

It is concluded that the media, in general, promotes men's dominance and leadership. The study found that women in decision making and leadership roles are underrepresented in the media and there is little reference to the capacity of women to fulfill these roles. Instead the media projects and reinforces traditional non-equitable gender identities and roles assigned to men and women. News stories on gender-based violence generally do not deconstruct or challenge patriarchal norms and tend to portray such incidents as isolated events. Damaging stereotypes (in print and broadcast media) are sometimes implicit, on other occasions, particularly in cinema, cartoons and some advertising; they are both deliberate and explicit.

2.2.2 Young Men and the Construction of Masculinity in Sub-Saharan Africa: Implications for HIV/AIDS, Conflict, and Violence, Gary Barker & Christine Ricardo, The World Bank sponsored Social Development Papers on Conflict Prevention and Reconstruction, Paper No. 26 / June 2005

This report explores the constructions of manhood in Africa and the implications for conflict and post-conflict recovery, and HIV/AIDS. The aim of this study is to explore what a gender perspective means when applied to young men in Africa focusing on conflict, violence and HIV/AIDS. This paper argues for applying a more sophisticated gender analysis related to conflict and to HIV/AIDS to examine how men and women, and boys and girls, are made vulnerable by rigid notions of manhood and gender hierarchies. The paper's central question is: What does a gender perspective mean when applied to young men in sub-Saharan Africa as related to conflict and HIV/AIDS?

The authors: (i) reviewed literature on men and masculinities, conflict and HIV/AIDS in sub-Saharan Africa; (ii) explores the construction of manhoods in Africa and argues for the application of a more sophisticated gender analysis that also includes men and youth; (iii) consulted with colleague organizations to identify promising program examples that apply a gender perspective to work with young men;

Methodologically, the study carried out 50 key informant interviews with staff at organizations working with young men in Botswana, Nigeria, South Africa and Uganda; and (v) carried out 23 focus group discussions and interviews with young men in Nigeria, South Africa and Uganda.

It was found that two of the most pressing social issues in Africa—conflict and HIV/AIDS—have direct links to gender and the social construct of masculinity. Nonetheless, most gender analyses of conflict in the Africa region focus on how sexual violence is used against women and girls, or on the relatively small number of women and girls involved as combatants. Reports on conflict, for example, generally conclude that those who use weapons are usually men, and mostly young men, and those who suffer and survive the consequences of violence and conflict are women and girls.

Similarly, in analyses of HIV/AIDS in Africa, most reports focus on how women are made vulnerable by the sexual behavior of men, often using an overly simplistic dichotomy that men always hold power in sexual relationships, and that women are powerless. Without a doubt, too many women and girls have been made vulnerable by the behavior of men and boys in conflict settings and in sexual relationships. However, in the development literature in general, and in many policy statements related to gender, African men, young and old, are presented in simplistic and overtly negative terms, and gender as it relates to men is ignored.

The authors concluded that there are pluralities of masculinities in Africa. Versions of manhood in Africa are socially constructed, fluid over time and in different settings, and plural. The key requirement to attain manhood in Africa is achieving some level of financial independence, employment or income, and subsequently starting a family. Older men also have a role in holding power over younger men and thus in defining manhood in Africa. Initiation practices or rites of passage are important factors in the socialization of boys and men throughout the region. For young men in Africa, as for young men worldwide, sexual experience is frequently associated with initiation into adulthood and achieving a socially recognized manhood.

2.2.3 An Analysis of Hyper-Masculinity in Magazine Advertisements, Megan Lea Vokey, 2008

The study analyzed the content of images in men's magazine advertisements for portrayals of hyper-masculinity. Because of the nature of the study, content analysis was employed in this study as the design. The sample of magazines was based on readership demographic information. Two issues of eight magazines targeting men differentiated by age, education, and household income published in November 2007 and April 2008 were analyzed.

Advertisements containing images of men were coded for hyper-masculine traits using a coding instrument based on the Hypermasculinity Inventory (Mosher and Sirkin, 1984). This study addressed the following research questions: (a) what proportion of the advertisements display hypermasculinity and (b) is hyper-masculinity inversely related to readership demographics of age, education, and household income? It was hypothesized that advertisements targeted at younger men, less educated men, and less affluent men would exhibit more hypermasculine traits than advertisements targeted at men who were older, more educated, and/or more affluent.

Data analysis proceeded in two steps. In the first step, the proportion of the advertisement that depicted hyper-masculinity overall, as well as the proportion of advertisements that depicted each of the hyper-masculinity traits individually, were calculated. In the second step, regression analyses were conducted to determine the relationship of age, education, and income to hyper-masculine traits, both overall and individually. It was found that, overall, 56% of advertisements in the sample (N: 527) depicted at least one hyper-masculine trait. The hypotheses were supported by the multiple regression results. Age, education, and household income each were significant predictors of hyper-masculinity in the advertisements. Of the three predictors, age accounted for most of the variance in hyper-masculinity. The societal implications of the findings are discussed.

2.2.4 Rise of the 'homo erotica'? Portrayal of women and gender role stereotyping in movies: analysis of two Nigerian movies, Omoniyi Adeyemi Adewoye, Agboola Odesanya and Abdulmutallib A. Abubakar (2014)

The rationale for the study is that over time, the role of mass media as agents of socialization has attracted an array of criticisms from different segments of the society. To social psychologists, the images portrayed in the mass media, often times, alter people's perception of social realities and

are believed to play significant roles in stimulating anti-social behaviours such as crime, delinquency and violence. To critical feminists, the mass media are seen as agents of male chauvinism, systematically deployed for the perpetuation of a male dominated socio-cultural, political and economic order through the portrayal and continuous reinforcement of negative gender role stereotypes of women.

This study is therefore designed to analyse the forms and pattern of portrayal of women and gender role stereotypes in selected Nollywood movies. Two movies – *Ije* (2012) and *Mr. and Mrs.* (2012) – were selected using purposive sampling technique and content-analysed. Specifically, the study set out to analyze the forms in which women are portrayed in selected Nollywood movies and the patterns of gender role stereotypes inherent in such portrayals and to examine the extent to which the identified forms of portrayal and stereotype patterns conform to or reinforce widely held beliefs and stereotypes about women in the larger Nigerian socio-cultural setting. The collection and analysis of data for this study by content analysis, since the questions that are being raised are primarily those relating to the amount and nature of the content of those films i.e. the quantity and quality of variables that make up the entire content.

Findings revealed that women were generally portrayed in the movies as sex objects and objects of erotic gaze for men, domestic servants, “the weaker sex”, “the wicked mother-in-laws” and working class women as insubordinate wives and uncaring mothers, among other negative forms of portrayals. It also found that the forms of portrayal and stereotypes of women in the movies reviewed fit into and can reinforce widely held social beliefs and gender role expectations from women in the larger Nigerian socio-cultural environment.

2.2.5 Gender Reporting In Nigerian Newspapers: Content Analytic Study of the Guardian, Vanguard, Daily Champion and Daily Sun, Inoma Anyanwu, Ozoemena (2007)

This study examined gender reporting in Nigerian newspapers. The primary objective was to analyse how the two gender groups were represented in reported news stories in the Nigerian dailies selected for this study. This study, therefore, addressed the following research questions: (i) are men and women equally represented in news stories published in the Nigerian newspapers?

(ii) what is the nature of stories reported about men and women in Nigerian newspapers? and (iii) are men or women misrepresented in any way in news stories contained in Nigerian newspapers? The study design adopted was content analysis. Four newspapers – The Guardian, Vanguard, Daily Sun and Daily Champion published in 2004 and 2005 were sampled and publications were selected per newspaper for each year using systematic random sampling technique. Coding sheet was used to obtain data for the study and the data obtained was analysed using frequency distribution and percentages. The results showed that the female gender group is under-reported in the selected newspapers compared to the male gender group.

There is a clear imbalance in the representation of both gender groups in reported stories in the selected newspapers used in this research. Men appeared more often in published stories. This is obviously expected since men occupy most of the important public positions, while there is an underrepresentation of women as they are involved more in the private and domesticated spheres of life. Thus, women are systematically positioned in the back pages most times which is where marginal stories belong. In sum, Nigerian journalists should ensure that women are not under-represented in reported news stories. They should be gender sensitive in their coverage of news stories.

2.2.6 Nigerian Women's Perception And Responses To Gender Based Nollywood Movies: A Study Of Women In South East, Nigeria, Ifeoma Vivian Dunu And Cornelius Aghadiogwu Ukwueze, International Journal of Advancements in Research & Technology, Volume 4, Issue 7, July -2015

This is a study of women from different socio cultural backgrounds in south eastern Nigeria and sought to determine how and in what ways, these greater number of women, especially those in rural communities, negotiate or perhaps either reject or accept their identities as given in Nollywood. Essentially, the specific objectives include the following: to establish Nigerian women's level of exposure to gender based Nollywood movies; to determine Nigerian women's perceptions and disposition to gendered portrayals in the movies and to explore their responses as well as the extent at which they may have been affected by such portrayals.

A mixed method of 'Survey' and 'Focus Group Discussion', were employed whereas the 'Cultivation' and 'Deconstruction' theories served as the reception frameworks to couch these

reception. While ‘Cultivation’ determines the women’s cultivation and acceptance of their portrayals as reality, ‘Deconstruction’ looks at their possible rejection and dissidence of same. Findings demonstrate that the women aside being widely exposed to the movies identified the negative female stereotypes and though accepted being ‘entertained’ and influenced by looks of most female characters, upheld that their attitudes, beliefs, goals, ideologies and relations towards other women were not influenced. What came out quite distinct is the women’s perception of these films as media constructions and not realities and their distancing themselves from such portrayals, even in their relationships with one other thereby calling to question the assumed powerful and uniform effects of media messages and validates the notion of the active audience.

2.2.7 Class and Gender Representation in Nollywood Movies. Mafoya Dossoumon, 2013

The basic aim of this study was to examine class and gender representations through textual analysis of a sample of films retrieved from the website of the largest Nollywood streaming service, irokoTV. In order to investigate the patterns in class and gender representations, the similarities in portrayals, the instances of stereotypes, and the value assumptions in terms of who has power, the following research questions were posed: (1) What class stereotypes are portrayed in Nollywood films? (2) What gender stereotypes are portrayed in Nollywood films? (3) What hegemonic ideas of power are portrayed in Nollywood films as a result of class and gender representations?

The study uses what the author called an exposure approach to select a sample of convenience of the top 5 films most attended to by the audience on iROKOTv and relies on close reading and a distancing technique called the “commutation test” to discuss the meaning of class and gender representations in the films. Basically, the study did a qualitative content analysis.

Findings indicate that even when they appear to subvert dominant ideologies, the films still reinforce long established societal norms about the importance of wealth and female gender stereotypes such as submissiveness in domestic households.

The Nollywood films in this study appear at first glance to be harmless melodramas that entertain the masses but beneath the surface of melodramatic tales, ideologies can be found that reinforce the status quo and keep the masses in check. Even when they appear to subvert dominant

ideologies, Nollywood films still reinforce long established societal norms. The films in this study emphasize wealth and represent female gender stereotypes such as the “wicked” woman in domestic households. Overwhelmingly, the films are about the domestic lives of upper and middle class families and the aspirations of the working class. Women’s roles are mostly portrayed in domestic settings where the ideal woman is a mother, housewife, or other related roles. At the same time, men are depicted mostly as successful businessmen or down on their luck business men who have to contend with the vengeful wife or mother in law. When they are portrayed as successful in business, women are often depicted in a negative stereotypical manner. They are portrayed as being overly harsh and oppressive of their own families. A successful woman thus becomes a “wicked” woman. A successful woman’s husband becomes a victim of his wife and his wife’s success. His own failures in business are explained away as bad luck as the plot narratives zoom in on his wife’s wickedness.

Men somehow always manage to lose their jobs or business leaving their wives to be the sole breadwinners. This situation always leads to tension between the husband and wife. The wife despises the husband for being unable to sustain the upper or middle class lifestyle the family has grown used to living while the husband is portrayed as the victim of a vengeful wife. The implication of this narrative is that wives resent their economic dependence on husbands. The minute, they get economic independence as a result of their husband’s “bad luck,” wives will exercise their full power. In cases where the wife is supportive of the husband during hard times, the mother-in-law takes over the role of the “wicked” woman. The films spread the message that power inherently resides with men in Nigerian society solely as a result of their gender. The only way a woman has power is when she makes more money than her husband and her husband is unemployed. However, the overarching ideology is that power in the hands of women in a domestic household leads to abuse of men and ultimately ends in tragedy. The message is that women cannot handle power in a domestic household. Power goes to their head.

Gender representations in the films in this study contain persistent stereotypical casting of female characters who challenge the dominant ideology. These women are portrayed as wicked. In a domestic household, the ideal woman is docile and submissive to the man. When female characters take initiative and find the resources to transform and self-determine their lives, the films depict

their success as impossible without a man's help thus somewhat negating the very idea of self-determination for women. Speaking of self-determination, when the idea of a woman's success being dependant on a man's help is extracted from the narratives, Nollywood films can actually serve as encouragement to women that they can be anything they dream if they take their destinies into their own hands.

2.2.8 Patriarchy, male dominance, the role and women empowerment in Nigeria Abidemi R. Asiyanbola, International Union for the Scientific Study of Population (IUSSP/UIESP) XXV International Population Conference Tours, France, 18-23, 2005

In the paper, the nature of male dominance and roles in Nigerian family is empirically analyzed and discussed. The data used in the paper was obtained from a questionnaire survey of 233 households in Ibadan city, Nigeria between November 1999 and April 2000.

Information was collected on some socio-economic variables which include age, income, educational level, household size, number of children in the household, age of the youngest child, number of cars in the household, family type, religion, and presence of house help in the household. Information was also collected on involvement daily in the following domestic activities: cooking, clearing the house and the surroundings, fetching water, getting rid of household wastes, and shopping.

ANOVA, paired samples 't' test and correlation statistical techniques were used to analyze the data. The result of the study shows that there is no significant intra-urban variation in male dominance within domestic units, but significant intra-urban variation at $p < .05$ is found in male activities/roles within domestic units. A significant difference at $p < .01$ is found between male and female activities/roles within domestic units with the female doing much of the domestic activities. No significant relationship is found between male activities/roles and their socio-economic characteristics. These results suggest that men are majorly affected by cultural orientation, and women empowerment could be enhanced through a re-orientation of men via gender education.

The implications of these result is that men irrespective of their socio-economic status need re-orientation. There is the need for gender education. The need for gender education, enlightenment, awareness and consciousness rising among men must target all age groups irrespective of social

class. This is because according to UN (1996) a growing body of research shows that boys as young as three years old are searching for masculine models for their sense of self. Men growing up without a good gender model “grow up with an inflated, hypermasculine view of manhood and are therefore more prone to violence” (UN 1996:108). Re-orientation of men’s mind set via gender education could greatly enhanced women empowerment. This could be achieved through organized seminars, training and workshops for men as well as introduction of gender studies in the primary, secondary and tertiary institutions.

2.2.9 Audience perception of portrayals of women in Nigerian home video films. Azeez, Adesina. Lukman. (2010). Journal of Media and Communication Studies Vol. 2(9), pp.200-207

This study investigated how Nigerians, particularly women, interpreted the meanings of the representations of women in Nigerian films. It aimed at understanding how Nigerian audience interpreted the meanings of the images of women in Nigerian films, with a focus on investigating whether or not there was a marked difference in the ways different individuals and groups interpreted the representations. The general objective of this study were to investigate how the Nigerian audience receive and interpret the images of women in Nigerian films; investigate whether or not there is any difference in the ways different individual audience interpret the representations of women in Nigerian films; and to determine factors that influence how the audience interpret the meanings in the representations of women in Nigerian films.

To achieve the objectives of this study, three sessions of focus group discussion involving a representative sample of viewers of Nigerian video films, from different socio-economic groups were undertaken. The participants ranged according to age, sex, ethnicity and educational level.

Thus, the participants in the first group (26 - 34 years), which is the first session, were postgraduate students studying at “masters’ level” on a part time basis at the University of Lagos. The second group (18 – 25 years), which is the second session, consisted of participants who were in the third and fourth year of their first degree also at the University of Lagos. The participants in the third group (35 to 45 years), which is the third session, were predominantly less educated people including artisans, market women, shop owners and lower-cadre civil servants. The highest

level of education among this group was primary school, which is equivalent to 'standard six' in the Nigerian system and which means they were not only predominantly illiterate, but were less exposed than the first two groups.

The participants in the first and second groups were selected through systematic and cluster random sampling techniques respectively. The aim of using these techniques was not to achieve statistical representation, but was rather meant to ensure that diversity was inherent in the composition of the groups. The participants in the third group were selected through a non-probability sampling technique (purposively) from markets and streets in Ibadan, Oyo State in the South-western part of Nigeria.

The study found that there is a marked difference in the ways women and men interpret the meanings embedded in the representations of women in Nigerian films. While men and less educated women interpret the representations in conformist manner, having the preferred meanings of the ideological meanings embedded in the representation, educated women interpret the representations 'oppositionally' and 'agitatively'. She also found that men tend not to see anything significantly wrong with the representations of women in the films but rather adopt dominant or preferred readings of their meanings, accept the representations in the films as the reality of Nigerian women and wish such to continue unmodified for the reinforcement of Nigerian culture. Women, as she also found, contrarily receive these portrayals as negative, irritating, ideological and derogatory, thereby perceiving the Nigerian films, as a form of culture industry, devoted to women's domination.

It also concludes that there is a marked difference in the ways women, with high education and those with little or no education, perceive the representations of women in Nigerian films. The difference is related to the way each group of women understands and identifies or dis-identifies with the meanings of the images of the films. On this basis, this study proposes a new model for understanding how women in Nigeria interpret popular culture.

One significant point which Azeez (2010)'s findings identify is that, although Nigerian films are ideological apparatuses or devices that perpetuate the images, myths, ideas, concepts or discourses

that fix women in negative/lower positions, viewers might actually find pleasure in what comes across to them in a film, but still know that such is a representation and not reality.

Just as the current study, gender representations in Nigerian films was the subject of the enquiry, only that the current study looked at how men were projected. The survey design was used in the reviewed study, whereas content analysis was used in the current study.

2.2.10 Amobi, Ifeoma T. (2013) Audience Interpretations of the Representation of Women in Nigerian Nollywood films from different social contexts in Nigeria.

Amobi (2013) looked at how female Nollywood actors, students and lecturers of the university of Lagos and Ibadan, make sense of the sexist representations of women in Nollywood films and if and how their social contexts shape their interpretations. She employed a combination of focus group and in-depth interview but found that Nigerian female audiences aggressively demystify the representations of women in Nigerian home video films. Although the representations of women in these films, appear to exercise discursive power through their propensity to present dominant gender subjectivity and or gender positions with which women are supposed to identify, women audiences have significant power to negotiate with or distance themselves from these readings created in films (Azeez, 2010, p. 201). Perhaps, this is an obvious indication that these women could possibly rework these imbedded meanings, to effect changes in their negative representations.

Meanwhile, Amobi (2013) further argues that the ability of the female audiences to interpret these films may not necessarily translate to changes in neither the continued stereotypical depictions of women nor the society's image of the woman. This therefore points at both the media and the society to objectively address these divergences; especially the Nollywood films at constructing and redesigning the feminine roles in these movies. For instance, building the Nigerian women's capacity via Nollywood movies, on significant themes like 'leadership', 'education' and 'entrepreneurship', could help dilute the belligerence on ways they receive their identities.

Taking into account, the research elements addressed by these reception studies, whereas the two studies were conducted only in Oyo and Lagos states of the Western Nigeria, need for the representation of the south eastern women, becomes necessary for obvious reasons. One of such

is the preponderance of patriarchal cultural ideologies among these Igbo speaking states in Nigeria and the greater number of female audiences domiciled in the region.

2.2.11 Portrayal of women in Nigerian home video films: Empowerment or subjugation?

Okunna, C. S. (1996). *Africa Media Review* Vol. 10, No. 3.

Using Igbo language video films as a case in point, the study examined the portrayal of women in films, and the reactions of young women towards this portrayal. The major purpose of which was to gain an insight into what Okunna (1996) considered an apparently novel and unexplored situation at that time: to examine the portrayal of women in the media through their portrayal in selected Igbo language films.

To generate the data for this, data were gathered from a focus group discussion and the class discussion among mass communication undergraduates who were enrolled in a course of critical writing and reviewing. Although the 32-member class comprised male and female students, 26 of them were involved in the discussion of these films. The discussion yielded relevant data for the study. Given the purposeful decision which informed the use of these two categories of respondents, the method of their selection was definitely convenience sampling.

The rationale for the study was that the explosion in the number of local video films was truly astounding. The proliferation and the popularity of these films heightened fears that the little gain that might have been made in this struggle is being eroded by the internalization of the negative images of women by the large audience of local home video films. In addition, a growing number of Nigerian women expressed misgivings about the portrayal of women in Nigerian video films. This study therefore searched for empirical evidence to support or disprove such misgivings. The theory that was used to anchor the study is the 'cultivation theory', based on Gerbner's 'cultivation hypothesis.'

Ten Igbo language video films were used for the study. Questions for the focus group discussion and the class discussion revolved around the following aspects of the films:

- i. The portrayal of women in the films - realistic or otherwise;
- ii. The image of women, vis-a-vis the major female characters - negative or positive; and

iii. Possible influence of this image on the respondents' perception of women.

The image of women in these films was found to be very bad and capable of negatively influencing the perception of women among the large audience of video films in Nigeria. The results of the study indicated that the portrayal of women in Igbo language video films is unrealistic. The paper concludes that, in this era of concern for women's empowerment, these films are counterproductive and damaging to the cause of women. Rather than contribute to the much-needed empowerment of Nigerian women, such films will only lead to the subjugation of women because they can increase men's disdain for women, sow distrust between women, undermine their confidence in themselves and strengthen the forces which push women to the background in this patriarchal society.

It is advocated that women actors should reject roles that relegate them to second fiddle. The domination of male producers in the home video industry is decried, and women are encouraged to seek more positive and active roles.

The reviewed study has helped to give perspective to the current study. The study, which was done in 1996, concluded that the image of women in Nigerian films was found to be very bad and capable of negatively influencing the perception of women among the large audience of video films in Nigeria. Twenty-two years on, the current study uses content analysis to examine if hypermasculinity is portrayed in Nollywood films.

2.2.12 Ateya, A. M. (2012). Women empowerment as portrayed through the Egyptian cinema: Content analysis of films produced between 2001 and 2011. M.Sc Thesis Submitted to the Department of Journalism and Mass Communication, the American University in Cairo.

Unlike the two previous studies reviewed, this study was carried out outside Nigeria. The study shares similar design, content categories and some objectives with the current study. This research analyzed the portrayal of women empowerment in the Egyptian cinema between the years 2001-2011. This specific period was chosen as this is when the Egyptian cinema started to tackle women's issues in line with real-life improvements in Egyptian women's status quo; such as the issue of Khul law, the establishment of the National Council for Women and the right to pass on

the Egyptian nationality to their children to the researcher conducted a content analysis of 20 movies that were produced during the time span covered in the study and that have discussed woman's question or have presented women through different frames. The researcher explored differences in women portrayals with regard to women empowerment as compared to previous studies' findings that were conducted on movies produced in the nineties in order to trace changes that might have taken place. It is this objective that makes this research parallel to the study at hand. In this study being reviewed, the researcher focused on the Egyptian cinema and studied movies that discussed women's issues or the woman's question produced during the 21st century. Theoretically, the study was anchored on the concept of framing and Freire's theory of empowerment.

The study applied both quantitative and qualitative approaches in order to investigate the problem under study. In-depth interviews with cinema experts, scholars and practitioners was conducted for the qualitative data collection part, and a content analysis of movies produced during the period 2001-2011 was carried out for the quantitative data collection part. Using both approaches will help in achieving triangulation of data which could be useful in validating the research results. In-depth interviews with cinema experts, scholars and practitioners will be conducted in order to supplement the content analysis in the data collection part of this research and will help in filling some information gap. This research will use a purposive sampling.

A list of 52 female characters were coded in order to explore the different empowerment/disempowerment frames women get presented through in the Egyptian cinema as well as to gauge any differences in women portrayals than those concluded in previous studies. Also, the researcher aimed to analyze depictions of single, divorced and widowed women and whether the presence of female filmmakers in movies' production teams will affect representations of women empowerment.

The findings of this study revealed that portrayals of women have improved as compared to previous studies of movies that were produced in the nineties. Meanwhile, portrayals of women's background, age and relationship status have remained negative. Furthermore, single, divorced and widowed women are stereotyped in the Egyptian cinema. Female and male filmmakers of the movies studied in this research had similar representations of women empowerment.

In addition, findings with regard to the socio-cultural dimension of women empowerment in the public sphere also reveal that women are depicted as empowered in some elements as well as disempowered in others. Results supported that single, divorced and widowed women are depicted as disempowered with regard to socio-cultural, familial/interpersonal and psychological public spheres. In other words, they are disempowered when it comes to the society's perceptions and stereotyping, but they are less disempowered in the private sphere. This finding resonates with previous studies' findings that articulated that single, divorced and widowed women are negatively portrayed on screen.

Last but not least, movies produced in the 21st century tackled issues of great importance to the woman's question such as female autonomy, female sexuality issues and female independency. Females are also depicted through new empowerment frames as well as disempowerment ones.

Having successfully used content analysis to examine portrayals of women in Egyptian films, the current study used similar design and mirrored the code sheet a little bit as well as adopts some of the content categories used in the reviewed study. This alone confirms the reliability of the coding instrument.

2.2.13 Men's perceptions of masculinities and sexual health risks in Igboland, Nigeria, Clifford Odimegwu, Christian N. Okemgbo 2008 *International Journal of Men's Health* 7(1): 21-39

This study was designed to examine how men from the Igbo ethnic group perceive masculinity and its impact on their sexual and other health needs. The study adopted descriptive survey design. Qualitative data were generated and analyses of the results were carried out. Participants indicated that there is a shift from traditional to non-traditional attitudes and practices among men in the area from which the sample was drawn. Factors responsible for this shift include education, religion, migration patterns, the influence of mass media and globalization. The men reported awareness of sexual and other health needs in the context of their experience of masculinity. Implications of findings for future research and advocacy are discussed.

2.2.14 Masculinity and Nigerian Youths, Egodi Uchendu *Nordic Journal of African Studies* 16(2): 279–297 (2007)

This paper considers the masculine views of a cross-section of Nigerian youths or, more precisely, undergraduates, to determine the forms of masculinity among youths. Participants were thirty-seven male and thirty-three female undergraduate students who have been exposed to some years of university education, with its potential to influence the development of a critical mentality, some appreciation of gender issues, and, more importantly, differing levels of detachment from traditional values. The students' ages ranged from twenty to twenty-seven.

Drawn from different ethnic groups the masculine notions of the category of young men represented in this study show both similarities and differences. Influenced by the university environment, which promotes cross-cultural mingling and exchange of ideas, the views of the study participants are combinations of indigenous and non-indigenous masculine notions but reshaped by the economic and social changes that have taken place in the last two to three decades in the country. Youths aspire to project an ideal masculine identity as they grow older. They regard their educational pursuits as a preparatory phase for actualizing their dream personality. A pointer from this study is that masculine gender expressions cannot be generalized. Individual views can vary widely and are strongly affected by traditional practice as well as environmental and other realities.

This group study with Nigerian undergraduate students on masculinity brings several issues into focus. The youths' expressions underscore new understandings and models of masculinity based on certain contemporary social and economic conditions. Their views on masculinity indicate that the social construction of gender puts pressure on individuals to act in certain ways: being also responsible for the burden on gender relations within (and possibly across) culture groups in Nigeria.

The researchers suggest that it will be necessary to examine rural and semi-literate youths' views on masculinity for a more comprehensive picture of the subject under discussion.

2.2.15 Feminism in the Mass Media: Redressing the Imbalance and Redefining the Image of Women, Ugwulor Chinyere Christiana, 2009

This study evaluated the impact of feminism in the mass media: redressing the imbalance and redefining the image of women. The objectives of the study included to find out whether Nigerian women are aware of their marginalization in the media, to find out the extent to which the mass media portray women negatively, to find out which media misrepresent women, to find out the efforts made to minimize the discrimination on the image of Women and to find out other effective measures the media can employ to improve the image and status of women.

The survey method was adopted for the study, with structured questionnaire as the instrument of data collection. A sample of 300 respondents was picked from Enugu Urban, Agbani and Nsukka towns who responded to the questionnaire. The sample was determined using a random sampling technique. The findings showed among other things that 99 percent of the respondents were in affirmative that Nigerian women are misrepresented and marginalized by the media through what the media present to the public on women, and they are aware of it. Also, the findings showed that women are subordinate to men all over the world.

2.2.16 Social Construction of Manhood in Nigeria: Implications for Male Responsibility in Reproductive Health, Janice E. Olawoye, Femi O. Omololu, Yinka Aderinto, Iyabode Adeyefa, Debo Adeyemo, Babatunde Osotimehin

This paper examines social construction of masculinity and manhood and gender socialization among the three major ethnic groups in Nigeria, with the aid of a combination of qualitative and quantitative data. The major objective of the study was to investigate the process of the social construction of masculinity and manhood from the perspectives of both men and women from different socio-cultural backgrounds. From this study, a detailed, comparative description of masculinity and manhood in the context of the socially heterogeneous Nigerian society was derived.

Due to the realization that the topic is still largely exploratory and relatively few studies had been conducted on male responsibility in Nigeria in 1998 when the data collection took place, the study

relied heavily upon the use of qualitative data collection during the first stage of the study, but also made use of quantitative data collection in the follow-up study. Focus group discussions (FGD) and in-depth interviews (IDI) were predominantly used to secure the views of both young and older Nigerian males and females, in addition to family case studies and a survey that involved 1,475 interviewees.

The sample included male and female, young and old respondents, representing the Yoruba of the Southwest, the Igbo of the Southeast and the Hausa of the North. The study found that, in general, manhood is usually strongly associated with the social position in the family and the physical capability to satisfy the sexual needs of the female partner(s) and to produce children. Decision-making authority, including decision on reproduction, is largely vested in the man. Gender socialising for developing boys into men, including their sexual behaviour, is largely affected by instruction from the mother and the example of the father, while role enactment is closely monitored by the society. Even though significant socio-cultural differences between ethnic groups were found in gender socialising and the resultant roles, male dominance is pervasive and affects reproductive behaviour and health status of both males and females. Change in gender roles, including sexual relationships, will require enlightenment on the need for greater male responsibility in their relationship with females.

2.3 Theoretical Review

This section underscores some of the relevant theories that explain the thesis topic. Theoretical review and the ensuing theoretical framework are important in every academic study. Severin and Tankard (2001) in Ateya (2012) explain that theory fosters a better understanding of how the world around us works. Some of the key objectives of mass communication theories are to study the effects of media consumption, and predict consequences or show relationship between variables. Nwodu (2006) explains it as a way of providing a theoretical perspective for the study by using a substance of the theory to explain or address the research problem.

2.3.1 Social role theory

Social role theory, as propounded by Eagly, Wood and Diekmann (2000), came as a result of their enquiry about stereotypes in relation to gender and what causes sex differences and similarities in

behaviour. The social role theory begins from a social psychological vantage point that highlights social roles and interweaves role-related processes with these other perspectives to produce a powerful analysis of sex differences and similarities. The theory posits that stereotypes, or gender role beliefs, form as people observe male and female behaviour and infer that the sexes possess corresponding dispositions, and that behavioral sex differences spring from the differential social roles inhabited by women and men, especially those concerning the division of labour. They maintain that biology works with psychology to facilitate role performance.

Parsons and Bales (1955) had laid the foundation of the theory by providing an explicit analysis of female and male roles. They described the division of labour between husbands and wives as a specialization of men in task-oriented (or instrumental) behaviour and of women in socio-emotional (or expressive) behaviour.

According to Eagly and Wood (2012), the origins of men's and women's social roles lie primarily in humans' evolved physical sex differences, specifically men's size and strength and women's reproductive activities of gestating and nursing children, which interact with a society's circumstances and culture to make certain activities more efficiently performed by one sex or the other. People carry out gender roles as they enact specific social roles (e.g., parent, employee). Harrison (2005) adds that because of economic, ecological, social, and technological pressures, women and men were assigned to labor tasks that were consistent with their physical attributes. Thus, men were more likely to fulfill tasks that required speed, strength, and the ability to be away from home for expanded periods of time.

Gender roles are descriptive and prescriptive. The descriptive aspect, or stereotype, tells men and women what is typical for their sex in particular contexts and situations. The prescriptive aspect tells them what is expected or desirable (Rudman & Glick, 2001). Socialization facilitates these sex-typical role performances by enabling men and women to develop appropriate personality traits and skills. Additionally, gender roles influence behaviour through a biosocial set of processes: hormonal fluctuations that regulate role performance, self-regulation to gender role standards, and social regulation to others' expectations about women and men.

A profound question posed by Eagly and Wood (2012) is why men and women, and boys and girls, behave differently in many circumstances but similarly in others. They argue that sex differences and similarities in behaviour reflect gender role beliefs that in turn represent people's perceptions of men's and women's social roles in the society in which they live. To buttress the argument, Eagly and Wood (2012) explain that in postindustrial societies men are more likely than women to be employed, especially in authority positions and women are more likely than men to fill caretaking roles at home as well as in employment settings.

Men and women are differently distributed into social roles because of humans' evolved physical sex differences in which men are larger, faster, and have greater upper-body strength, and women gestate and nurse children. Given these physical differences, certain activities are more efficiently accomplished by one sex or the other, depending on a society's circumstances and culture.

2.3.2 General Strain Theory

This theory was propounded by Agnew (1992), and he argues that the experience of negative emotions increases an individual's likelihood of engaging in delinquent behavior because it creates a desire to relieve (correct) the negative emotions. According to general strain theory, there are three categories of events likely to produce psychological stress: 1) failure to achieve positively valued goals, 2) removal of positively valued stimuli, and 3) the presentation of negatively valued stimuli. Resultant strain produced by the aforementioned events causes an individual to experience a range of negative psychological emotions. The individual will then seek corrective action to alleviate these negative emotions using various methods, one possible method being the performance of deviant acts.

Research on the theory suggests that the manner in which an individual will respond to negative emotions is related to the gender of that individual (i.e., gender has been shown to affect the coping strategies employed as a reaction to stress). That is why the theory is relevant in this study. Agnew and Brody (1997) argue that the presence of negative emotions itself does not predict crime, but that the individual's response to the negative emotions is better able to predict criminal behavior and that these responses are dependent upon gender (Hay, 2003; Jang, 2007; Sharp, Brewster, and Love, 2005; Sigfusdottir and Silver, 2009).

Agnew and Broidy (1997) also suggest that men and women experience different types of psychological stress due to gender differences in goals. They claim that men are generally driven more by “material success and extrinsic achievement” (i.e., masculine goals) and women are generally more “concerned with the establishment and maintenance of close relationships and with meaning/purpose in life” (p. 279). Agnew and Broidy argue that this difference in strain type is relevant to likelihood of criminal behavior. The criminal behavior of women will more likely be performed as an effort to increase the establishment of relationships. Men, however, are more likely to commit crimes that will increase their ability to achieve material success.

It is illustrated that for men, material success and extrinsic achievement is a means to a specific end: honour and respect. A man who believes he is treated honorably and respectably by his peers will be satisfied with the level of masculinity that he is presenting to others. However, failure to obtain financial success and extrinsic achievement (e.g., cars, pursuing women) can cause a man to feel as though he is not measuring up to the masculinity goal that he has set for himself. In some cases, other accomplishments may promote honor and respect for the individual. For instance, he may possess musical talent or athletic ability that causes others to esteem him, notwithstanding a lack of financial success (Anderson, 1999).

However, when a man does not experience the level of honour and respect that he perceives to be sufficient for his standard of masculinity, he experiences “failed masculinity.” Failed masculinity produces negative affect due to it being a failure to achieve a positively valued goal. Negative emotions stemming from failed masculinity can also occur as a result of the removal of positively valued stimuli (i.e., losing a job or a girlfriend) or the introduction of noxious stimuli that counters masculinity (i.e., bullying or peer challenges to manhood).

2.3.3 Gender Schema Theory

Gender schema theory was first developed by Sandra Bem in 1981 and later expanded by Carol Martin and Charles Halverson in 1983 as a cognitive theory to explain how individuals become gendered in society, and how sex-linked characteristics are maintained and transmitted to other members of a culture. Gender-associated information is predominantly transmuted through society by way of schemata, or networks of information that allow for some information to be more easily

assimilated than others. Bem argues that there are individual differences in the degree to which people hold these gender schemata. These differences are manifested via the degree to which individuals are sex-typed.

Williams (2018) expatiated that gender schema theory suggests that young children are influenced by society's ideas about what it means to be a male or female in their culture. She states that once children have formed a basic gender identity they start to develop gender schemas. Gender schemas are based on children's interactions and observations of others, their environment, and the culture. These gender schemas are used to organize and direct the child's behavior based on his or her society's gender norms and expectations related to the child's gender.

A gender schema can be thought of as an organized set of gender-related beliefs that influence behavior. Gender schemas are formed as a result of the children's observation of how society defines what it means to be male and female in his or her culture. Gender schemas help determine what the child attends to, how the child interprets the world, and what the child remembers about his or her experiences. In other words, gender schemas organize the child's experiences by providing a means for the child to make sense of new social information. For example, a six-year-old boy may have a schema that contains information about which types of clothing are for girls and which types of clothing are for boys. Since dresses are for girls, the boy would refuse to wear one if presented the opportunity.

According to gender schema theory, being schematic means having a readiness to sort information into categories on the basis of a particular dimension, despite the availability of other possible and reasonable alternative dimensions (Bern, 1984). Thus, being gender schematic means spontaneously sorting attributes and behavior into categories related to sex, despite availability of viable alternative categories unrelated to sex. For the gender-schematic person, the gender connotations of stimuli as either masculine or feminine are proposed to be especially salient.

Core gender identity is tied up in the sex typing that an individual undergoes. This typing can be heavily influenced by child rearing, media, school, and other forms of cultural transmission. Bem refers to four categories in which an individual may fall: sex-typed, cross-sex-typed, androgynous, and undifferentiated. Sex-typed individuals process and integrate information that is in line with

their gender. Cross-sex-typed individuals process and integrate information that is in line with the opposite gender. Androgynous individuals process and integrate traits and information from both genders. Finally, undifferentiated individuals do not show efficient processing of sex-typed information (Williams, 2018)

Being that gender schema theory is a theory of process and not content, this theory can help explain some of the processes by which gender stereotypes become so psychologically ingrained in our society. Specifically, having strong gender schemata provides a filter through which we process incoming stimuli in the environment. This leads to an easier ability to assimilate information that is stereotype congruent, hence further solidifying the existence of gender stereotypes (Bern, 1994 in Cherry, 2017).

Within adolescent development, the theory hypothesizes that children must choose among a plethora of dimensions, but that gender schemas lead to the regulation of behaviours that conform to the cultural definition of what it means to be male or female. Additionally, Bem asserts that there is also a heterosexuality subschema, which likely encouraged the development of gender schemas. Most societies treat exclusive heterosexuality as the benchmark for proper masculinity and femininity—that is, heterosexuality is the norm. Furthermore, the heterosexuality subschema asserts that men and women are supposed to be different from one another. It is hypothesized that this is why cross-sexed interactions are likely to be sexually coded. Sex-typed individuals have a general readiness to invoke the heterosexuality subschema in social interactions, behaving differently towards individuals of the opposite sex that they find attractive versus unattractive (Bern, 1994 in Hoffman & Borders, 2001).

According to gender schema theory, children develop gender schema based on their experiences and the gender attributes of their culture. An individual's self-schema is merged with the culturally determined schema for their gender (Bern, 1983). Children begin by developing a simple concept of what distinguishes a male from a female. Children first learn their own gender by ages two and three. Then, they learn what it means to be a male or female in their society. As soon as the child figures out what it means to be a male or a female, he or she actively seeks information concerning the appropriate gender roles and traits. Then, the child tries to display gender-appropriate behavior.

Children take everything they observe of males and females and organize them around their gender schema.

2.3.4 Stereotype Theory

The idea of stereotype theory was first conceived by Walter Lipmann (1965). Lipmann used the concept to refer to images individuals have in their minds about certain things or categories. In effect he used the word to refer to “the typical picture that comes to mind when thinking about a particular social group”. Lipmann argues that: “the way things are in the real world are often not the same as images that exist in the minds of people living in a society, yet the dominant group perpetuates the inaccurate images in the minds of the marginalized”.

Lipmann (1965) cited in Glaveanu (2007), compares stereotypes with stable images in our head that shorten our perceptions. They are economical in the sense that previous experience moulds current perceptions. There are, however, some notable exceptions: we tend not to stereotype persons we love or admire. Glaveanu (2007) also summarizes theoretical reviews of stereotypes by various authors: a set of shared convictions/beliefs about members of a particular group (Leyens at al., 1994; Smith and Bond, 1994); perceptions of a genuine correspondence between group membership and certain traits (Doise et al., 1999); constructs describing both personality traits and behaviour patterns (Leyens at al., 1994; Drozda-Senkowsks, 1999); standardized, stable and preconceived images (Gavreliuc, 2006); and a natural function of the human and cultural mind (Nachbar & Lause, 1992).

The stereotype theory explanations on how the perceived image people have of the female gender could translate into the type of role they are assigned as characters in home video films. It emphasizes the view that the mass media reinforce the dominant segment of society's existing patterns of attitudes and behavior toward minorities by perpetuating rigid and usually negative portrayals, which can have the result of keeping minorities in subordinate positions.

The theory proposes that in entertainment content, and in other messages, the media repeatedly present portrayals of various categories of people, such as the aged, women, and major racial and ethnic groups; those portrayals tend to be consistently negative, showing people as having more undesirable attributes and few positive characteristics than members of the dominant groups; such

portrayals are similar among the various media--providing corroboration; these portrayals provide constructions of meaning for members of the audience, particularly for those who have only limited contact with actual people of the relevant categories; and thus, members of the audience incorporate those meanings into their memories as relatively inflexible schemata--stereotypic interpretations--that they use when thinking about or responding to any individual of a portrayed category, regardless of his or her actual personal characteristics.

According to Glaveanu (2007), stereotypes are defined by their social, shared, generalised, contextual, dual and schematic nature. That is stereotypes are shared beliefs between group / category members about the in or out-group members (both their personality and behaviour – the dual nature) usually formed during the process of social interaction (therefore being contextual). They are schematic (often simple, essentialist) and generalised (describing all members and ignoring individual differences).

2.3.5 Gaze theory

Gaze theory which was propounded Mulvey (1975), is rooted in Freud's Psychoanalysis Theory. The theory posits that we see the world from the lens of the men, who are the dominant gender in media production. The theory provides a theoretical explanation of why women are often portrayed as sex objects in movies and men are projected in very masculine manner. Mulvey (1975) cited in Gauntlett (2002, p. 38) argued that there are two pleasures derivable from watching cinemas. One is 'scopophilia', a voyeuristic gaze directed at other people, while the second is narcissistic voyeurism – seeing oneself in a primary character and identifying with it.

Mluvey (cited in Gauntlett 2002, p. 38) argues further that: in "a world ordered by sexual imbalance, pleasure in looking has been split between active/male and passive/female". The determining male gaze projects its phantasy onto the female figure, which is styled accordingly. In their traditional exhibitionist role, women are simultaneously looked at and displayed, with their appearance coded for strong visual and erotic impact so that they can be said to connote to-be-looked-at-ness.

Mluvey's argument in gaze theory – that the female character has no importance in a film, beyond her role as a 'spectacle', the erotic object of both the male characters and the cinema spectators –

explains the underlying motive behind the portrayal of women as sex objects in movies. Interestingly, a majority of such movies are most times produced and directed by men – the gender whose erotic gaze the movies were ‘meant’ to satisfy in the first instance.

2.3.6 Feminist Muted Group Theory

Shirley and Ardener (1968) propounded the feminist muted group theory, which explains why certain groups in society are muted, silent or not heard. They suggest that in every society a social hierarchy exists, that privileges some group over others. These groups that function at the top (men) of the social hierarchy determine to a great extent the communication system of the entire society and the “mutedness” occurs because of the lack of power that is given to another group (women) that occupies the low end of the pole. They assert that women are the ones that usually are at the lower rung of the social hierarchy; hence, they are usually undermined and silenced.

Kramarae (1981) made the following key assumptions of the feminist muted group theory to include: that because men are the dominant group in the society, the women are perceived as less competent; that in order to become participating members in society women must transform their perceptions and models of perceiving into terms of dominant group. That is to say, in a male dominated society, the assignment of roles in the cultural industries adversely affects women; to sustain supremacy men assign to themselves the more paying, more powerful and prestigious roles while leaving the weaker and less prestigious ones to women.

2.3.7 Sexual Objectification Theory

Sexual objectification theory assumes that there is a growing perception of women as physical objects of male sexual desire. This theory suggests that by reason of certain cultures, women’s value is tied to their looks and sexual appeal to men. This leads to the reduction of people, especially women, to physical objects of sexual desire. Fredrickson and Roberts (1997), proponents of the objectification theory, explain that certain cultures socialize girls and women to internalize an observer’s perspective on their own bodies. When young girls and women internalize an observer’s perspective of their own bodies, they live much of their life in the third-person. In other words, females learn to be more concerned with observable body attributes rather than focusing on non-observable body attributes such as feelings and internal bodily states.

The objectification theory takes as a given that all women and girls in our society live in a culture in which their bodies are looked at, evaluated, and potentially objectified. Thus, the aim of objectification theory is to explicate how living in a social–cultural context that sexualizes and dehumanizes the female body can lead to specific negative affective experiences and mental health risks for women and girls.

What this theory means in essence is that the objectification of women in the cultural industries such as the mass media has become a global trend; various cultures are beginning to adopt that. The extent to which women are objectified in the media is almost always a reflection of the way they are objectified in the real world.

2.3.8 Relational models of ‘Masculinities’

A gender relational model for understanding masculinities has been developed, predominantly through the work of Connell (1995, 2001). Here, men and women are not postulated as polar opposites, rather ‘gender’ is understood as being about sets of relations between men and women, but also relations between men and between women. Masculinities are a part of, and not distinct from, this larger system of relations that Connell (2001) terms the ‘gender order’. This allows for exploration of similarity, as well as difference, between men and women and for consideration of how other aspects of identity contribute to, and cross-cut, these similarities and differences.

Masculinities are seen as configurations of social practices that are patterned, and ordered hierarchically, in particular ways. They are ordered hierarchically in respect to women but, importantly, there are also sets of masculinity practices that are the most valued in any given place and time - what Connell terms ‘hegemonic’ forms. Other sets of masculinity practices become subordinated to, or marginalised from, these more valued hegemonic practices. In this way, configurations of gender practice, including ‘masculinities’, can be understood as habitual practices that are also open to change in new or differing circumstances.

Masculinity is, therefore, not a character or personality type that men possess in greater or lesser amounts. Rather, ‘masculinities’ are understood as being historically contingent but not essentially determined (either by biology or processes of socialisation) social practices, that are fluid but

hierarchically ordered with dominant (hegemonic) configurations acting collectively, becoming incorporated into the social structures of societies and, thus, replicating themselves. In relating this to health, it becomes apparent that the way that power moves within these varied sets of social, gendered practices has an impact on health and well-being.

As Schofield et al (2000) point out, “a gender relations approach is one that proposes that men’s and women’s interactions with each other and the circumstances under which they interact contribute significantly to health opportunities and constraints” (p. 251). In this way, it becomes possible to unpack what Sabo (2000) has termed ‘negative-gendered’ and ‘positive-gendered health synergies’ (p, 137); that is the way that patterns of gender relations promote favourable or unfavourable health processes, practices or outcomes.

2.3.9 Gender Intensification Hypothesis

The gender intensification hypothesis, proposed by Hill and Lynch (1983), that beginning in adolescence, girls and boys face increased pressure to conform to culturally sanctioned gender roles. These pressures come from a variety of sources that convey messages about appropriate gender roles, such as parents, peers, educators, and the media. In the face of these pressures, adolescents are thought to become more differentiated in their gender-role identities, which presumably will be adaptive for their adult roles as women and men.

The gender intensification hypothesis is defined as the belief that developmentally there is an acceleration of gender-differentiated socialization, roughly occurring at the beginning of the adolescent period (Hill & Lynch, 1983). According to the gender intensification hypothesis, during adolescence gender differences between the sexes become more exaggerated, as adolescent girls and boys identify more strongly with the feminine and masculine stereotype than they did in childhood. It is theorized that one reason this happens is because greater conformity occurs during adolescence to societal expectations. As well, sanctions occur for gender appropriate behaviour, activities, and traits by parents, teachers, peers, and the media (Hill & Lynch, 1983).

Gender intensification has been used to explain an array of characteristics in which gender differences emerge or intensify during adolescence. As such, the concept is intuitively appealing because it so readily explains these systematic changes. Nonetheless, little empirical research has

directly tested the gender intensification hypothesis. The purpose of the present research, therefore, was to test two key assumptions underlying gender intensification: the divergence of girls and boys in their gender-role identities across adolescence and the ability of gender intensification to explain the emergence of the gender difference in depressive symptoms, which occurs in adolescence.

The adolescent and young adult peer group, in particular, often celebrates and reinforces hyper-masculine ideology (Mosher and Tomkins, 1988). During adolescence, masculine norms of "being tough" and related traits such as aggression become heightened (Mills, 2001). During this time, the social price of not conforming is very high and boys who do not conform to this standard are often excluded, physically and verbally bullied, or labelled with terms implying 'inferior' status of a homosexual or a girl, such as 'sissy' or 'fag' (Katz,2001).

Violent behaviour by young men, particularly in schools, is often the only solution to end unwanted teasing and harassment. Boys that are able to demonstrate that they are prepared to engage in, or at least condone, violent behaviour in certain circumstances (e.g., harassing girls) are usually able to avoid being the recipient of unwelcome harassment (Mills, 2001).

When Hill and Lynch (1983) proposed their gender intensification hypothesis, they commendably integrated a vast literature regarding adolescent gender differences and similarities, addressing domains such as psychological well-being, mental health, academic and career aspirations, and parent and peer relationships. Although little empirical research existed at the time regarding parent and peer socialization of gender roles in adolescence, Hill and Lynch were clearly interested in how adolescents came to be socialized into gendered roles and behaviors, suggesting that these pressures intensified during adolescence with the onset of puberty and resulted in increased attraction from opposite-sex partners and better adaptation for adult roles.

2.4 Theoretical Framework

According to Owuamalam (2012), theoretical framework means to predicate a study on a particular relevant theory, depending on the subject and perspective of the research exercise in a bid to enhance better grasp of the interrelatedness of concepts in the study. This study is anchored on the following theories:

2.4.1 Stereotype Theory

The stereotype theory was first conceived by Walter Lipmann (1965) to refer to images individuals have in their minds about certain things or categories, and most specifically, the typical picture that comes to mind when thinking about a particular social group. Lipmann argues that the dominant group perpetuates the inaccurate images in the minds of the marginalized.

The stereotype theory explains how the perceived image people have of the female or male gender could translate into the type of role they are assigned as characters in home video films. It emphasizes the view that the mass media reinforce the dominant segment of society's existing patterns of attitudes and behavior toward minorities by perpetuating rigid and usually negative portrayals, which can have the result of keeping minorities in subordinate positions.

The theory proposes that in entertainment content, and in other messages, the media repeatedly present portrayals of various categories of people; those portrayals tend to be consistently negative, showing people as having more undesirable attributes and few positive characteristics than members of the dominant groups; such portrayals are similar among the various media--providing corroboration; these portrayals provide constructions of meaning for members of the audience, particularly for those who have only limited contact with actual people of the relevant categories; and thus, members of the audience incorporate those meanings into their memories as relatively inflexible schemata--stereotypic interpretations – that they use when thinking about or responding to any individual of a portrayed category, regardless of his or her actual personal characteristics.

The relevance of this theory to this study is that the repeated portrayals of men as having certain hypermasculine traits in Nigerian films will influence the perceived image people have of them in Nigerian society. Nollywood films can be used to reinforce the dominant segment of society's existing patterns of perceptions, attitudes and behaviour toward men by perpetuating rigid and hypermasculine portrayals of the male gender.

2.4.2 Social role theory

Eagly, Wood and Diekmann (2000), the propounders of the theory, explain that stereotypes, or gender role beliefs, form as people observe male and female behaviour; and the sexes possess

corresponding dispositions, and that behavioral sex differences spring from the differential social roles inhabited by women and men, especially those concerning the division of labour. Gender roles mean expectations for female and male behaviour. It is described as society's shared beliefs that apply to individuals on the basis of their socially identified sex (Eagly, 2009 in Eisenclas, 2013).

Harrison (2005) adds that because of economic, ecological, social, and technological pressures, women and men were assigned to labor tasks that were consistent with their physical attributes. Thus, men were more likely to fulfill tasks that required speed, strength, and the ability to be away from home for expanded periods of time. Patriarchy arises when the physical attributes of men and women interact with economic and technological developments to give men the roles that yield decision-making authority and access to resources.

The relevance of this theory to this study is that while it is socialization that facilitates sex-typical role performances by enabling men and women to develop appropriate personality traits and skills; those roles are perpetuated by the cultural institutions such as the mass media. The implication is that Nollywood films shape expectations for male behaviour by certain portrayal of the men in the films. Those films perpetuate hypermasculine tendencies by assigning certain tasks and personality traits and skills to men.

2.4.3 Gender Hierarchy Theory

The gender hierarchy theory was propounded by Wood and Eagly (2002). The gender hierarchy theory is based around the belief of male dominance in the society and the discrimination of women (Holter, 2005). The basic categories which are associated with this theory are those of gender (in)equality. It is assumed that male domination and the resulting forms of inequality are of structural nature. Inherent for this approach is the conviction that women and men constitute "competing groups with different chances in the market" (p. 17). Within this tradition, categories of masculinity and femininity are of static character, which is internally integrated (at times, differing natures of men and women are adduced, as if referencing biological determinism).

The relevance of this theory to this study is that the portrayals of hypermasculine traits in Nigerian films are only a reflection of the belief of male dominance in the society and the discrimination of

women. The portrayals of male dominance reinforce the patriarchal ideology and the tenets of hegemonic masculinity. As the gender hierarchy theory assumes, male domination or projection of hypermasculine traits and the resulting forms of inequality are of structural nature.

2.5 Gaps in Literature

Having reviewed various literatures on masculinities, hypermasculinities, effects of masculinities, common themes in masculinity research, hegemonic masculinity, among others; and explained relevant theories and theoretical frameworks as well as some related studies that are used to give context to this study, the researcher has observed that existing knowledge and previous researches had expressed concerns about the hypermasculinity in the media.

But the most striking observation is that hypermasculinity is a complex concept, and has scarcely been given research attention by Nigerian scholars; almost all the reviewed studies and opinions are from foreign sources. Past and ongoing theorizations and studies on gender in Nigeria have paid a lot of attention to the portrayal of women in the media. Ogunyemi (2014) observes that the motif of genderisation and social themes in most studies in the Nigerian intellectual space is the female gender; it is always about the female gender. Baker & Ricardo (2005) also consent that the studies on gender perspective and gender mainstreaming have too often ignored the gender of men and boys. How then are men projected in the media?

Therefore, the paucity of hypermasculinity research in Nigeria opens up a knowledge gap about how the Nigerian media such as the film industry portrays the man or projects the concept of manliness.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The explanatory sequential mixed method design was adopted in this study, which implies collecting and analyzing quantitative and then qualitative data in two consecutive phases within one study, with a final phase of integration or linking of data from the two separate strands of data (Ivankova, Cresswell & Stick, 2006; Berman, 2017). To be more exact, the explanatory sequential mixed method design, according to Clark (2011), consists of first collecting quantitative data and then collecting qualitative data to help explain or elaborate on the quantitative results. The rationale for this approach is that the quantitative data and results provide a general picture of the research

problem; more analysis, specifically through qualitative data collection is needed to refine, extend or explain the general picture. That is, it involves the integration of quantitative and qualitative methods in order to strengthen the rigour of the study and enrich the analysis and findings.

The quantitative approach adopted for this study was content analysis (the study and analyses of communication contents in a systematic, objective and quantitative manner for the purpose of measuring variables) whereas the qualitative approach was in-depth interviews with identified film experts and scholars. The objective of qualitative research was to gain understanding of underlying reasons and motivations and uncover prevalent trends in thought and opinion (Park & Park, 2016); whereas, the objective of quantitative research was to quantify data and generalize results from a sample to the population of interest. They are both blended to validate the findings.

Akinfeleye and Amobi (2011) explain that in analyzing the content of popular culture (such as film), the questions that are being raised are primarily those relating to the amount and nature of the content i.e. the quantity and quality of variables that make up the entire content.

A combination of the quantitative and qualitative approaches and the integration of their data also meant a blend of interpretivism and positivist paradigms. Positivism entails an empiricist stance that 'reliable knowledge can only be derived from experience' (Cohen, et al., 2007, p. 11) and it involves the formation of hypothesis, test of hypothesis through observation, manipulation of variables and data collection (Cohen, et al., 2007). Positivism paradigm is brutally objective. Interpretivism involves interpretation and it encourages researchers to be more interpretive and inductive (Johari, 2009). It also involves filtering participants' statements and actions through the lens of the researchers own subjectivity (Walsham, 1995).

3.2 Population of the Study

In this study, the researcher focused on Nollywood films produced from 2015 to 2017 that have men playing leading or supporting roles. This specific period was chosen as this was when scholars and activists started recognizing the importance of explicitly investigating men as gendered beings (Peretz, 2016); even though research efforts in masculinity had since started, the study received renewed attention following microeconomic shifts mostly in the 2000's when machines replaced

muscles and women became more relevant (Katz 2011). More so, women's rise in power at this period in various sectors of the economy has created a crisis in gender studies and inspired insight into masculinity all over the world (Gray & Ginsberg, 2007). It is said that it is in the 21st century that the scope of gender studies significantly broadened to not only be about women, but also include men and multiple other ideas, like race, ethnicity, sexuality and ability (Bondy, 2011).

Given that this study spans from 2015 to 2017, the population of this study comprises of films registered by the Nigerian Film and Video Censor's Board between 2015 and 2017. Data provided by the Nigerian Film and Video Censor's Board shows that in 2015, a total of 1,097 were approved; for 2016, 1,601 films were approved and in 2017, 1, 165 films were approved. That is the total population consists of 3863 films. A painstaking review of the synopsis of the films by the researcher shows that 100% of the films have men playing leading, supporting roles or some role of note. That is to say, 3863 films make up the population for this study.

The interview population is indeterminate as it comprises film experts and scholars in South-East, Nigeria whose exact population could not be defined as there was no record to that effect.

3.3 Sample Size

Using the Australian Calculator, the sample size was 350, derived as follows:

Confidence Level:	95% ▼
Population Size:	3863
Proportion:	0.5
Confidence Interval:	0.05
Upper	0.55000
Lower	0.45000
Standard Error	0.02551
Relative Standard Error	5.10
Sample Size:	350

The sample size agrees with the figure on the Morgan’s Table for Sample Size prepared by The Research Advisors (2006), where a population in the region of 3000-4000, with confidence level of 95% and 5.0% margin of error yields a sample size of 350 (See Appendix D).

As for the number of interviewees, the size is usually a small number of non-representative cases selected to fulfill a given quota (Park & Park, 2016). Therefore, the said sample was as purposeful as possible without recourse to the number of persons. For that reason, the researcher selected a relatively small number of participants “deliberately selected on the basis of their known attributes” (Denscombe, 2010, p. 35). They are made up of 30 interviewees comprising 15 film experts and 15 scholars.

3.4 Sampling Technique

Since the quantitative approach in this study is content analysis, multi stage sampling is considered most appropriate in the quantitative phase (Wimmer and Dominick, 2011 in Obayi, et al. 2016). The following stages were suggested and adopted for this study: sampling of the content sources, then periods and time frame of the study, and using scientific approach to arrive at a given simple size.

First, given that the total number of films produced during the span of this study (2015-2017) were 3863, the proportion of each year in relation to the total number is as follows:

S/No	Year	Total Produced	Proportion (%)
1	2015	1,097	28.4
2	2016	1,601	41.4
3	2017	1,165	30.6
Total		3863	100

Consequent upon the proportion given in the table above, the sample size is allocated to the various years as follows:

S/No	Year	Proportion (%)	Sample Size Allocated (Total is 370)
1	2015	28.4	99
2	2016	41.4	144
3	2017	30.6	107
Total		100	350

For each of the years, the allocated samples were taken from the highest grossing films for that year (see *Appendix D*). This is because those are the ones that are most viewed, and as a result the hypermasculinity tendencies in them will more consumed by the viewers. More so, they are easily available for viewing and coding by the researcher.

For the in-depth interview (qualitative) phase, interviewees were 30 in number comprising 15 film experts and 15 scholars (university lecturers). The 30 persons were evenly selected from each of the 5 South-Eastern States (Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and Imo). That is, 6 persons (film experts and lecturers combined) were selected from each of the states. The snowballing procedure was adopted in the selection of film experts as interviewed persons suggested other people to be interviewed until the required number was exhausted. The university lecturers were purposively selected from the departments of Mass Communication in Abia State University (Abia), Odimegwu Ojukwu University (Anambra), Ebonyi State University (Ebonyi), Enugu State University of Science and Technology (Enugu) and Imo State University (Imo).

3.5 Measuring Instruments

The code sheet was used to record depictions of hypermasculinity in the selected Nollywood films. The researcher was guided by the various content categories and units of analysis that are indicative of hypermasculinity in the selected Nollywood films. The coding sheet that was developed for this study is a modification and extension of various other coding instruments used in previous related studies (Hibbeler, 2009; Luther & Legg, 2007; Burk et al., 2004; Burk, et al., 2004; Tanner, Haddock, Zimmerman & Lund, 2003; Krahe & Fenske, 2002; Bourg, 2001;

Rohlinger 2000; Tyler, Hoyt, & Whitbeck, 1998; Taylor and Bang 1997; Kolbe & Albanese 1996; Zaitchik & Mosher, 1993). (see Appendix B)

Interview schedule was used to gather the qualitative data. It is a very common research tool in a small-scale research (Dever, 1995). It is used to get the story behind a participant's experiences and pursue in-depth information around the topic of study (McNamara, 1999). Wimmer and Dominick (2011) observe that in-depth interview has numerous advantages as it provides a wealth of detail and accurate response on sensitive issues.

3.6 Units of Analysis

Unit of analysis is defined as the smallest element of content analysis but the most important (Wimmer & Dominick, 2011). It consists of the variable that the researcher would actually look at in the course of the analysis (Obayi, Anorue & Onyebuchi, 2016). In this research, the unit of analysis is the male character within the select Nollywood movies. Having the male character within the movie as the unit of analysis will help to gauge the hypermasculinity traits the men exhibited in the selected Nollywood films. Not all the male characters in movies were studied; only men in leading and supporting roles were coded. As O'Neil (2016) asserts in a related study, this is to exclude individuals who may be extras or background characters, and not central roles or figures in the films. This is not to say that extras and background people are unimportant in films, they are just not part of the central analysis for the present study. Using a similar process, Evans and Davies (2000, p. 260) considered in their study the main male characters, "those who were the focus of the story" as the unit of analysis.

3.7 Content Categories

The content categories in this study are those things that the researcher considers markers of hypermasculinity which relate to the male characters in the selected Nollywood films. Just like the coding sheet, the content categories that will guide this study are a modification and extension of the ones used in previous related studies. Those include the three hypermasculinity traits identified by Mosher (1984) and others (Waters, 2017; O'Neil, 2016; Hibbeler, 2009; Vokey, 2008; Luther & Legg, 2007; Burk et al., 2004; Burk, et al., 2004; Tanner, Haddock, Zimmerman & Lund, 2003;

Krahe & Fenske, 2002; Bourg, 2001; Rohlinger 2000; Tyler, Hoyt, & Whitbeck, 1998; Taylor and Bang 1997; Kolbe & Albanese 1996; Zaitchik & Mosher, 1993; Signorielli, 1989, Goffman 1979). Together with the content variables (the meaning of each of the variables is explained in the code book in appendix A), the content categories included:

1. Frequency of occurrence of traits (See Appendix A to understand all variables)

- a. 1 – 10 times
- b. 11 – 20 times
- c. 21 – 30 times
- d. 31 – 40 times
- e. 41 – 50 times
- f. Above 50 times

2. Hypermasculinity Traits

- a. Violence as manly
- b. Callous attitude towards women and sex
- c. Danger as exciting
- d. Toughness as emotional self-control
- e. Other hypermasculinity traits

3. Hypermasculinity framework expressed

- a. They are born with hypermasculinity traits (biological determinism)
- b. They learn hypermasculinity traits (gender role socialization)
- c. Societies expect them to have those hypermasculinity traits (social constructionism)

4. Equitability of gender traits

- a. Gender equitable traits
- b. Non-gender-equitable traits

5. Demographics of male characters

- a. Age**

- i. Child
- ii. Adolescent
- iii. Young adult
- iv. Middle aged
- v. Old/elderly
- vi. Unable to determine

b. Marital Status:

- i. Single
- ii. Married
- iii. Divorced
- iv. Widowed
- v. Unable to determine

c. Educational qualification:

- i. Learned
- ii. Not learned
- iii. Unable to determine

d. Occupation:

- i. White-collar worker
- ii. Blue-collar worker
- iii. Pink-collar worker
- iv. Unemployed
- v. Unable to determine

e. Social status

- i. Lower/working
- ii. Middle
- iii. Upper
- iv. Unable to determine

f. Family life:

- i. Being a Member of a Stepfamily
- ii. Being a Single Parent
- iii. Having a Single Parent
- iv. Being in an Adoptive Family
- v. Community as Family
- vi. Being a Member of a Nuclear Family
- vii. Unable to Determine

Those are the content categories that were coded in the selected Nollywood films. They are different the kinds of content the researcher investigated, and which helped in answering the research questions.

3.10 Validity of instruments

The code sheet and oral interview schedules were, prior to their administration, submitted to the supervisors of this thesis who critically evaluated them for content validity. The instruments were also validated during the thesis proposal defense by a group of panelists who made corrections that were effected prior to administration and use.

3.11 Intercoder Reliability

Reliability is a great concern when conducting a content analysis. To ensure reliability of the instruments, it is recommended that between 10 and 25 percent of the materials should be analyzed by independent coders (Wimmer & Dominick, 2011).

The following guidelines, as explained by Lombard, Snyder-Duch and Bracken (2002), were utilized. To ensure reliability for this study, the researcher employed an independent coder that was trained and provided with the coding scheme. The independent coder was asked to code a random representative sample of ten percent of the films. Thus, a total of 35 films were randomly selected for inter-coder reliability. The coder was given 35 coding sheets (see *Appendix B*) and a copy of the rules of coding (see *Appendix A*).

The results of the independent coder were examined against the researcher’s coding to test for an acceptable level of reliability. The coefficient of the intercoder reliability was calculated using the Cohen’s Kappa based on the SPSS. Kappa is considered a more robust measure for inter-rater reliability than most statistics (George & Mallery, 2003).

Four content categories (4 items) were coded for reliability. They include: equitability of traits, hypermasculinity framework, literacy level of male characters and frequency of male characters who expressed hypermasculine traits.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T	Approx. Sig.
Measure of Agreement Kappa	.878	.088	8.879	.000
N of Valid Cases	757			

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis

Interpretation of Cohen’s Kappa

Value of Kappa	Level of Agreement	% of Data that are Reliable
0–.20	None	0–4%
.21–.39	Minimal	4–15%
.40–.59	Weak	15–35%
.60–.79	Moderate	35–63%
.80–.90	Strong	64–81%
Above .90	Almost Perfect	82–100%

Therefore, the coefficient of reliability is .878, an indication of acceptable and strong reliability of the coding instrument.

Note: in order to be sure of where the two judges agree, the two coders, upon making any coding decision in the course of watching the films, wrote down the specific time (minute) mark in the film where each decision was made. Any time the two coders made the same coding decision at the same time mark in the film; their decisions were adjudged to agree.

3.12 Method of Data Analysis

Frequencies and percentages were used at descriptive level to analyse the data collected and collated from the code sheets, using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23. The software was used to generate charts and tables, and to test the hypotheses. Regression Analysis and ANOVA were used to test the hypotheses.

Regression was used on the bases that it was earlier employed in a related study by Abidemi (2005) and it suits the nature of this study as the researcher sets out to predict the correlation between the demographics of the males and their tendency to exhibit hypermasculine traits. That is, the demographics of the male characters were regressed with hypermasculine traits observed in the films. More so, regression is one of the most reliable methods of statistical analyses used in content analyses (Coners & Mathies, 2014)

As for the analysis of the responses from the in-depth interview, the researcher used an inductive approach in order for themes used to answer the research questions to arise from the interviews and also did a constant comparison analysis to each of the transcripts, probing for common words, phrases and concepts among the interviewees (Firmin et al., 2017).

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This chapter comprises the presentation and analysis of the data coded from the 350 films selected for this study as well as the qualitative responses obtained from the interviewees, in other to meet the objectives of this study. Following from the presentation and analysis of the various data, the findings were discussed in connection with the research questions.

The presentation and analysis of the data were done in four sections: first, the presentation and analysis of the quantitative data coded from the films (the analysis of which is based on the SPSS using charts, simple percentages and tables); next is, test of the hypotheses using a number of tools such as Regression Analysis and ANOVA, and based on the SPSS version 23; that is followed by inductive analysis of the responses from the in-depth interviews; and the discussion of findings concludes the chapter.

Meanwhile for each of the tables presented in the first section, the normality of the various was tested by examining the skewness and kurtosis. Typically, skewness and kurtosis are presented using a histogram: a normal distribution is a symmetric distribution with well-behaved tails on the histogram. Also, a normal kurtosis and skewness are achieved when the standard errors of the kurtosis and skewness multiplied by 3 are greater than the absolute value of the kurtosis and skewness.

Another rule of thumb according to BPI Consulting (2016) is that the data are fairly symmetrical if the skewness is between -0.5 and 0.5; or moderately skewed if the skewness is between -1 and -0.5 and 1.

The findings were discussed with an interpolation of the inferences from the quantitative data and the response from the in-depth interviews using inductive approach and pattern matching (Wimmer and Dominick, 2012).

4.1 Presentation and Analysis of Coded Data

Overall, all the 350 films selected for this study were watched over 4-month span and coded for hypermasculinity. As presented in Table 1, out of the 903 male characters in the 350 films who played either leading or supporting roles, 757 of them exhibited various levels of hypermasculine traits. Therefore, the analyses below are based on those characters who clearly exhibited degrees of hypermasculine traits in the films.

Table 4.1: Proportion of male characters exhibiting hypermasculine traits in select films

	Frequency	Percent	Mean	Standard deviation
Valid Characters who clearly exhibited degrees of hypermasculine traits	757	35.0	1.16	.368
Characters who clearly did not exhibit hypermasculine traits	146	6.8		
Total	903	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s Field Data, 2018

It is evident from Table 4.1 above that the select Nollywood films significantly sold hypermasculine ideologies as a collective characteristic of the male human, giving that majority (83.3%) of the male characters exhibited hypermasculine traits in the films and only 16.2% of male characters did not exhibit traits that were decidedly considered hypermasculine. The dataset in Table 1 is highlighted by a high mean of 1.16 and a standard deviation of .368; an indication of prevalence of male characters exhibiting hypermasculine traits in the films.

Fig 4.1: Histogram showing distribution of the proportion of characters who exhibited hypermasculine traits in the coded films

The distribution of Fig. 4.1 is a little bit skewed to the right but is a fairly normal distribution. The kurtosis and skewness tests on the SPSS showed an absolute kurtosis value of 0.392 (less than 3 times the standard error value of 0.163) and skewness value of 0.841. According to the rule of thumb the data is moderately skewed (between 0.5 and 1).

Table 4.2: Frequency of occurrence of hypermasculine traits in coded films

	Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. Deviation
Valid 1 – 10 times	28	7.6	2.72	.996
11-20 times	145	39.2		
21-30 times	114	30.8		
31-40 times	70	18.9		
41-50 times	10	2.7		
Above 50 times	3	.8		
Total	370	100.0		

Source: Researcher's Field Data, 2018

The incidence of hypermasculine traits in the select films were grouped into 6 frequency brackets, namely: 1-10 times, 11-20 times, 21-30 times, 31-40 times, 41-50 times and above 50 times. Data presented in Table 4.2 above shows that majority (39.2%) of the select Nollywood films had between 11 and 20 incidence and the least proportion of the films (0.8%) had over 50 incidences of hypermasculine traits.

The dataset in Table 4.2 is highlighted by a high mean of 2.72 and a standard deviation of .996. Based on the overall inference drawn from the descriptive statistics, it is safe to conclude that there is regular occurrence and large amount of hypermasculine traits in Nollywood films.

Fig 4.2: Histogram showing distribution of the frequency of occurrence of hypermasculine traits in coded films

The kurtosis and skewness tests on the SPSS showed an absolute kurtosis value of 0.021 (less than 3 times the standard error value of 0.253) and skewness value of 0.576. According to the rule of thumb the data has normal kurtosis but is symmetrically skewed.

Table 4.3: Literacy status of male characters who exhibited hypermasculine traits in coded films

	Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. Deviation
Valid Learned	689	91.0	1.10	.345
Not Learned	58	7.7		
Indeterminate	10	1.3		
Total	757	100.0		

Source: Researcher's Field Data, 2018

Data presented in Table 4.3 above shows that majority (91.0%) of the male characters who exhibited hypermasculine traits in coded films were learned; whereas the literacy status of least proportion (1.3%) of the male characters were indeterminate.

The data is accentuated by a high mean of 1.10 and standard deviation of .345. The wider implication is that there is the near absence of unlearned male characters in Nollywood films, even in village or remote settings, a situation that seems to present men as widely educated.

Fig 4.3: Histogram showing distribution of the proportion of characters who exhibited hypermasculine traits in the coded films

The distribution in Fig. 4.3 is a little bit skewed to the right but is a fairly normal distribution. The kurtosis and skewness tests showed an absolute kurtosis value of 0.567 (less than 3 times the standard error value of 0.177) and skewness value of 0.802. According to the rule of thumb, the data is moderately skewed (between 0.5 and 1).

Table 4.4: Age frameworks of male characters who exhibited hypermasculine traits in coded films

	Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. Deviation
Valid Teen/Adolescent	2	.3	4.27	.584
Young Adult	41	5.4		
Middle aged	475	62.7		
Old/elderly	231	30.5		
Indeterminate	8	1.1		
Total	757	100.0		

Source: Researcher's Field Data, 2018

Data presented in Table 4.4 above shows the age frameworks of various male characters that exhibited hypermasculine traits in select films. The table shows that majority (62.7%) of the male characters that exhibited hypermasculine traits in select films were middle aged; whereas the least proportion (0.3%) of the male characters that exhibited hypermasculine traits were teens/adolescents.

The dataset is stressed by a very high mean of 4.27 and standard deviation of .584. The broader implication being that majority of the male characters who show hypermasculine traits as coded in the select Nollywood films are middle-aged males and to a reasonable extent, old/elderly persons.

Fig 4.4: Histogram showing distribution of age frameworks of male characters who exhibited hypermasculine traits in coded films

The distribution in Fig. 4.4 is symmetrically skewed and is a normal distribution. The kurtosis and skewness tests showed an absolute kurtosis value of 0.417 (less than 3 times the standard error value of 0.177) and skewness value of 0.113. According to the rule of thumb, the data is fairly symmetrical (between -0.5).

Table 4.5: Occupations of male characters who exhibited hypermasculine traits in coded films

	Frequency	Valid Percent	Mean	Std. Deviation
Valid Pink-collar worker	353	46.6	1.97	1.046
Blue-collar worker	136	18.0		
White-collar worker	206	27.2		
Unemployed	58	7.7		
Indeterminate	4	.5		
Total	757	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s Field Data, 2018

Data presented in Table 4.5 above shows the occupation of the various male characters that exhibited hypermasculine traits in select films. The table shows that majority (46.6%) of the male characters were pink-collar workers; whereas the occupation of least proportion (0.5%) of the male characters were indeterminate. The trend that is most visible in the table is that Nollywood portrayed men as mostly with some kind of occupation.

The dataset is accentuated by a high mean of 1.97 and standard deviation of 1.46. The implication being that a slight majority of the male characters who show hypermasculine traits as coded in the select Nollywood films are pink-collar workers, with a sizeable proportion being white-collar workers and to a reasonable extent, blue-collar workers.

Fig 4.5: Histogram showing normality of the data on occupation of male characters who exhibited hypermasculine traits in coded films

The distribution in Fig. 4.5 is a little bit skewed to the right but is a fairly normal distribution. The kurtosis and skewness tests showed an absolute kurtosis value of -0.941 (less than 3 times the standard error value of 0.177) and skewness value of 0.567. According to the rule of thumb, the data is moderately skewed (between 0.5 and 1).

Table 4.6: Marital status of male characters who exhibited hypermasculine traits in coded films

	Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. Deviation
Valid Single	417	55.1	1.50	.646
Married	326	43.1		
Widowed	7	.9		
Indeterminate	7	.9		
Total	757	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s Field Data, 2018

Data presented in Table 4.6 shows the marital statuses of the various male characters that exhibited hypermasculine traits in select films. The Table shows that majority (55.1%) of the male characters were single; and the least (0.9%) of the male characters were either widowed or indeterminate. A sizeable proportion of those male characters are married but the glaring trend in the table is that Nollywood sells the idea that a man is either married or single, and hardly somewhere in-between. The dataset is accentuated by a high mean of 1.50 and standard deviation of .646. The broader implication being that single and married male characters in the select Nollywood films show almost equal amount of hypermasculine traits, with those of the single male characters being only slightly higher.

Fig 4.6: Histogram showing normality of the data on marital status of male characters who exhibited hypermasculine traits in coded films

The distribution in Fig. 4.6 is slightly skewed to the right but is a fairly normal distribution. The kurtosis and skewness tests showed an absolute kurtosis value of 0.53 (less than 3 times the standard error value of 0.177) and skewness value of 0.983. According to the rule of thumb, the data is moderately skewed (between 0.5 and 1).

Table 4.7: Family life of male characters who exhibited hypermasculine traits in coded films

	Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. Deviation
Valid Being a Member of a Nuclear Family	385	50.9	2.99	2.244
Being a Single Parent	5	.7		
Having Single Parent	102	13.5		
Being in an Adoptive Family	1	.1		
Being a Member of a Stepfamily	23	3.0		
Unable to Determine	241	31.8		
Total	757	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s Field Data, 2018

Data presented in Table 4.7 above shows the family life of the various male characters that exhibited hypermasculine traits in select films. The table shows that majority (50.9%) of the male characters were part of a nuclear family and the least of them (0.1%) had an adoptive family. That is exactly what you would expect in a typical Nigerian family. Majority of the people in society are part of a nuclear family.

The dataset in Table 4.7 is stressed by a high mean of 2.99 and standard deviation of 2.244. The implication being that majority of the male characters who exhibited hypermasculine traits in select films were part of a nuclear family and the family life of reasonable number of the male characters who exhibited hypermasculine traits in select films could not be determined.

Fig 4.7: Histogram showing normality of the data on family life of male characters who exhibited hypermasculine traits in coded films.

The distribution in Fig. 4.7 is symmetrically skewed and is a fairly distribution but it has a bit of a kurtosis issue. The kurtosis test showed an absolute kurtosis of 0.637 which is an issue because it

does not align with the rule of thumb since it is greater than 3 times the standard error value of 0.177 and the lines are not properly peaked. But in terms of skewness, with a value of .432, the data is fairly symmetrical (because -0.5).

Table 4.8: Social status of male characters who exhibited hypermasculine traits in coded films

	Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. Deviation
Valid Lower	184	24.3	2.12	.875
Upper Middle	365	48.2		
Upper	142	18.8		
Lower Middle Class	66	8.7		
Total	757	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s Field Data, 2018

Data presented in Table 4.8 above shows the social status of the various male characters that exhibited hypermasculine traits in select films. The table shows that majority (48.2%) of the male characters belong to the upper middle class and the least (8.7%) of them belong to the lower middle class. It shows that Nollywood hardly have lower middle class male characters: they are either so rich or so poor.

The dataset in Table 4.8 is accentuated by a very high mean of 2.12 and standard deviation of .875. The implication being that majority of the male characters who exhibited hypermasculine traits in select films belong to the upper middle class; with reasonable percentages belonging to the upper and lower classes.

Fig 4.8: Histogram showing normality of the data on social status of male characters who exhibited hypermasculine traits in coded films

The distribution in Fig 4.8 is symmetrically skewed and is a normal distribution. The kurtosis and skewness tests showed an absolute kurtosis value of 0.286 (which is normally peaked since it is less than 3 times the standard error value of 0.177) and skewness value of 0.500. According to the rule of thumb, the data is fairly symmetrical (between -0.5).

Table 4.9: Hypermasculine traits exhibited by male characters in coded films

		Frequency	Percent	Mean	SD
Valid	Violence as manly	1543	20.6	3.21	1.5
	Callous attitude towards women and sex	1497	20.0		4
	Danger as exciting	408	5.4		
	Toughness as emotional self-control	1906	25.4		
	Other hypermasculine traits	2144	28.6		
	Total	7498	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s Field Data, 2018

Data presented in Table 4.9 above shows the hypermasculine traits exhibited by the various male characters in the select films. The table shows that almost all hypermasculine traits were equally exhibited in the films, except for *danger as exciting*: 20.6% for violence as manly; 20.0% for callous attitude towards women and sex; 25.4% for toughness as emotional self-control; and 28.6% for other hypermasculine traits not included in the four indices of hypermasculinity earlier presented.

The dataset in Table 4.9 is accentuated by a very high mean of 3.21 and standard deviation of 1.54, the implication of which is that all hypermasculine traits, with the exception of showing danger as exciting are reasonably demonstrated by the various male characters in the select films.

Fig. 4.9: Histogram showing normality of the data on hypermasculine traits exhibited in coded films

The distribution in Fig. 4.9 is symmetrically skewed and is a normal distribution. The kurtosis and skewness test showed an absolute kurtosis value of 0.513, which is a bit of an issue, albeit

insignificant, since it is greater than 3 times the standard error value of 0.157. According to the rule of thumb, with a skewness value of .231, the data is fairly symmetrical (between -0.5 and 0.5).

Table 4.10: Descriptive Statistics showing the distribution of each of the hypermasculine traits in the select films

	Frequency	Mean	Std. Dev
Valid Violence as manly	1543	2.35	1.62
Callous attitude towards women and sex	1497	2.22	1.60
Danger as exciting	408	1.17	.45
Toughness as emotional self-control	1906	3.50	1.66
Other hypermasculine traits	2144	4.27	4.54
Total	7498		

Source: Researcher’s Field Data, 2018

The descriptive data presented in Table 4.10 above shows the mean and standard deviation distribution of the individual hypermasculine traits in the select films in order to reveal the overarching traits that was depicted in those films. The table shows that almost all hypermasculine traits have equal mean and standard deviation, with the exception of *danger as exciting*.

The implication is that, just as the frequencies suggest, the mean value stresses that it is not so easy to point at the overarching hypermasculine traits in the select film, as there is no significant mean difference between violence as manly, callous attitude towards women and sex, toughness as emotional self-control; and other hypermasculine traits not included in the four indices of hypermasculinity. The exception is danger, which has a significantly low frequency and mean values.

Table 4.11: Equitability of traits exhibited by male characters in coded films

	Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. Dev
Valid Gender equitable traits	8954	85.7	1.14	.350
Non-gender equitable traits	1497	14.3		
Total	10451	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s Field Data, 2018

Data presented in Table 4.11 above shows the equitability of gender traits exhibited by the various male characters in the select films. The table shows that there were more gender equitable than non-gender equitable traits in those films.

The dataset in Table 4.11 is stressed by a high mean of 1.14 and standard deviation of .350, the implication of which is that there is markedly more gender equitable than non-gender equitable traits.

Fig 4.10: Histogram showing normality of the data on equitability of traits exhibited in coded films

The distribution in Fig. 4.10 is a little bit skewed to the right but is a fairly normal distribution. The kurtosis and skewness tests showed an absolute kurtosis value of 0.150, which is just a bit higher than 3 times the standard error value of 0.48, revealing a minor kurtosis issue; and the absolute skewness value of 0.037. According to the rule of thumb, the data is fairly symmetrical (between -0.5 and 0.5).

Table 4.12: Hypermasculinity frameworks expressed in the films

		Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. Dev
Valid	Gender role socialization	438	57.9	1.67	.850
	Biological essentialism	129	17.0		
	Social constructionism	190	25.1		
	Total	757	100.0		

Source: Researcher’s Field Data, 2018

Data presented in Table 4.12 above shows the hypermasculinity frameworks expressed by the various male characters in the select films. The table shows that majority (57.9%) of the male characters who exhibited hypermasculine traits were framed by gender role socialization but the least (17.0%) of them were framed by biological essentialism.

The dataset in Table 4.12 is stressed by a high mean of 1.67 and standard deviation of .850, the implication of which is that majority of the male characters who exhibited hypermasculine traits were framed by gender role socialization.

Fig 4.11: Histogram showing normality of the data on hypermasculine framework expressed in coded films

The distribution in Fig. 4.11 is a little bit skewed to the right but is a fairly normal distribution. The kurtosis and skewness tests showed an absolute kurtosis value of .275 (less than 3 times the standard error value of 0.177) and skewness value of 0.681. According to the rule of thumb, the data is moderately skewed (between 0.5 and 1).

4.2 Test of the Hypotheses

In this section, the researcher tests in five (5) hypotheses proposed in the study, using various kinds of parametric and nonparametric tests. The various analyses were once again based on the use of SPSS Version 23. The hypotheses are tested in the null.

Here is re-statement of the hypotheses:

- H_i1: There is a significant correlation between the demographics of the male actors and depictions of hypermasculinity traits in the select Nollywood films.
- H_i2: The Frameworks of hypermasculinity are evenly responsible for the various hypermasculinity traits depicted in select Nollywood films.
- H_i3: The non-gender-equitable masculinity traits are significantly higher than the gender equitable masculinity traits in the select Nollywood films.

4.2.1. Hypothesis One: There is a significant correlation between the demographics of the male actors and depictions of hypermasculinity traits in the select Nollywood films.

A number of tests were done to examine the correlation between the demographics of the male actors and depictions of hypermasculinity traits in the select Nollywood films. Regression analyses were conducted to determine the relationship between the demographics, including the age, literacy level, social status, family life and marital status, to hypermasculine traits, both in their entirety and individually. The significant threshold of the analysis was set at .005; therefore p-value is significant when it is less than the threshold.

Note: to prepare data for regression analyses, it is important to check that data for violations of the assumptions of the statistical tests underlying regression: normality of the variables. Said checks were done and reported on Fig 4.6 for normality of the distribution of literacy level of the male characters even though it was slightly skewed positively (right skew) but no kurtosis issues; Fig 4.8 for normality of the distribution of literacy level of the male characters and the distribution was

symmetrically skewed and is a normal distribution with no kurtosis issues; Fig. 4.10 for normality of the distribution of occupations of the male characters is moderate though a little bit skewed to the right (positive skew) but is a fairly normal distribution; and Fig 4.12 for normality of the distribution of marital status of the male characters is also moderate though a little bit skewed to be right (positive skew) but is a fairly normal distribution.

Furthermore, Fig 4.14 reported the normality of the distribution of family life of the male characters and shows that it symmetrically skewed and is a fairly normal distribution but it has a bit of a kurtosis issue; and Fig. 4.16 is for normality of the distribution of social status of the male characters is symmetrically skewed and is a fairly normal distribution. There are significantly no violations of the assumptions of normality in the demographic variables. However, multiple regression was used in the test of this hypothesis as it is said to be strong even when there is a slight deviation of the assumptions of normality, particularly when the sample size is large (Green & Salkind, 2005).

4.2.1.1. Regression of demographic dispositions of male characters on overall hypermasculine traits in the select films

The univariate regression analyses on Table 4.13 below were done using each of age, literacy level, social status, family life and marital status as predictor variables to determine the strength of the relationship between each of the predictor variables and overall hypermasculine traits in the select films.

Table 4.13: Univariate regressions of age, literacy level, social status, family life and marital status on overall hypermasculine traits in the select films.

	Predictor	R	R-squared	F	DF	p-value
Valid	Age of character	.695	.483	706.441	1	<.005
	Literacy level of character	.400	.160	144.172	1	<.005
	Social status of character	.125	.016	12.031	1	<.005
	Occupation of character	.822	.676	1576.19	1	<.005
	Family life of character	.927	.859	4609.734	1	<.005
	Marital status of character	.554	.307	333.733	1	<.005

Source: Researcher’s Field Data, 2018

A comparison of the results of the regression analyses on Table 4.13 showed that all six demographic variable were significant predictors of overall hypermasculinity at $p < .005$. However, R and R-Squared values differ for all the predictors.

Note: R represents the simple correlation between the demographic variables as predictors and the hypermasculine traits whereas R-Squared values indicate how much of the variation in hypermasculinity can be explained by each of the predictors.

Family life of the male characters was the strongest predictor of hypermasculinity ($R = .927$; $R\text{-Squared} = .859$), accounting for 92.7% correlation with the hypermasculine traits, which indicates a very strong and very high degree of correlation (see Table 14), and also accounts for 85.9% of the variance in the depiction of overall hypermasculinity, which means that 85.9% of the total variance in hypermasculinity can be explained by the family life of the male characters. That is, family life of the characters is weighted more heavily than other predictors.

That is followed by occupation of the male characters ($R = .822$; $R\text{-Squared} = .676$), accounting for 82.2% correlation with the hypermasculine traits, which indicates strong and high degree of correlation (see Table 4.14), and also accounts for 67.6% of the variance in the depiction of overall hypermasculinity, which means that 67.6% of the total variance in hypermasculinity can be explained by the occupation of the male characters.

Next is the age of the male characters ($R = .695$; $R\text{-Squared} = .483$), accounting for 69.5% correlation with the hypermasculine traits, which indicates a moderate degree of correlation (see

Table 14), and also accounts for 48.3% of the variance in the depiction of overall hypermasculinity, which means that 48.3% of the total variance in hypermasculinity can be explained by the age of the male characters.

That is followed by marital status the male characters ($R = .554$; $R\text{-Squared} = .307$), accounting for 55.4% correlation with the hypermasculine traits, which indicates moderate degree of correlation (see Table 14), and also accounts for 30.7% of the variance in the depiction of overall hypermasculinity, which means that 30.7% of the total variance in hypermasculinity can be explained by the marital status of the male characters.

Next is the literacy status of the male characters ($R = .400$; $R\text{-Squared} = .160$), accounting for 40.0% correlation with the hypermasculine traits, which indicates weak and low degree of correlation (see Table 14), and also accounts for 16% of the variance in the depiction of overall hypermasculinity, which means that 16% of the total variance in hypermasculinity can be explained by the literacy status of the male characters.

The least is the social status of the male characters ($R = .125$; $R\text{-Squared} = .016$), accounting for 12.5% correlation with the hypermasculine traits, which indicates very weak correlation (see Table 14), and also accounts for 1.6% of the variance in the depiction of overall hypermasculinity, which means that 1.6% of the total variance in hypermasculinity can be explained by the male characters.

Table 4.14: Classification of Correlation

Range	Interpretation
0.0 to 0.2	Very weak
0.2 to 0.4	Weak and low
0.4 to 0.7	Moderate
0.7 to 0.9	Strong and high
0.9 to 1.9	Very strong and very high

Source: Rowntree (1987)

4.2.1.2 Multiple regressions of demographic dispositions on overall hypermasculine traits in the select films.

This analysis was done as an extension of the linear regression above. It was important to predict the general and relative contribution of the demographic dispositions to the overall hypermasculine traits. How each demographic characteristic of the male characters varies with the overall hypermasculinity traits when other demographics characteristics are held constant were also analyzed.

Table 4.15: Model summary of the multiple regression statistics

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.941 ^a	.885	.884	.290

a. Predictors: (Constant), Family life of the character, Social Status of Characters, Educational status of characters, Marital status of characters, Age of character, occupation of the Characters

The multiple regression coefficient (R) which indicates the quality of the prediction of the hypermasculinity traits as the dependent variable is .941. Therefore, a value of .941 indicates a very good level of prediction, from table 15 above, the coefficient of determination (R-square) is .885. That is to say, the demographic dispositions of the male characters explain 88.5% of the variability of the hypermasculinity traits shown by the male characters in those films.

Table 4.16: Analysis of the variance between demographics and hypermasculinity

Model	Sum of Square	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	483.794	6	80.632	960.534	.00 ^b
Residual	62.959	750	.084		
Total	546.753	756			

a. Dependent Variable: Hypermasculinity Traits

b. Predictors: (Constant), Family life of the characters, Social Status of Characters, Educational status of characters, Marital status of character, Age of character, occupation of the Characters.

The *F*-ratio in table 4.16 above shows that the independent variables (family life of the characters, social status of characters, educational status of characters, marital status of character, age of character, occupation of the characters) statistically significantly predict the dependent variable (hypermasculinity traits): thus, $F(6, 750) = 960.534, p < .0005$.

4.2.1.3 Multiple regression analyses predicting each of the hyper-masculine traits individually using the demographic dispositions

It was important to determine if the individual hypermasculinity traits were differentially related to the demographic dispositions of the male characters. After conducting the multiple regression analysis in the last section (reported in Table 4.15 and 4.16) using proportion of hypermasculinity overall as the predicted score, multiple regression equations were also computed predicting each of the hyper-masculine traits individually. The purpose of these analyses was to determine if the individual hyper-masculinity traits were differentially related to the demographic dispositions. The results of the multiple regression equations using age, literacy level, social status, family life and marital status as the predictor variables on the individual hyper-masculinity traits (violence as manly, toughness as emotional self-control, calloused attitude towards women, and danger as exciting) are presented in Table 4.17 through 4.20, respectively.

Table 4.17: Multiple regressions of age, literacy level, social status, occupation, family life and marital status on *violence is manly* in the select films

	Predictor	R	R-squared	F	DF	p-value
Valid	Age of character	.203	.401	32.530	1	<.005
	Literacy level of character	.160	.026	19.961	1	<.005
	Social status of character	.020	.000	.295	1	.587
	Occupation of character	.078	.006	4.603	1	.032
	Family life of character	.153	.23	17.996	1	<.005
	Marital status of character	.061	.004	2.827	1	.093

The regression analyses on Table 4.17 showed that only 3 demographic variable (age, literacy level and family life) were significant predictors of *violence as manly* at $p < .005$. However, R and R-

Squared values differ for the 3 predictors. As the table shows, age is more strongly related ($R^2=.041$) than literacy level ($R^2=.026$) and family life ($R^2=0.23$)

Table 4.18: Multiple regressions of age, literacy level, social status, occupation, family life and marital status on callous attitude towards women and sex in the select films

	Predictor	R	R-squared	F	DF	p-value
Valid	Age of character	.193	.037	29.342	1	<.005
	Literacy level of character	.153	.023	18.033	1	<.005
	Social status of character	.508	.003	2.056	1	<.114
	Occupation of character	.081	.007	5.037	1	.025
	Family life of character	.158	.025	19.316	1	<.005
	Marital status of character	.034	.001	.894	1	.345

The regression analyses on Table 18 showed that only 4 demographic variables (age, occupation, marital status and family life) were significant predictors of *danger as exciting* at $p<.005$. However, R and R-Squared values differ for the 4 predictors. As the table shows, occupation of the character is more strongly related ($R^2=.461$) than age ($R^2=.038$), family life ($R^2=.267$) and marital status ($R^2=.227$)

Table 4.20: Multiple regressions of age, literacy level, social status, occupation, family life and marital status on toughness as emotional self-control in the select films

	Predictor	R	R-squared	F	DF	p-value
Valid	Age of character	.193	.037	29.342	1	<.005
	Literacy level of character	.153	.023	18.033	1	<.005
	Social status of character	.508	.003	2.056	1	.114
	Occupation of character	.081	.007	5.037	1	.025
	Family life of character	.158	.025	19.316	1	<.005
	Marital status of character	.034	.001	.894	1	.345

The regression analyses on Table 4.20 showed that only 3 demographic variables (age, literacy level and family life) were significant predictors of *toughness as emotional self-control* at $p < .005$. However, R and R-Squared values differ for the 3 predictors. As the table shows, age is more strongly related ($R^2 = .037$) than family life ($R^2 = .025$), and literacy level ($R^2 = .023$)

Table 4.21: Multiple regressions of age, literacy level, social status, occupation, family life and marital status on *other hypermasculine traits* in the select films

	Predictor	R	R-squared	F	DF	p-value
Valid	Age of character	.340	.115	98.439	1	<.005
	Literacy level of character	.268	.072	58.513	1	<.005
	Social status of character	.293	.086	71.089	1	.114
	Occupation of character	.335	.112	95.522	1	<.005
	Family life of character	.327	.107	90.243	1	<.005
	Marital status of character	.004	.000	.012	1	.915

The regression analyses on Table 4.21 showed that only 4 demographic variables (age, occupation, literacy level and family life) were significant predictors of *other hypermasculine traits* not explained by the four indices of hypermasculinity at $p < .005$. However, R and R-Squared values differ for the 4 predictors. As the table shows, age of the character is more strongly related ($R^2 = .117$) than occupation ($R^2 = .112$), family life ($R^2 = .107$), and literacy level ($R^2 = .072$).

4.2.2 Hypothesis Two: The frameworks of hypermasculinity are evenly responsible for the various hypermasculinity traits depicted in select Nollywood films.

A number of tests were done to examine the association between the frameworks of hypermasculinity and the various hypermasculinity traits depicted in the select Nollywood films: that is, the strength of the association between relative movements of the two variables. Correlation coefficient was used to measure the degree of relations between the frameworks of hypermasculinity and the various hypermasculinity traits. Regression analysis was also conducted

to determine the said association. The significant threshold of the analysis was set at .005. Therefore p-value is significant when it is less than the threshold.

4.2.2.1 Correlations of the frameworks of hypermasculinity and the various hypermasculinity traits in the select films

The univariate regression analyses on Table 4.22 below were done using each of age, literacy level, social status, family life and marital status as predictor variables to determine the strength of the relationship between each of the predictor variables and overall hypermasculine traits in the select films.

Table 4.22: Correlations of the frameworks of hypermasculinity with hypermasculinity traits

			Violence as manly	Callous attitude towards women and sex	Danger as exciting	Toughness as emotional self-control	Other hypermasculinity traits
Spearman's rho	Gender role socialization	Correlation Coefficient	-.532**	-.532**	-.567**	-.532	-.586**
		Sig. (e-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
		N	438	438	408	438	438
	Biological essentialism	Correlation Coefficient	.00
		Sig(2-tailed)	
		N	129	129	129	129	129
	Social constructionism	Correlation Coefficient	-.405**
		Sig. (2tailed)000
		N	190	190	190	190	190

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.001 level (2-tailed).

The analyses on Table 4.22 above shows that, with the hypermasculinity traits as follows: violence as manly (-.532), callous attitude towards women and sex (-.532), danger as exciting (-.567), toughness as emotional self-control (-.532) and other hypermasculinity traits (-.596), and social constructionism which showed negative correlations with other hypermasculinity traits (-.405),

there was no sort of correlations between the frameworks of hypermasculinity and the various hypermasculinity traits in the select films. While the negative association was statistically significant at $p < 0.005$, it can be inferred from the table that there is no association between the framework of hypermasculinity and hypermasculinity traits in the select films.

4.2.2.2 Regressions of the frameworks hypermasculinity with hypermasculinity traits in the select films

The univariate regression analysis on Table 4.23 below was done to determine the strength of the relationship between the frameworks of hypermasculinity and hypermasculinity traits in the select films. Incidentally, following the SPSS analysis, only *gender role socialization* as a framework of hypermasculinity and some *hypermasculine traits* had a sort of interaction, which is why it is the only result provided below.

As always, R represents the simple correlation between the frameworks of hypermasculinity with hypermasculinity traits whereas R-Squared values indicate how much of the variation in hypermasculinity traits can be explained by each of the frameworks.

Table 4.23: Model summary of the multiple regression statistics

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error	Sig.
1	.699 ^a	.488	.484	.000	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), other hypermasculinity traits, toughness as emotional self-control, danger as exciting

The multiple regression coefficient (R) which indicates the quality of the prediction of the hypermasculinity traits as the dependent variable is .699. Therefore, a value of .699 indicate a good level of prediction and is statistically significantly since $p < .005$. From table 15 above, the coefficient of determination (R-square) is .488. That is to say, gender role socialization explains 48.8% of the variability of the hypermasculinity traits.

There are however no sufficient statistical based to conclude that there is an association between the frameworks of hypermasculinity and hypermasculinity traits in the select films. Therefore, the

researcher rejects the alternate hypothesis that the frameworks of hypermasculinity are evenly responsible for the various hypermasculinity traits depicted in select Nollywood films.

4.2.3 Hypothesis Three: The non-gender-equitable masculinity traits are significantly higher than the gender equitable masculinity traits in the select Nollywood films.

Descriptive statistics (Mean and standard deviation) and T-test (inferential statistics) were used to find out the weighted means of the non-gender-equitable masculinity and gender equitable masculinity traits in the select films as well as compare their means to determine whether there is significant difference between them. The essence of combining descriptive and inferential statistics is that the inferential statistics helps the researcher to establish with some degree of confidence that the obtained mean of the sample groups in the descriptive statistics was too great to be a chance event and there is a real difference between the sample groups.

Table 4.24: Descriptive statistics on non-gender-equitable masculinity and gender equitable masculinity traits in the select films

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Gender equitable	8954	1	5	2.61	1.725
Non-gender equitable	1497	1	4	2.19	.908
Valid N (listwise)	1497				

Descriptive analyses in Table 4.24 reveals that gender equitable masculinity traits had 8954 occurrences in the select films, whereas non-gender equitable masculinity traits had 1497 occurrences. The mean value and standard deviation of gender equitable masculinity traits are 2.61 and 1.725 respectively; while the mean value and standard deviation of non-gender equitable masculinity traits are 2.19 and .908 respectively. On plain statistical bases, the gender equitable masculinity traits are higher than the non-gender equitable masculinity traits in the select films. However, how significant is the difference?

Table 4.25: One-sample T-test on non-gender-equitable masculinity and gender equitable masculinity traits in the select films

	Test Value = 0					
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Gender equitable	234.952	8953	.000	2.610	2.59	2.63
Non-gender equitable	93.461	1496	.000	2.194	2.15	2.24

The means score of Gender equitable masculinity traits [$t(8953) = 234.952, p < .005$] was statistically significantly higher than the mean score of non-gender-equitable masculinity traits [$t(1496) = 93.461, p < .005$] in the select films. Owing to the statistically significant difference between the means ($p < .05$), we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternate hypothesis that non-gender-equitable masculinity traits are significantly higher than the gender equitable masculinity traits in the select Nollywood films. The implication is that it is evident from the test of hypothesis that gender equitable masculinity traits were statistically significantly higher than the non-gender-equitable masculinity traits in the select films, and not the other way around.

4.3 Inductive Analysis of Interview Responses

In this section, the qualitative information collected in the in-depth interview sessions were presented and analyzed. The idea is to be able to make sense of the oral responses of the participants by searching for patterns that lie within their bounds (Park & Park, 2016).

It is inductive because the researcher, in this section, generated new themes emerging from the verbal responses of the interviewees. The inductive approach is usually used to report patterns existing in the responses and string them together to resolve research objectives. The approach is used to reduce volumes of verbal materials into more manageable and relevant data from which the researcher identifies patterns and gain insight. Themes are allowed to emerge from the responses through repeated examination and comparison of the responses.

So, what this researcher did in this section was to organize the raw responses after transcribing them; then the researcher used open coding to review the materials: that is, notes and headings

were made in the text as they were read repeatedly; then, similar headings were brought together into broader categories. Common words, phrases and concepts mentioned in the oral responses were brought together to enable the researcher use them to answer specific research questions.

That is, the noteworthy answers from the interviewees that are in tandem with the objectives of the study were underlined, enabling the researcher to sift through the responses, remove irrelevant portions and analyse the portions highlighted.

In table 4.26 below, the respondents were identified by arbitrary letters and codes without their names, on the basis that they were promised confidentiality and anonymity prior to the interview sessions.

Table 4.26 Details of In-depth Interview Participants

Identifiers	State	Code	Occupation	Experience (in Years)	Sex
Interviewee 1	Abia	AB1	Lecturer	8	F*
Interviewee 2	Abia	AB2	Film Producer	10	M**
Interviewee 3	Abia	AB3	Lecturer	15	M
Interviewee 4	Abia	AB4	Lecturer	8	F
Interviewee 5	Abia	AB5	Film Producer	9	M
Interviewee 6	Abia	AB6	Actress	7	F
Interviewee 7	Anambra	AN1	Lecturer	17	F
Interviewee 8	Anambra	AN2	Lecturer	10	M
Interviewee 9	Anambra	AN3	Film Producer	7	F
Interviewee 10	Anambra	AN4	Film Director	7	M
Interviewee 11	Anambra	AN5	Lecturer	10	F
Interviewee 12	Anambra	AN6	Actor	8	M
Interviewee 13	Imo	IM1	Lecturer	18	F
Interviewee 14	Imo	IM2	Film Producer	11	M
Interviewee 15	Imo	IM3	Actor/Film Editor	10	M
Interviewee 16	Imo	IM4	Film Director	11	M
Interviewee 17	Imo	IM5	Lecturer	14	F
Interviewee 18	Imo	IM6	Lecturer	15	M
Interviewee 19	Ebonyi	EB1	Lecturer	10	F
Interviewee 20	Ebonyi	EB2	Film Producer	9	M
Interviewee 21	Ebonyi	EB3	Actress	12	F
Interviewee 22	Ebonyi	EB4	Actor	8	M
Interviewee 23	Ebonyi	EB5	Lecturer	12	F
Interviewee 24	Ebonyi	EB6	Lecturer	7	M
Interviewee 25	Enugu	EN1	Lecturer	18	F
Interviewee 26	Enugu	EN2	Lecturer	17	F
Interviewee 27	Enugu	EN3	Actor	20	M

Interviewee 28	Enugu	EN4	Lecturer	16	F
Interviewee 29	Enugu	EN5	Film Producer	11	M
Interviewee 30	Enugu	EN6	Actress/Producer	18	F

4.3.1 Variety of hypermasculinity traits projected in Nollywood films.

The interviewees were of varied opinions regarding the variety of hypermasculinity traits projected in Nollywood films: to some, hypermasculinity is a "bogus term that should not be mentioned" (EB2) while describing the characteristics of men in Nollywood films and to others who hold opposite view, they insist that "Nollywood screenwriters, actors and all the people responsible for the production of stories and films... practically shove the bloated idea of manliness into the throats of every one of their viewers" (AN5). Whatever their views were, the researcher gained valuable insights on a variety of hypermasculinity traits projected or believed to have been projected in Nollywood films. One pattern of thought was evident: the majority of those who belonged to the academics are insistent of hypermasculinity in the films whereas the practitioners are averse to the suggestion of hypermasculinity in Nigeria films. For those who maintain there is "a bloated idea of manliness" in those films, their thoughts mirror one another, thus:

“...typical man in a Nigeria film is a boss who has the final decision to make about his life, home and society in the films... majority of the affairs of the society are handled by the men. It is common to see the kings and elder (all men) ruling a kingdom...” (AB1)

"...the man is seen as the superstructure and he is as well expected to behave that way. He is as well expected to behave that way..." (AN1)

“...to be warriors, to be lords okay those stereotypes that you see, that hardened king, that criminal, that kidnapper you are seeing, that insensitive man...”

Ironically, a man, a lecturer, AB3, spoke so passionately about the way that Nollywood fills our visual experience with so much violence from the men, so much that it appears “manhood stands for violence”. He says:

“I am uncomfortable with the way men are projected in films as wicked and violent and everything evil, and abhorrent and Machiavellian and jealous and volatile and aggressive... those are

what Nollywood is selling to us and unfortunately, we are buying that ...” (AB3)

Some of the respondents looked at hypermasculinity as anti-feminist expressions in Nollywood films and revealed that to be a man, one has to "subject the woman folks under his control and see power over women as a divine right” (EN2). It is a thought that is reflected by many respondents, thus:

“...men in Nigeria films forcefully compel the women in most cases to bend to their will. This coercion can also be evident in rape cases where a man rapes another woman or even his wife...” (AB1)

“...exercising unwarranted power over women... they see female characters as underdogs in the political setting...” (AB4)

"...he's always the subject while the woman on the other hand is always groomed, okay..." (AN1)

“... men are portrayed as violent towards women in Nigeria, mean dominant unemotional and sometimes even wicked towards women especially in films where a man dies and leaves behind properties for his family...” (AB1)

"...men are groomed in the films never to see anything wrong with them, men are groomed never to broker any nonsense from any woman, and so they grow up with this mindset and then in the area of intelligence, you see men downplaying the intelligence of the woman simply because she is a woman..." (AN1)

There seems to be a consensus among most respondents, especially the female lecturers the subjugation and objectification of women as a major hypermasculine trait seen in Nollywood films. They maintain that:

“...beating up a woman that is one that gives me the most concern...”(EN4)

“...men are portrayed as deceitful, they deceive women a lot... they lie to them telling them what they are not...” (IM1)

“...men are mean to women that their general attitudes towards them are not good in the movies...” (EN1)

“...the traits male characters project in Nigeria film is pretense and deceit... men are projected to be very deceitful to women, luring them into doing things that are of selfish interest to the male and pretend to be happy...” (IM3)

For those who maintain that hypermasculinity is a “bogus term that should not be mentioned” (EB2), what we perceive as hypermasculinity is clearly the exact representation of a man in society. They suggested that “manliness” is a rather more acceptable word than the “judgmental concept of hypermasculinity” (IM2).

Some of the respondents echoed that opinion as follows:

“...men are projected rightly because what so ever that is portrayed in Nigeria film is the same with what is happening in the society. The movie we watch is the mirror of the society therefore what so ever traits that are projected are not stereotypical rather it is an exact representation of a man in the society. (IM3)

“...it's easy to say what hypermasculine traits you find in films... you only have to look around you. Films are only a reflection of what we see every day. If a man in the real world is known to be aggressive, unemotional, bullish and so on, then that's exactly what you see in film...” (AB2)

One of the respondents who admitted that while it is true that there are hypermasculine traits in Nigeria films, it is not worrisome as it is merely because the media interact with the society and reflect the real-world idea of manliness:

“...from my point of view as a sociologist, media contents are full of hypermasculinity... yes, only because the society we live in... even the world at large, is full of it... we can't separate the media and society... they are in interaction...” (IM5)

Another respondent thinks that even if it is true that there are hypermasculine traits in Nigeria films, it is not in the same proportion as often discussed by some scholars:

“I am an actor and I do not think the films that I act or watch or show too much manliness, the way you described it... maybe on occasions but not too much... the ones that are shown mostly bother on a man taking charge of situations, just as you would expect a man to...” (EN3)

“...as a film director, I can tell you there are expressions of masculinity among men in the films and in the same proportion, there are expressions of femininity or feminism (I’m not sure which is correct) in the films... nothing more than necessary... those are part of being men and women...” (AN4)

Interestingly, a respondent feels that if we call masculine traits as hypermasculinity, we should also be prepared to call the positive side of men as hypermasculinity.

“... traits portray in Nigeria is generosity, men in the movie industry are generous...”(EN1)

4.3.2 The perceived frequency of occurrence of hypermasculinity in Nollywood films.

A decent number of the respondents, particularly those who believe that there is projection of hypermasculine traits in the films, considered the frequency of the traits as widespread. There seems to be a consensus among them that if the idea of manliness or masculinity is generally expressed regularly and is accepted in real life, then it is not a surprise if it expressed regularly since films, they maintained, are a reflection of real-world situations. They stressed that:

“... there is a lot of such occurrences...”(AN1)

“...since these films mirror the African society and what is portrayed in these films are reflection of the nature of a typical African man. The regularity of expression of hypermasculine traits is not any way in doubt...” (AB1)

“..sometimes it is so frequent in the films that some male characters... immediately you see them... in any movie... what will come in your

mind is that *this man go wicked or him to sabi beat woman...* be very mean to women...” (EB3)

“... like I said, as long as we see it every day, we should expect to see it every day in films... it’s part of the story. Hypermasculinity is the accepted fiber of the human nature both in real life and in films...” (AB2)

“... if you see many expressions of manliness in the films, it only means that you see many men...” (EN3)

“... it is just as you would see it in society... like I said we can separate the media and society because of their interaction” (IM5)

A respondent who was visibly agitated over the idea that there is hypermasculinity in Nollywood films, himself a film producer, feels that even if hypermasculine ideologies existed and are largely expressed in those films, they are justifiable and they are not more of a concern than the quantity of feminist ideologies in those films.

“...we see plenty men in films, so we see plenty expressions or representation of manliness... are you expecting us to wear skirt on a man and make him less of a man because you suspect we are showing too much... what again did you call it... hypermasculinity...” (AN4)

“... as a film director, I can tell you there are expressions of masculinity among men in the films and in the same proportions, there are expressions of femininity or feminism (I’m not sure which is correct) in the films... nothing more than necessary... those are part of being men and women...” (AN4)

4.3.3 The overarching hypermasculinity traits depicted in Nollywood films.

The responses of those who insist that there is clearly a projection of hypermasculine traits in Nollywood films show that their views about which of the traits is (are) predominant are parallel, as majority of their thoughts mirror themselves. Their opinion is that men often show violence against women and other men. Majority of them are from the anti-feminist perspective of saying that the man’s “worst evil is that he is repeatedly violent or aggressive towards women and we

have come to take that as normal and hegemonic and something that should not and cannot be challenged” (EB6).

The thoughts of the respondents from the anti-feminist perspective include:

“...it’s the one that bothers me most. That is, physical violence against women. Men are portrayed as violent towards women in Nigeria, mean, dominant, unemotional and sometimes even wicked towards women especially in films where a man dies and leaves behind properties for his family...” (AB1)

The overarching... when male characters become too overbearing and domineering towards women (AB4)

“... where the woman is always seen as the object, that is what bothers me the most...” (AN1)

"...the trends confirm that we have two structures, the first and the essential one is the man, and he is the subject; the second and inessential one is the woman and she is the object...the predominant one is the idea where women are always seen as the object or insignificant no matter how loaded the woman is..." (AN1)

“...mean or engaging in domestic violent beating up their wives all of that ...” (EB3)

“...the case whereby a man raises up his hands to beat a woman...” (IM1)

“... being violent, uncaring and dominating over the woman bother me the most...” (EB1)

Couple of the respondents feel it is impossible to choose a particular trait has been the dominant one expressed by men in the films, as according to them, they are all equally weighted.

“... in fact, all of them ...” (EN4)

“... to me all those unusual characters that they portray in Nigeria movie is a thing of concern...” (AB3)

Some respondents looked at violence, toughness and being dispassionate as the most recurring traits of the man in the films; and unlike those from the anti-feminist perspective, the emphasis here are on the traits and not on the receivers of the traits:

“... violence; violence bothers me the most and another bad trait that bothers me the most is being dispassionate... not having feelings anymore...” (EN1)

“...unemotional and dispassionate are the most recurring...” (IM3)

A couple of the respondents thought that the most recurring hypermasculine traits in the Nigeria films is when a man is overly dominant and is projected to be in control, particularly according to the expectations of the patriarchal society. They stress that:

“...the man is the boss... the man is dominant and commands respect and submission... that’s what is mostly seen ...” (AB2)

“...typical of the African man, what most men exhibit in the films is control... the man wants to be in control” (AN4)

4.3.4 The dominant framework of hypermasculinity projected in Nollywood films.

The responses of the participants concerning the framework of hypermasculinity project in Nollywood films appeared that majority of them feel that gender role socialization is the most dominant framework of hypermasculinity seen in those films; while a number of them hold different opinions but they are largely of the opinion that "everyone is a product of the society... a product of what the person grew up actually to see... a product of the reality around them...” (AN1)

Regarding those who believe that gender role socialization is the most dominant framework of hypermasculinity seen in those films, their responses reflect each other; thus:

“...these traits are not genetic but acquired in the society. Although, the society does not expect any human to be violent and callous, but it does little or nothing practically to defaulters especially when it is a man against a woman...’ (AB1)

“ I think the traits are not inborn, they are rather learned from older men or their peer in the films.....society expects every man to behave that way since there is no equality between the male and female gender in our society. This further explains why male characters are considered weak and ineffectual whenever they appear to be less stoic...” (AB4)

“...sometimes often talk of classical conditioning and socializations conduits for behavior...so that naturally applies to male characters in films... I’m a great fan of the Nigerian film industry... I want to believe that most traits in the films are learned...” (IM5)

Other respondents insist on biological essentialism as they maintain that aggression and other hypermasculine traits are largely inborn and have little or not to do with socialization or societal expectation of masculinity. They share parallel opinions, thus:

“...most men in the movies have this kind of aggressiveness in them because they are born with it, no matter how good a woman is they still have that aggressiveness toward them...” (IM1)

"...I believe it is inborn..."(EB1)

A couple of the respondents believe that the frameworks are situational and multi-dimensional as a man can acquire traits through any framework possible. It does not have to be from one framework only. They thought that:

“Each man his own, innate, socialized or otherwise... we are different even a man can learn from all the frameworks all at once... but I think majority of the masculine traits are learnt from observation...” (AB2)

“...like all traits, the source of acquisition is multi-dimensional... could come from many sources... I’m not sure there is a dominant source of learning traits...” (AN4)

The idea of social constructionism was hardly expressed by the respondents but it was also explained by AN1 as another observed framework of hypermasculinity in the films and one in which suggests that patriarchy is the soul of hypermasculinity as the patriarchal society expects a man to behave in a certain way. She stressed that:

“...this is African; and in African, there are certain expectations from men and women, and then also in Africa from childhood, men and women are groomed to behave differently... women are to take care of the needs of the man and so we see a situation where the men and the woman right from childhood have been, you know have been groomed to behave in a certain way and why we try to deviate from the accepted norm it becomes a problem...” (AN1)

4.3.5 The ratio gender equitable and non-gender-equitable masculinities in Nollywood films.

The proportions of gender equitable and non-gender-equitable masculinities in Nollywood films clearly divided opinions among the respondents. What is however common in the views of the respondents was that all the male characters exhibit both gender equitable and non-gender-equitable masculinities in those films. Even the most maligned male character exhibit equitable masculinities in Nollywood films, irrespective of the proportion. Whichever opinion the participants expressed, some of their responses were quite discerning.

While admitting that there are cases where men exhibited admirable equalities that endeared them to woman, children and their fellow men and gave them positive perception by the viewers, a number of the respondents still think that the projection of men as callous and aggressive and other negative portrayals far outweighs the positive portrayals. The words of those who hold this view mirror one another, thus:

“...there are few cases of gender equitable... but more negative traits of men” (AB1)

“Equitable? Yes, they are few instances... I think the negative traits of men are much more portrayed than the positive traits...” (AB4)

“...the traits that are more portrayed in recent films are the negative ones...” (EN1)

“...the negative trait is mostly portrayed because that is what is affecting the society...” (IM3)

One respondent chose to take what she referred to as the “middle ground” by not making any judgment with regard to which traits are more visible in the films: gender equitable and non-gender-equitable masculinities. She maintains that:

“I’ve seen films where there are admirable qualities in the man were highlighted... I will not completely say that the men are always negatively portrayed in Nigeria films, I take the middle ground here...”
(AN1)

“...I have seen loving and caring men; I have seen men who are caring, I’ve also seen tyrants... have also seen educated men who know the true worth of the woman and also behave accordingly... so, men are also loving, men are also kind, men are also caring. Have also seen many instances... in films...” (AN1)

Some respondents refused to be drawn into making judgments about whether there were more gender equitable traits than non-gender-equitable ones or otherwise. They only expressed the fact that they have seen a lot of gender equitable traits, where men exhibited caring, loving and admirable qualities in the movies. They stressed that:

“Yes, there are some cases that men are projected to be very loving...”
(EB3)

“... they sometimes show love, they show them love and care... they are so many instances of love and care. You often see a man show his wife love there was peace and harmony in that home...”(EN4)

“...there are cases when men are portrayed as loving, and that is when the man has something to benefit or something important he needs from the lady...” (IM1)

A number of respondents were obviously agitated over what they call the “demonization of men” (AB2) because they maintain that men have admirable qualities that are shown in the films much more than the traits that depict aggressiveness and callousness. They insist that men are well portrayed and there is an abundance of gender equitable traits, where men exhibited caring, loving and admirable qualities in the movies. Their thoughts reflect each other as follows:

“...the positive one is more constant because most Nigeria movie always end up in happy mood...” (IM1)

“...there are many instances where men are portrayed as loving and nice husbands in the movies... 65% of those men are caring and loving...” (EB1)

“...other traits they portray in Nigeria is generosity, men in the movie industry are generous there are such cases like that where men are portrayed to be caring and nice...”(EN1)

“... there are such instances that men are projected to be caring loving and nice to women and at the long run there is always a happy ending which gives a positive perception about male gender...” (IM3)

“...let’s not demonize men, please... there are certainly more loving and positive attributes of a man shown on films than just being aggressive towards women... to say otherwise will be an emotional statement...” (AB2)

“...away with all this conspiracy against men... we are certainly loving and caring, and that shows in our films...” (AN4)

“...there are certainly more gender equitable traits than otherwise ...a woman for instance can get angry and abusive towards men, so can a man... it doesn’t make any of them more evil than the other...” (EN3)

“...any argument about it? If all that we see in the films are negative traits of men or traits that suggest that men always have women under their armpit, then why do we even watch those films...? Most certainly, there are admirable qualities of men in those films... and they far outweigh those aggressive traits...” (IM5)

4.3.6 The proportion of hypermasculinity by the demographics of the male characters in Nollywood films.

The proportion of hypermasculinity by the demographics of the male characters in Nollywood films is another subject that clearly divides opinions among the respondents. However, most of the respondents are of the view that hypermasculine traits can be predicted by the demographics of the male characters in Nollywood films. The extent to which that is so and which of the demographic characteristic of the actors mostly influence their behavior,, is what divides opinion among the respondents.

A number of the respondents think the income level of the male characters mostly influences their exhibition of hypermasculine traits in the film, with the low-income earners having more propensities for hypermasculinity than then others. The words of those who hold this view mirror one another, thus:

"The low-income class men and the illiterates are largely portrayed to exhibit hyper-masculine traits..." (AB1)

"...men from the low-income class exhibit hypermasculine attitudes more than men from high-income class but I've also seen men from the high-income file okay, I've also seen men from high-income class beating their wives..."(AN1)

One respondent however maintained that the high-income earners have more propensity for hypermasculinity than the others:

"...those who are wealthy to some level have greater possibility of exhibiting the negative traits... I don't think there is any age bracket associated and literacy has possibilities also because there is every tendency that an illiterate's mentality is very low therefore there is possibility that they exhibit negative trait." (IM3)

There are respondents who think that the exhibition of hypermasculine traits in the films by the male characters is not a function of the demographic characteristics of the man but a function of other factors far removed from their demographics, such as temperament and certain privileges that the man enjoys. They stressed that:

"There is no particular income class, neither is there any age bracket or literacy level that is negatively portrayed..." (AB4)

"...anybody can be violent even men with low-income level or high-income level, some of them are violent their status has nothing to do with that..." (IM1)

"...no there is no particular age bracket or income level... (EB1)

"I am not sure a particular age, income, status or so exhibit more hypermasculine traits... I can only say that those who exhibit more hypermasculine traits especially those that affect women are those who feel that they enjoy certain privileges over them women..." (AB2)

"anyone can show traits of a man, especially the man that is in control... for those who are aggressive, it might not be a matter of age, income or the things you listed... but it might be a function of temperament..."(EN3)

A number of the respondents think that the age of the male characters mostly influences their exhibition of hypermasculine traits in the films, with the younger ones having more propensity for hypermasculinity than the others. Those respondents maintain that:

"...from what I have noticed the younger men... they exhibit it more than the elderly men..." (AN1)

"...so those traits that are being portrayed in Nigeria films are associated with some certain literacy level and age bracket..." (EN1)

4.4 Discussion of Findings

The findings of this research are discussed here in tandem with the research questions that guided this study as stated in chapter one of this thesis. The discussion is based on the analyses of the quantitative and qualitative data presented in the previous sections.

4.4.1 Research Question 1

What are the hypermasculinity traits projected in select Nollywood films?

It was first of all established that 83.3% of the characters clearly exhibited degrees of hypermasculine traits in the film; which is an indication the Nollywood films significantly sold hypermasculine ideologies as a collective characteristic of the male human. This was backed up by a high mean of 1.16 and a standard deviation of .368 – a clear accentuation of a significant prevalence of male characters exhibiting hypermasculine traits and the universality of hypermasculine ideologies in the films. It is important to use descriptive statistics to ascertain the statistical significance of the distribution and be able to conclude which item is significantly overarching.

Data presented in Table 4.9 shows that except seeing *danger as exciting*, other hypermasculine traits are sufficiently exhibited in the select films. The most prominent is *other hypermasculine traits* (28.6%): that is, any of the following acts engaged in by a male character: impulsivity, pursuit of self-esteem, self-reliant, primary of work, risk-taking, decisive, competitive, ambitious, confident, egotistical, assertive, competitive, aggressive, unemotional and never cries. The next prominent hypermasculine traits exhibited in the select Nigerian films include: *toughness as emotional self-control* (25.4%). *Violence as manly* (20.6%) and *callous attitude towards women and sex* (20.0%).

The dataset is accentuated by a very high mean of 3.21 and standard deviation of 1.54, the inference of which is that all hypermasculinity traits, with the exception of showing *danger as exciting*, are reasonably demonstrated by the various male characters in the select films.

Findings from the in-depth interview reveal that opinions are divided among the respondents over whether they should even be any such thing as hypermasculinity, as a fraction of the respondents believe it is "bogus term that should not be mentioned" (EB2) but for those who believe that "Nollywood... practically shove the bloated idea of manliness into the throats of every of their viewers" (AN5), the variety of hypermasculine traits evident in the films include "men are projected in films as wicked and violent and everything evil, and abhorrent and Machiavellian and jealous and volatile and aggressive" (AB3). Some of the respondents looked at hypermasculinity as anti-feminist expressions in Nollywood films and reveal that to be a man, one has to "subject the woman folks under his control and see power over women as a divine right" (EN2) and the hold the opinion that "men are portrayed as violent towards women in Nigeria, mean dominant unemotional and sometimes even wicked towards women" (AB1) with several demeaning actions such as "beating

up a woman" (EN4) and being "very deceitful to women, luring them into doing things that re of selfish interest to the male and pretend to be happy" (IM3).

Having already established in this study that the most prominent hypermasculinity traits exhibited in Nollywood films are those categorized as *other hypermasculine traits* (28.6%) accounting for all behaviours that demonstrate impulsively, pursuit of self-esteem, self-reliant, primary of work, risk-taking, decisive, competitive, ambitious, confident, egotistical, assertive, competitive, aggressive, unemotional and never cries. It was also revealed that other traits exhibited in the select Nigerian films in descending order of distinction or appearances include: *toughness as emotional self-control* (25.4%), *violence as manly* (20.6%) and *callous attitude towards women and sex* (20.0%).

The descriptive data presented in Table 4.10 shows the mean and standard deviation distribution of the individual hypermasculine traits in the select films in other to reveal the overarching traits that was depicted in those films. The analyses reveal that *violence as manly* has a mean value of 2.35 and a standard deviation of 1.62; *callous attitude towards women and sex* has a mean value of 2.22 and a standard deviation of 1.60; *danger as exciting* has a mean value of 1.17 and a standard deviation.45; *toughness as emotional self-control* has a mean value of 3.50 and a standard deviation of 1.66; and *other hypermasculine traits* has a mean value of 4.27 and a standard deviation of 4.54. The implication is that the frequency distribution only suggest a simple majority of the hypermasculine traits but the mean and standard deviation values stress that it is not so easy to point at the overarching hypermasculine traits in the select films, as there is no significant mean difference between violence as manly, callous attitude towards women and sex, toughness as emotional self-control; and other hypermasculine traits not included in the four indices of hypermasculinity. The exception is danger as exciting, which has a significantly low frequency and mean values.

Inference drawn from the in-depth interview is that the predominant hypermasculine traits exhibited in Nigerian films seems to be violence against women and other men, violence, toughness, being dispassionate and dominance. Those from the anti-feminist perspective of saying that the man's "worst evil is that he is repeatedly violent or aggressive towards women and we have come to take that as normal and hegemonic and something that should not and cannot be challenged" (EB6). Some respondents of similar persuasion noted that:

"Men are portrayed as violent towards women in Nigeria, mean, dominant, unemotional and sometimes even wicked towards women especially in films where a man dies and leaves properties for his family..." (AB1)

"...male characters become too overbearing and domineering towards women (AB4)

There are other respondents who feel it is impossible to choose a particular trait as been the dominant one expressed by men in the films because they are all equally weighted. That is why *AB3* stressed that "all those unusual characters that they portray in Nigeria movie is a thing of concern". Some respondents looked at violence, toughness and being dispassionate as the most recurring traits of the man in the films; and unlike those from the anti-feminist perspective, the emphasis here are on the traits and not on the receivers of the traits. That is why *IM3* particularly maintained that "unemotional and dispassionate are the most recurring traits." A couple of the respondents thought that the most recurring hypermasculine traits in the Nigerian films is when a man is overly dominant and is projected to be in control, particularly according to the expectations of the patriarchal society. They echo the opinion of *AB2* that: "...the man is the boss... the man is dominant and commands respect and submission... that's what is mostly seen..."

It is said that the traits associated with various levels of masculinity vary depending on location and context and are influenced by a variety of social and cultural factors (Witt, 2010). For the Nollywood films and by extension the Nigerian society, there is a reasonable projection of violence as manly, callous attitude towards women and sex, toughness as emotional self-control; and other hypermasculine traits not included in the four indices of hypermasculinity.

The discussion above is reflective of the thoughts of Siddhanta and Singh (2015) who consider the most emphasis of hypermasculinity to be on physical strength, aggression and sexuality while exhibiting emotional self-control as sign of toughness as well as composure and impassiveness in times of great stress.

To buttress the data presented above on the projection of hypermasculine traits by Nollywood films, Zaitchik and Mosher (1993) explains that hypermasculinity often comprises of a cluster of beliefs that includes toughness, violence, dangerousness, and calloused attitudes towards women and sex.

Typically, hypermasculinity concerns the social and cultural roles, personal traits, and behaviours, such as aggression and dominance, which are deemed acceptable for men (Mosher and Tomkins, 1988). Other traits traditionally cited as hypermasculine include courage, independence, and assertiveness (Murray, 2000), competition, logic and rational thinking, strength, boldness and aggressiveness (Jordan, 2014). Most of those traits are subsumed in the features projected by Nigerian films as shown in Table 9.

What it means is that Nollywood films portray violence and physical aggression as “manly ideas”, promoting a world where “all of male life is a struggle of dominance of others”, and where sex is seen as a matter of power. Behaviours such as acting tough and fighting are mostly projected as the only acceptable reactions to fear because masculinity does not permit expression of pain and vulnerability. The way men are projected in those films reveals that there is the idealization of stereotypically masculine traits, such as virility and physicality. For those reasons, it is safe to conclude that the select Nollywood films significantly sold hypermasculine ideologies as a collective character of the male human.

The above conclusion that Nollywood films significantly sold hypermasculine ideologies as a collective character of the male human based on their portrayal of the male characters is supported by the assumption of the stereotype theory that the repeated portrayals of men as having certain hypermasculine traits in the media will influence the perceived image people have of them. According to the theory, Nollywood films are reinforcing a stereotyped perception of Nigerian men by perpetuating rigid and hypermasculine portrayals of the male characters.

4.4.2 Research Question 2

How frequently did the hypermasculinity traits occur in the select Nollywood films?

The data presented in Table 4.9 and used to answer research question one above reveals that all hypermasculinity traits, with the exception of showing *danger as exciting*, are reasonably demonstrated by the various male characters in the select films, but it did not show the extent to which the traits are projected in each of the films. To do so, the incidences of hypermasculine traits in the select films were grouped into 6 frequency brackets, namely: 1-10 times, 11-20 times, 21-30 times, 31-40 times, 41-50 times and above 50 times, and each film was looked at in terms of the frequency of hypermasculine traits shown in each of them and to check which of the 6 frequency brackets that such occurrences belong to.

Data presented in Table 4.3 shows that majority of the films (39.2%) has between 11 and 20 incidences of hypermasculine traits exhibited in them; and a reasonable percentage of those films (30.8%) had between 21 and 30 incidences of hypermasculine traits exhibited in them; the rest include 18.9% of the films which had between 31 and 40 incidences of hypermasculinity; 7.6% had between 1 and 10 incidences of hypermasculine traits; 2.7% of the films had between 41 and 50 times and 0.8% of the films had over 50 incidence of hypermasculine traits.

That is to say, lined up in descending order of prevalence are films where hypermasculine traits occurred most prominently between 11 and 20 times and between 21 and 30 times, and to some lesser extents between 31 and 40 times, 1 and 10 times, 41 and 50 times and above 50 times. The implication is that most Nollywood that had between 11-20 incidence of hypermasculine traits, closely followed by the ones that had 21 and 30 incidences, were more offered by the Nigerian film industry. Therefore, with a high mean of 2.72 and a standard deviation of .996, the overall inference drawn from the statistics is that there is regular occurrence and large amount of hypermasculine traits in Nollywood films.

The result points to the fact that films often depict hyper-masculine ideology. All the films analyzed contained varied levels hypermasculine traits. This finding confirms past quantitative and qualitative research indicating hypermasculinity to be widespread in films supports past observations and empirical conclusions that hypermasculine ideology may be accepted and/or idealized by many men and producers of media products, and that filmmakers in patriarchal societies try as hard as possible to reflect societal ideology of hegemonic masculinity and hypermasculinity, which are illustrative of patriarchy. Film producers know this and are selling plenty hypermasculine ideologies to their audience. They are providing status quo masculine gender representations that reinforce accepted and/or idealized ideas and beliefs about masculinity (e.g., callous attitude towards women and sex, toughness as a form of emotional self-control, violence as manly, etc.)

Qualitative data derived from the in-depth interview revealed that majority seems to be of the opinion that hypermasculinity is generally expressed regularly in films which is not a surprise since it is only a reflection of real-world situations. The concern however is that “there is a lot of such occurrences” (AN1), and as a film industry in a patriarchal society “the films mirror the African society and what is portrayed in these films are reflection of the nature of a typical African man;

the regularity of expression of hypermasculine traits is not in any way in doubt” (AB1). It is a thought that is buttressed by *EB3* as follows:

“...sometimes it is so frequent in the films that some male characters... immediately you see them... in any movie... what will come in your mind is that *this man go wicked or him go sabi beat woman...* be very mean to women...” (EB3)

The finding above does not discountenance the opinions of those who feel agitated over the idea that there is hypermasculinity in Nollywood films, as they feel that even if hypermasculine ideologies existed and are largely expressed in those films, they are justifiable and they are not more of a concern than the quantity of feminist ideologies in those films. That is why *AN4* expressed that:

“Should we make him less of a man because you suspect we are showing too much about him... what again did you call it... hypermasculinity...?” (AN4)

“...as a film director, I can tell you there are expressions of masculinity among men in the films and in the same proportion, there are expressions of femininity or feminism (I’m not sure which is correct) in the films... nothing more than necessary... those are part of being men and women...” (AN4)

The denial of hypermasculinity by *AN4* is because what according to him is called hypermasculinity is only a demonstration of the ‘hierarchy of power’ in society, which has “men in the dominating pole.” That is exactly what is assumed in the gender hierarchy theory which maintains that male domination or projection of hypermasculine traits and the resulting forms of inequality are of only structural nature.

The hypermasculinity in films is nothing new to gender and media researchers. Various researches have shown that the media are powerful agents for the projection and propagation of hypermasculine tendencies because hypermasculine archetypes abound in the mass media, especially action films, advertisements, and a plethora of popular culture media (Dill &Thill, 2007; Scharrer, 2010; Iwamoto, 2003)

However, the Nigeria situation is a bit new and insightful as data has revealed. It is evident that with the frequent recurrence of hypermasculine traits in Nigerian films, Nollywood is without doubt playing a crucial role in constructing and transmitting gender ideology, thereby possibly influencing gender attitude, values, and beliefs (see Lukas, 2002). The Nigerian films audience members are increasingly being bombarded with messages selling the idea that masculinity is violent, physically aggressive and sexually domineering and that anger and stoic toughness are legitimate emotions for men to display. That is in consonance with the tenets of the stereotype theory which maintains that members of the audience incorporate those meanings into their memories as relatively inflexible schemata--stereotypic interpretations – that they use when thinking about or responding to any individual of a portrayed category, regardless of his or her actual personal characteristics.

4.4.3 Research Question 3

What is dominant framework of hypermasculinity projected in select Nollywood films?

The analyses of the data coded from the films and responses from the in-depth interviews clearly indicated the various frameworks of hypermasculinity projected in select Nollywood films and select Nollywood films clearly exhibited degrees of hypermasculine traits, what frameworks underpinned their behavior: were the male characters born with the hypermasculine traits (biological determinism), did the male characters learn the he hypermasculine traits (gender role socialization) or did the male characters have the he hypermasculine traits because that is what is obtainable in the environment where they live or people expect them to have the traits (social constructionism)?

Data presented in Table 4.12 shows that 57.9% of the male characters who exhibited he hypermasculine traits were framed by gender role socialization; 17.0% of them were framed by biological essentialism; and 25.1% of the male characters were framed by social constructionism. The analysis on the chart emphasizes that the he hypermasculine framework with the most prevalence among the male characters in the select films is gender role socialization; followed in a distant second by social constructionism and them biological essentialism. The dataset above is stressed by a high mean of 1.67 and standard deviation of .850, the implication of which is that

majority of the male characters who exhibited the hypermasculine traits were framed by gender role socialization. That is, the male characters seemed to have learnt the he hypermasculine traits in the course of the storyline.

It is important to mention that, other than gender role socialization which commands majority of the frameworks, a reasonable percentage of the he hypermasculine traits in those films were framed by social constructionism; that is, they exhibit those he hypermasculine traits because that is what is obtainable in the environment where they live or people expect them to have the traits. In other words, only very few male characters are born with hypermasculine tendencies. They are mostly either learnt or hegemonic (society's expected idea of manliness).

However, it was important to ascertain if those frameworks significantly predict various acts of hypermasculinity depicted in the select Nollywood films. Hypothesis was tested in this study to examine the strength of the association between relative movements of the two variables, using correlation coefficient and regression analyses and based on a significant threshold of .005. The test of hypothesis was also necessary to ensure that the result from the simple percentage in Table 12 that 57.9% of the male characters who exhibited he hypermasculine traits were framed by gender role socialization was statistically significant and not out of chance.

Correlation coefficient and univariate regression analyses on Table 4.22 and 4.23 respectively showed that there was no correlation between the frameworks of hypermasculinity and he hypermasculinity traits in the select films. That is, it cannot be said that the frameworks predict what the male characters do; they can go out of all their way to show any traits without being predicted by a particular framework. The only twist is: the multiple regression coefficient (R) in Table 4.23 indicates a correlation only between gender role socialization and the he hypermasculinity traits. The quality of the prediction of the he hypermasculinity traits as the dependent variable is .699. Therefore, a value of .699 indicate a good level of prediction and is statistically significantly since $p < .005$. From the table, the coefficient of determination (R-square) is .488. That is, gender role socialization explains 48.8% of the variability of the he hypermasculinity traits. However, even the said correlation between gender role socialization and the he hypermasculinity traits was revealed in Table 4.22 to be an inverse correlation. The Table 22 shows that there is only an inverse correlation between gender role socialization and some he hypermasculinity traits such as violence as manly (-.532), callous attitude towards women and sex

(-.532) danger as exciting (-.567), toughness as emotional self-control (-.532) and other he hypermasculinity traits (-.596), and social constructionism which showed negative correlations with other he hypermasculinity traits (-.405).

An inverse correlation means that the variable move in opposite directions: that is, the more the male characters learn how to be a man, the less they show tendency for violence as manly, callous attitude towards and sex, danger as exciting, toughness as emotional self-control and other he hypermasculinity traits. Other than that, there are no sufficient statistical bases to conclude that there is an association between the frameworks of hypermasculinity and individual hypermasculinity traits in the select films. This does not totally ignore the fact that a reasonable majority (57.9%) of the male characters who exhibited overall he hypermasculine traits were framed by gender role socialization; which means that even if the researcher cannot correlate frameworks of hypermasculinity and individual he hypermasculinity traits, overall he hypermasculinity seems to be predicated on gender role socialization.

Majority of the respondents in the in-depth interviews feel that gender role socialization is the most dominant framework of hypermasculinity seen in films; while a number of them hold different opinions but they are largely of the opinion that “everyone is a product of the society...a product of what the person grew up actually to see; a product of the reality around them.” (AN1). The thoughts of those who hold that opinion is echoed by *IM5* who stated that:

“Sociologies often talk of classical conditioning and socialization as conduits for behavior... so that naturally applies to male characters in films... I’m a great fan of the Nigerian film industry... I what to believe that most traits in the films are learned:

Only very few respondents supported biological essentialism by maintaining that aggression and other he hypermasculine traits are largely inborn and have little or not to do with socialization or societal expectation of masculinity. They share parallel opinions with *IM1* who stated that:

“...most men in the movies have this kind of aggressiveness in them because they are born with it, no matter how good a woman is they still have that aggressiveness toward them...” (IM1)

Some of the participants were also of the opinion that the frameworks are situational and multi-dimensional as a man can acquire traits through any framework possible. It does not have to be from one framework only. They thought that:

“Each man his own, innate, socialized or otherwise... we are different... even a man can learn from all the frameworks all at once... but I think majority of the masculine traits are learnt from observation...” (AB2)

“... like all traits, the source of acquisition is multi-dimensional... could come from many sources... I’m not sure there is a dominant source of learning traits...” (AN4)

The idea of social constructionism was hardly expressed by the respondents but it was also explained by *ANI* as another observed framework of hypermasculinity in the films and one in which suggests that patriarchy is the soul of hypermasculinity as the patriarchal society expects a man to behave in a certain way.

There is continued argument among scholars with regard to the causation of hypermasculinized traits. Some scholars say that hypermasculinity stems from hormonal irregularities (i.e., higher levels of prenatal testosterone). Many studies claim that low levels of prenatal androgens can lead to male homosexuality while the opposite is true for those who exhibit hypermasculinized tendencies, often having a higher likelihood of committing crime, and having aggressive attitudes. High testosterone levels can also be linked to a lack of empathy and moral judgments (Montaya, 2013 in Siddhanta & Singh, 2015) which could lead to the hypermasculinized tendencies (Subramanian, 2014; Brannon, 2000; O’Shaunnesey & Stadler, 2005).

Other scholars are certain that all the hypermasculinity stems from those behaviour, values, and personality characteristics expected of boys/men, when act as a model or script for behavior (Brannon, 1998; Cosgrove, 200). There are scholars who argue on the notions that human beings rationalize their experience by creating models of the social world and share and reify these models through language (Leeds-Hurwitz, 2009). That is to say, the characteristics typically thought to be immutable and solely biological are products of human definition and interpretation shaped by cultural and historical contexts (Subramanian, 2010).

True to the social role theory, socialization facilitates sex-typical role performances by enabling men and women to develop appropriate personality traits and skills; those roles are perpetuated by the cultural institutions such as the mass media. The gender intensification hypothesis by Hill and Lynch (1983) also emphasizes the essence of socialization as a basic framework for the hypermasculinity. They stress that beginning in adolescence, girls and boys face increased pressure to conform to culturally sanctioned gender roles. These pressures come from a variety of sources that convey messages about appropriate gender roles, such as parents, peers, educators, and the media. In the face of these pressures, adolescents are thought to become more differentiated in their gender-role identities, which presumably will be adaptive for their adult roles as women and men. However, in the select Nollywood films the frameworks of hypermasculinity seems to be diverse, even though gender role socialization seems to be a more prominent framework.

4.4.4 Research Question 4

How did the amount of gender equitable masculinities compare with non-gender-equitable masculinities in the select Nollywood films?

Data presented in Table 4.11 shows the equitability of gender traits exhibited by the various male characters in the select films: that is, what traits shown by men in the select films are desirable (equitable) versus what traits shown by men in the select films are aggressive towards women and children (non-equitable)? It has to be stated that non-gender-equitable masculinities do not represent all the hypermasculinity. They only represent traits that are subjugating and oppressive to women and children.

Data present in Table 4.11 shows that 85.7% of the traits were gender equitable; and 14.3% of them were non-gender equitable traits. The dataset is stressed by a high mean of 1.14 and standard deviation of .350. Based on that data, it is evident that in terms of equitability indices, there are

clearly more gender equitable traits than non-gender equitable ones exhibited by the various male characters in the select films.

In other not to rely entirely on frequencies, descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) and T-test (inferential statistics) were used to find out the weighted means of the non-gender-equitable masculinity and gender equitable masculinity traits in the select films as well as compare their means to determine whether there is significant difference between them. The essence of combining descriptive and inferential statistics is that the inferential statistics helps the researcher to establish with some degree of confidence that the obtained mean of the sample groups in the descriptive statistics was too great to be a chance event and there is a real difference between the sample groups. Descriptive analyses in Table 4.24 reveals that the mean value and standard deviation of gender equitable masculinity traits are 2.61 and 1.725 respectively; while the mean value and standard deviation of non-gender equitable masculinity traits are 2.19 and .908 respectively. That is to say, statistically, the gender equitable masculinity traits are higher than the non-gender equitable masculinity traits in the select films. Meanwhile, the means score of gender equitable masculinity traits [$t(8953) = 234.952, p < .005$] was statistically significantly higher than the mean score of non-gender-equitable masculinity traits [$t(1496) = 93.461, p < .005$] in the select films. Owing to the statistically significant difference between the mean ($p < .05$), the researcher confirms that gender equitable masculinity traits were statistically significantly higher than the non-gender-equitable masculinity traits in the select Nollywood films.

Responses from the in-depth interview reveal that the proportions of gender and non-gender-equitable masculinities in Nollywood films clearly divide opinions among the respondents. What is common in their views was that all the male characters exhibit both gender equitable and non-gender-equitable masculinities in those films. Even the most smeared male character exhibit equitable masculinities in Nollywood films, irrespective of the proportion.

While admitting that there are cases where men exhibited admirable qualities that endeared them to women, children and their fellow men and gave them positive perception by the viewers, a number of the respondents still think that the projection of men as callous and aggressive and other negative portrayals far outweighs the positive portrayals. That opinion is echoed by *ABI*; *ANI* decided to take a “middle ground” and because she has seen films where there are admirable

qualities in the man were highlighted and will not completely say that the men are always negatively portrayed in Nigerian films”.

Majority of the respondents identified what they called “demonization of men” (AB2) because they maintain that men have admirable qualities that are shown in the films much more than the traits that depict aggressiveness and callousness. They insist that men are well portrayed and there is an abundance of gender equitable traits, where men exhibited caring, loving and admirable qualities in the movies. Their thoughts are reflected by AB2 who insisted that “there are certainly more loving and positive attributes of a man shown on films than just being aggressive towards women... to say otherwise will be an emotional statement” (AB2).

The implication is that the assumption of the social role theory about gender role differentiation is valid whether that role is gender-equitable or non-gender equitable. But in the Nollywood films, the findings imply that there more are instances when the male characters exhibits anti-masculine traits such as performing home-making activities like providing food or sustenance for family, taking care of children and women, cleaning the household or cooking; crying when faced with difficult or sad situation; romantically involved, submissive, weak, caring, chivalry, being attentive to their own appearance, gentle, having tender feelings, etc. than when they exhibit anti-feminine traits or when men were projected as being aggressive, dominating and violent towards women in particular. However, that does not temper the extent of hypermasculinity in the select films because the comparison of equitability is only about finding out how the norms associated with hegemonic masculinity has informed the attitudes of the male characters towards the opposite sex. This is without prejudice to other hypermasculine traits such as violence as manly; danger is exciting, toughness as emotional self-control and other hypermasculine traits.

Another inference to be drawn from this analysis is that the expression of more gender equitable masculinities is indicative of the rejection of the hegemonic masculinity paradigm and its harmful consequences while retaining other worrisome hypermasculinity traits in the select films. That is, the male characters are sometimes projected as being respectful and caring in their relationship with women or men, being involved in the lives of their children but that does not.

This is buttressed by UKaid (2015) who maintains that equitable and inequitable masculinities are not mutually exclusive in individual men. In some areas of life and relationship, with regard to violence for example, a man may manifest attitudes and behavior that are gender equitable. The

same man, however, on sexuality issues, may adopt some attitudes and behavior that are non-gender equitable. Similarly, gender equitable attitudes related to a particular issue in an individual man, may not always be reflected in his behavior. A man might consider violence against women to be wrong but simultaneously use emotional violence in his own intimate partner relationship, or decide not to intervene when faced with other men's violence against women.

4.4.5 Research Question 5

In what ways did the hypermasculinity in the select films relate to the demographics of the male characters in those films?

Data presented between Tables 4.3 and 4.8 analyzed the demographic characteristics of the male characters found in the select films, ranging from their age, marital status, occupation, social status, family life to their literacy level. Table 4.3 shows that majority (91.0%) of the male characters who exhibited hypermasculine traits in coded films were learned; 7.7% of those male characters were unlearned; whereas the literacy status of 1.3% of the male characters were indeterminate. The data is accentuated by a high mean of 1.10 and standard deviation of .345. The implication is that there is the near absence of unlearned male characters in Nollywood films, even in village or remote settings, a situation that seems to present men as widely educated.

Data presented in Table 4.4 shows that majority (62.7% of the male characters that exhibited hypermasculine traits in select films were middle-aged and reasonable percentage (30.5%) of them were old/elderly persons. The dataset is stressed by a very high mean of 4.27 and standard deviation of .584. The broader implication being that middle-aged characters and to a reasonable extent old/elderly characters are largest perpetrators of hypermasculine traits in the films.

Data present in Table 4.5 shows that majority (46.6%) of the male characters were pink-collar workers: a sizable percentage (27.2%) of them were white-collar workers and 18.0% of them were blue-collar workers. The dataset is accentuated by a high mean of 1.97 and standard deviation of 1.46. the implication being that a slight majority of the male characters who show hypermasculine traits as coded in the select Nollywood films are pink-collar worker, those who work in the service industry and different kinds of jobs that involve relations with people; with a sizeable proportion being white-collar workers (those in managerial and administrative positions) and to a reasonable extent, blue-collar workers (manual labourers).

Data presented in Table 4.6 shows that majority (55.1%) of the male characters were single; and a very sizeable percentage (43.1%) of them were married. The dataset is accentuated by a high mean of 1.50 and standard deviation of .646 the broader implication being that single and married male characters in the select Nollywood films show almost equal amount of hypermasculine traits, with those of the single male characters being only slightly higher because their status seems to afford them more freedom and sense of adventure that predisposes them to engage more in hypermasculine traits.

Data presented in Table 4.7 shows that majority (50.9%) of the male characters were part of a nuclear family: has a mother, father and sibling(s) or is a father of an identified child, husband to an identified woman or a son to a identified parent; with 13.5% of them as single parents; and the family life of 31.8% (241) of the male characters were indeterminate. The result is stressed by a high mean of 2.99 and standard deviation of 2.244. The implication being that the dynamics of a nuclear family seems to be a tinder for hypermasculine expressions.

Data presented in Table 4.8 shows that majority (48.2%) of them belong to the upper middle class; 24.3% of them belong to the lower class; 18.8% of them belong to the upper class; and 8.7% of them belong to the lower middle class. The dataset in Table 4.8 is accentuated by a very high mean of 2.12 and standard deviation of .875. That is, majority of the male characters who exhibited hypermasculine traits in select films belong to the upper middle class; with reasonable percentages belonging to the upper and lower classes. The implication is that majority of the hypermasculine traits exhibited in the select films was committed by characters who belonged to the upper middle class which also implies a rarity or near absence of the lower middle class in the select films.

The regression analysis on Table 4.13 showed that all six demographic variables (age, marital status, occupation, social status, family life and literacy level) were significant predictors of overall hypermasculinity at $p < .005$. That is, they significantly influence the expression of hypermasculine ideology in those films. Family life of the male characters was the strongest predictor of overall hypermasculinity ($R = .927$; $R\text{-Squared} = .859$), accounting for 92.7% correlation with the hypermasculine traits, which indicates a very strong and very high degree of correlation and also accounts for 85.9% of the variance in the depiction of overall hypermasculinity, which means that 85.9% of the total variance in hypermasculinity can be explained by the family life of the male characters. Family life as a predictor of hypermasculinity is followed by occupation of the male

characters ($R=.822$; $R\text{-Squared}=.676$), age of the male characters ($R=.695$; $R\text{-Squared}=.483$), marital status the male characters ($R=.554$; $R\text{-Squared}=.307$), literacy status of the male characters ($R=.400$; $R\text{-Squared}=.160$), and the least is the social status of the male characters ($R=.125$; $R\text{-Squared}=.016$), accounting for 12.5% correlation with the hypermasculine traits, which indicates very weak correlation and also accounts for 1.6% of the variance in the depiction of overall hypermasculinity, which means that 1.6% of the total variance in hypermasculinity can be explained by the social status of the male characters.

The general implication of the multiple regression analyses done to predict the correlation between the demographic characteristics of the male characters and hypermasculinity traits in the select films is that the demographic variables statistically significantly predicted hypermasculinity, $F(6, 750) = 960.534$, $p < .005$, $R^2 = .885$.

It was important to look at the extent to which each of the demographic variables of the male characters in the select films influenced each of the hypermasculine traits, instead of looking at the overall hypermasculinity as was done previously. The regression analyses on Table 4.18 showed that only 3 demographic variable (age, literacy level and family life) were significant predictors of *violence as manly* at $p < .005$. However, R and $R\text{-Squared}$ values differ for the 3 predictors. As the table shows, age is more strongly related ($R^2=.041$) than literacy level ($R^2=.026$) and family life ($R^2=0.23$). The regression analyses on Table 19 showed that only 3 demographic variable (age, literacy level and family life) were significant predictors of *callous attitude towards women and sex* at $p < .005$. However, R and $R\text{-Square}$ values differ for the 3 predictors. As the table shows, age is more strongly related ($R^2=.037$) than family life $R^2=0.25$) and literacy level $R^2=.023$). The regression analyses on Table 4.20 showed that only 4 demographic variables (age, occupation, marital status and family life) were significant predictors of *danger as exciting* at $p < .005$. However, R and $R\text{-Squared}$ values differ for the 4 predictors. As the table shows, occupation of the characters is more strongly related ($R^2=.461$) than age ($R^2=.038$), family life ($R^2=.267$) and marital status ($R^2=.227$).

The regression analyses on Table 4.19 showed that only 3 demographic variables (age, literacy level and family life) were significant predictors of *toughness as emotional self-control* at $p < .005$. However, R and $R\text{-Squared}$ values differ between the 3 predictors. As the table shows, age is more strongly related ($R^2=.037$) than family life ($R^2=0.25$) and literacy level ($R^2=.023$). The regression

analyses on Table 4.21 showed that only 4 demographic variable (age, occupation, literacy level and family life) were significant predictors of *other hypermasculine traits* not explained by the four indices of hypermasculinity at $p < .005$. However, Rand R-Squared values differ for the 4 predictors. As the table shows, age of the character is more strongly related ($R^2=.117$) than occupation ($R^2=.112$), family life ($R^2=.107$) and literacy level ($R^2=.072$).

Findings from the in-depth interview revealed that the proportion of hypermasculinity by the demographics of the male characters in Nollywood films clearly divides opinions among eh respondents. However, most of the respondents are of the view that hypermasculine traits can be predicted by the demographics of the male characters in Nollywood films. The extent to which that is so and which of the demographic characteristic of the actors mostly influence their behavior, is what divides opinion among the respondents.

Some of the respondents think that the income level of the male characters mostly influences their exhibition of hypermasculine traits in the films, with the low-income earners having more propensities for hypermasculinity than then others. This is mirrored by *ABI* who stated that "the low-income class men and the illiterates are largely portrayed to exhibit hyper-masculine traits" with regard to income, *IM3* maintained that the high-income earners have more propensities for hypermasculinity than others. With regard to age, *AN1* stressed that the "younger men... they exhibit it more than the elderly men." But majority of the respondents think that the exhibition of hypermasculine traits in the films by the male characters is not a function of the demographic characteristics of the man but a function of other factors far removed from their demographics, such as temperament and certain privileges that eh man enjoys. They stressed that:

“There is no particular income class, neither is there any age bracket or literacy level that is negatively portrayed...” (AB4)

"...anybody can be violent even men with low-income level or high-income level, some of them are violent their status has nothing to do with that ..." (IM1)

The findings of this study reinforce the gender intensification hypothesis, proposed by Hill and Lynch (1983): age and family life were stressed as the strongest predictors of hypermasculinity. Family, peers and educators put pressure on men to conform to culturally sanctioned gender roles

for them. That is why Mosher and Tomkins (1988) stress that the adolescent and young adult peer group, in particular, often celebrates and reinforces hyper-masculine ideology. Mills (2001) insists that during adolescence, masculine norms of “being tough” and related traits such as aggression become heightened.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary

The study sets out to examine hypermasculinity in Nigerian Nollywood films (2015-2017). The study was done on the basis that it was important to provide empirical evidence to confirm or invalidate hypermasculinity in Nigerian films and widen research attention to those less associated with gender issues: men, especially in a typically patriarchal society like Nigeria.

The objectives of this study were to identify hypermasculinity traits projected in select Nollywood films; find out the frequency of occurrence of hypermasculinity in select Nollywood films; identify the dominant framework of hypermasculinity projected in select Nollywood films; ascertain the relative amount of gender equitable and non-gender-equitable masculinities in select Nollywood films; and examine the proportion of hypermasculinity by the demographics of the male characters in the select Nollywood films. To achieve these objectives, five corresponding research questions are stated and three hypotheses proposed.

The design used in this study was basically explanatory sequential mixed method which combined content analysis and in-depth interviews with identified films experts and scholars. The code sheet was used to record depictions of hypermasculinity in 350 Nollywood films. The researcher was guided by the various content categories and units of analysis that are indicative of hypermasculinity in the selected Nollywood films. The presentation and analysis of the quantitative data were carried out with the SPSS version 23 statistical programme and presented in frequencies, charts and the descriptive statistics. The qualitative data was analysed using the inductive approach. The discussion of findings was done by interspersing the analysis from the quantitative data with the inductive analyses of the qualitative data in relation to each of the six research questions.

5.1.1 Summary of the Major Findings

The findings from this study are summarized as follows:

1. With the majority of the male characters (83.3%) in the select films clearly exhibiting degrees of hypermasculine traits in the films, it is inferred that Nollywood films significantly sold hypermasculine ideologies as a collective characteristic of the male

human. That is, they “practically shove the bloated idea of manliness into the throats of every of their viewers” (AN5), of the five indices of hypermasculinity (danger as exciting, toughness as emotional self-control, violence as manly, callous attitude towards women and sex and other hypermasculine traits), the most prominent in Nollywood films is *other hypermasculine traits* (28.6%): that is, any of the following acts engaged in by a male character: impulsivity, pursuit of self-esteem, self-reliant, primacy of work, risk-taking, decisive, competitive, ambitious, confident, egotistical, assertive, competitive, aggressive, unemotional and never cries. The next prominent hypermasculine traits exhibited in the Nigerian films include: *toughness as emotional self-control* (25.4%), *violence as manly* (20.6%) and callous attitude towards women and sex (20.0), and the least expressed is *danger as exciting* (5.4%).

2. That majority of the films (39.2%) had between 11 and 20 incidences of hypermasculine traits exhibited in them; and a reasonable percentage of those films (30.8) had between 21 and 30 incidences of hypermasculine traits exhibited in them. All the films, at varying degrees, contained varied levels hypermasculine traits. This confirms that hypermasculinity is widespread in Nollywood films. Hypermasculinity being expressed regularly in films is not a surprise since it is only a reflection of real-world situations in a patriarchal society such as Nigeria. However, it was found that opinions are still divided as to what constitute hypermasculinity in Nigeria, with many male interviewees and film experts feeling agitated over the idea that there is hypermasculinity in Nollywood films, as they feel that even if hypermasculine ideologies existed and are expressed in those films, they are justifiable and they are not more of a concern than the quantity of feminist ideologies in those films.
3. Majority of the male characters (57.9%) who exhibited hypermasculine traits were framed by gender role socialization; reasonably followed by 25.1% of the male characters who were framed by social constructionism. With a high mean of 1.67 and standard deviation of .850, the implication of which is that majority of the male characters seemed to have learnt the hypermasculine traits in the course of the storyline; reasonable percentage of the hypermasculine traits in those films were framed by social constructionism; that is, they exhibit those hypermasculine traits because that is what is obtainable in the environment where they live or people expect them to have the traits. A multiple regression coefficient

(R) analyses only shows significant association between gender role socialization and the hypermasculinity traits. The quality of the prediction of the hypermasculinity traits as the dependent variable is .699 ($p < .05$), indicating a good level of prediction. However, there was inverse correlation between gender role socialization and some hypermasculinity traits such as violence as manly, callous attitude towards women and sex, danger as exciting, toughness as emotional self-control, and other hypermasculinity traits, and social constructionism which showed negative correlations with other hypermasculinity traits. Therefore, the more the male characters learn how to be a man, the less they show tendency for violence as manly, callous attitude towards women and sex, danger as exciting, toughness as emotional self-control and other hypermasculinity traits.

4. It was found that there were more gender equitable traits (85.7%) than non-gender equitable traits (14.3%) in the select films. The dataset is stressed by a high mean of 1.14 and standard deviation of .350. Based on that data, it is evident that in terms of equitability indices, there are clearly more gender equitable traits than non-gender equitable ones exhibited by the various male characters in the select films. Gender-equitable masculinity traits were statistically significantly higher than the non-gender-equitable masculinity traits in the select Nollywood films, with the means score of gender equitable masculinity traits being [$t(8953) = 234.952, p < .005$] and that of non-gender-equitable masculinity being [$t(1496) = 93.461, p < .005$]. It was inferred that there more instances when the male characters exhibits anti-masculine traits such as performing home-making activities like providing food or sustenance for family, taking care of children and women, cleaning the household or cooking; crying when faced with difficult or sad situation; romantically involved, submissive, weak, caring, chivalry, being attentive to their own appearance, gentle, having tender feelings, etc. than when they exhibit anti-feminine traits or when men were projected as being aggressive, dominating and violent towards women in particular.
5. Multivariate correlations showed that all six demographic variables (age, marital status, occupation, social status, family life and literacy level) were significant predictors of overall hypermasculinity at $p < .005$. That is, they significantly influence expression of hypermasculine ideology in those films. Family life of the male character was the strongest predictor of overall hypermasculinity, followed by occupation of the male characters, age

of the male characters, marital status the male characters, literacy status of the male characters, and the least is the social status of the male characters. The multiple regression analyses showed that the demographic variables statistically significantly predicted hypermasculinity, $F(6,750) = 960.534$, $p < .0005$, $R^2 = .885$. Age, literacy level and family life were significant predictors of *violence as manly* $p < .005$, with age more strongly related than literacy level and family life; age, literacy level and family life were significant predictors of *callous attitude towards women and sex* $p < .005$, with age more strongly related than family life and literacy level; age, occupation, marital status and family life were significant predictors of *danger as exciting* at $p < .005$, with occupation of the character more strongly related than age, family life and marital status; age, literacy level and family life were significant predictors of *toughness as emotional self-control* at $p < .005$, with age more strongly related than family life and literacy level; age, occupation, literacy level and family life were significant predictors of *other hypermasculine traits* not explained by the four indices of hypermasculinity at $p < .005$, age of the character more strongly related than occupation, family life and literacy level.

5.2 Conclusion

Given the growing importance and influence of the film industry in Nigeria as well as the mounting interest in hypermasculine research, it was important to look at gender stereotyping in Nollywood, and to establish herein that Nollywood films significantly sell hypermasculine ideologies as a collective characteristic of the male human, especially when exhibiting traits such as toughness as emotional self-control, violence as manly, callous attitude towards women and sex and other hypermasculine traits has confirmed the critical role of the industry in constructing and transmitting gender ideology and influencing gender attitude, values, and beliefs. Hypermasculinity is widespread in Nollywood films and because of the frequency of its representation and given the socio-cultural context of patriarchy, the suspicion that it is only a reflection of real-world situations in a patriarchal society such as Nigeria is an easy one.

Hypermasculinity is profoundly woven into the fabric of the Nigerian films industry as all indices of hypermasculinity, excepting danger as exciting, are regularly expressed in the films. Audience of Nollywood are regularly bombarded with messages in the films selling the idea that masculinity

is violence against women and other men, toughness, aggression, assertiveness, impulsivity, risk-taking, pursuit of self-esteem, being dispassionate, dominance, risk-taking, egotistic, ambitious and sexually domineering and that anger and stoic toughness are the only appropriate emotions for men to display. Those are characteristic central to the hypermasculine ideology.

True to the social role theory, Nollywood films shape expectations for male behavior by certain portrayal of the men in the films. Those traits are mostly acquired by gender role socialization as majority of the male characters seemed to learn the hypermasculine traits, a framework that is known as gender role socialization. It is socialization that facilitates sex-typical role performances by enabling men to develop appropriate personality traits and skills. Sometimes those traits are framed by social constructionism, meaning that they exhibit those hypermasculine traits because that is what is obtainable in the environment where they live or people expect them to have the traits.

However, Nollywood still gives their characters the ample opportunity to reject hegemonic masculinity paradigm and its harmful consequences, which is why, in the midst of the variety of hypermasculine expressions in the films, one would still find instances when the male characters exhibit anti-masculine traits such as performing home-making activities like providing food or sustenance for family, taking care of children and women, cleaning the household or cooking; crying when faced with difficult or sad situation; romantically involved, submissive, weak caring, chivalry, being attentive to their own appearance, gentle, having tender feelings, etc. That is to say, hypermasculine is tempered in those films with gender-equitable masculinities. What the industry does is to reward gender-equitable masculinities.

Age, socio-economic power, occupation, marital status, literacy level and other demographic characteristics are variably related to hyper-masculine ideology idealization among men. All the demographic variables significantly influence the expression of hypermasculine ideology in those films. Family life of the male characters, age, occupation, marital status, literacy status, and social status are predictors of overall hypermasculinity. According to the gender intensification hypothesis, developmentally there is an acceleration of gender-differentiated socialization at the instances of some demographic variables.

The key takeaway of this thesis is the Nollywood films significantly sell hypermasculine ideologies as a collective character of the male human, especially when exhibiting traits such as toughness as

emotional self-control, violence, as manly, callous attitude towards women and sex and other hypermasculine traits. That means that they play a critical role in constructing and transmitting gender ideology and influencing gender attitudes, values, and beliefs; they also reflect real-world nuances of patriarchal society such as Nigeria.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the various findings made in this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. This study revealed that there are many hypermasculine traits in Nollywood. That can be reduced. There are storylines that do not normally yield themselves to representations of hypermasculine traits, such as musical/dance films (feature-length films that combines music, acting, dance and choreography), light-hearted comedies designed to amuse and provoke laughter. Those have become popular genres in Hollywood, but Nollywood filmmakers have not explored that genre. There is less adventure, and less need to demonstrate certain hypermasculine traits. Nollywood is replete with serious plot-driven films that are full of risk-taking, violence, and a host of hypermasculine traits.
2. It was found out that hypermasculinity is widespread and frequently portrayed in Nollywood films. Some factors are responsible for that. The poor quality of articulation and dialogue is one of the downsides of the Nigerian films industry. That has a ripple effect on the padding up some unnecessary actions to fill timeline and elongate the duration of the film, and by so doing, the frequency of hypermasculine traits is increased. Film writers should improve the quality of their dialogue and be conscious of their representations in the films.
3. It was found in this study that there are a lot of actions portraying violence against women. Filmmakers should pay more attention to stories that encourage promotion of mutual respect for both sexes. Women are also encouraged to take up careers in the technical aspects of film production, by so doing write and produce stories that protect their representations.
4. Nollywood should continue to give their characters the ample opportunity to reject hegemonic masculinity paradigm and its harmful consequences, by exhibiting and rewarding anti-masculine traits.

5. It was found that there is an inverse correlation between gender role socialization and some hypermasculinity: the more the male characters learn how to be a man, the less they show tendency for violence as manly, callous attitude towards women and sex, danger as exciting, toughness as emotional self-control and other hypermasculinity traits. Gender role socialization should therefore be increased as a fundamental part of a plot to reduce the incidence of hypermasculinity.
6. It was found that there were gender equitable traits than non-gender equitable traits in the select films. Yet hypermasculinity is still a concern. Story writers should reward gender equitable traits to make it more prominent. It should not just be seen as one of the acts in the film. The audience should be made to see it as something desirable. This can also be done by punishing adherence to hegemonic masculinity paradigm.

5.4 Suggestions for Further Studies

Having completed this study, and based on limitations observed in this study, the researcher hereby suggests that further research be done in the following areas.

1. A survey always affords the researcher opportunity to study the opinion of people in their natural setting. It is suggested that a further research be done by sampling the opinions of men and understand their impression of how films exaggerate the idea of manliness.
2. There should be further research on other forms of audio-visual media content aimed at men (e.g., videogames, television, and the internet). This would provide more detailed information regarding the extent of hyper-masculine ideology in the audio-visual media, as well as provide a more informed understanding of how often men are being exposed to such contents.

5.5 Contributions to Knowledge

This study has contributed to knowledge in the following ways:

1. The film industry is a powerful force in selling hypermasculine ideologies as a collective character of the male human.
2. There is a near absence of lower-middle-class population Nigerian films. Characters are mostly either very rich or very poor.

3. Hypermasculinity in films is tempered by rewarding gender-equitable masculinity and punishing the adoption of hegemonic masculinity.
4. Socio-cultural landscape of a film producer often has a wholesale effect on the development of a story plot. In a patriarchal society, the nuances of patriarchy are profoundly presented in films.

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Appendix A
CODE BOOK

Code Book for:

Hypermasculinity in Nollywood Films (2015-2017)

The essence of this code book is to educate the coder on the various concepts/terms used in the code sheet to enable him make an informed and valid decisions during the coding process. The explanations of the variables in this code book were largely adopted (with a bit of modification) from Vokey (2008) who did a parallel study albeit on magazines and based in Canada.

Part A: Film Identification Items

Name of Film_____

Director_____

Year of Production_____

Duration of Film_____

*Length of time that the film being coded lasted.

Men playing lead, support roles or any other role of note_____

*Identify which of the roles that the men of interest played in the film being coded.

Presence/Absence of women in the film_____

*Note whether or not there was a woman or women in the film being coded.

Part B: Thematic Observations in the Films

You will watch the entire film, and use all the visual information provided in the film to make the following coding decisions, having understood what the various content categories and variables mean.

1. Frequency of occurrence of traits (count occurrence of traits and tick the class of frequency it belongs from the options provided below)

- a. 1 – 10 times _____
- b. 11 – 20 times _____
- c. 21 – 30 times _____
- d. 31 – 40 times _____
- e. 41 – 50 times _____
- f. Above 50 times _____

2. Hypermasculinity Traits

a. Violence as manly

Tick if it appears that an act of physical violence is being carried out, is about to be carried out, or condoned (e.g., slapping, choking, hitting, stomping) or it appears that an act of verbal violence is being carried out, is about to be carried out, or condoned (e.g., yelling, name-calling) or it appears that multiple acts of physical and or verbal violence are being carried out, are about to be carried out, or condoned. Check if any weapon is present/discussed and/or being used (e.g., fists, guns). If any of those is seen, tick “violence as manly”.

b. Callous attitude towards women and sex

Tick if it appears that having/obtaining heterosexual intercourse is portrayed as an integral part of being a man or it appears that using any means necessary to obtain sex is appropriate or it appears that men are dominant and women are submissive, (e.g., portrayed as more important, or in a

dominant position to women) or a 'calloused relationship' between men and women is being displayed? (e.g., if a woman and a man are both present, does the relationship between them appear hostile, disrespectful, or antagonistic) or if it appears that an act/acts of physical violence against a woman is being carried out or condoned (e.g., slapping, choking) or it appears that an act/acts of verbal violence against woman is being carried out or condoned (e.g., yelling, name calling) or it appears that an act/acts of sexual violence against women is being carried out or condoned (e.g., sexual assault)

c. Danger as exciting

Tick if it appears that partaking in drugs, tobacco, and alcohol use/ activities is fun/exciting or if it appears that partaking in gambling/and or taking risks with money is exciting/fun or it appears that "partying"(e.g., attending wild, uninhibited parties) is fun/exciting or it appears that fast, dangerous driving is fun/exciting or it appears that adrenaline-jump or risky/dangerous sports are fun and exciting or there are other elements of danger engaged by men in the film

d. Toughness as emotional self-control

Tick if it appears that a man/men is/are depicted as being rugged, rough, or hardy (e.g., tough cowboy or police) or it appears that a message is sent that it is important for men to be in control and/or powerful or it appears that a man/men is/are depicted as being stoic (e.g., showing no emotion, cold) or it appears that a man/men is/are depicted as being angry (e.g., scowling, glaring) or it appears that being muscular is important for men.

e. Other hypermasculinity traits

Tick if any of the following acts is engaged in by a male character:

- i. Impulsivity
- ii. Pursuit of self-esteem
- iii. Self-Reliant
- iv. Primacy of Work
- v. Risk-taking

- vi. Decisive
- vii. Competitive
- viii. Ambitious
- ix. Confident
- x. Egotistical
- xi. Assertive
- xii. Competitive
- xiii. Aggressive
- xiv. Unemotional
- xv. Never cries

3. Hypermasculinity framework expressed

- a. biological determinism (Tick if the male character seems to be born with the hypermasculine traits)
- b. gender role socialization (Tick if the male character seems to have learnt the hypermasculine traits)
- c. Social constructionism (Tick if the male character seems to have the hypermasculine traits because that is what is obtainable in the environment where he lives or people expect him to have the traits)

4. Equitability of gender traits

a. Gender equitable traits

Tick when a man exhibits anti-masculine traits such as performing home-making activities like providing food or sustenance for family, taking care of children, cleaning the household or cooking; crying when faced with difficult or sad situation; romantically involved, submissive, weak, caring, chivalry, being attentive to their own appearance, gentle, having tender feelings, etc.

b. Non-gender-equitable traits

Tick when masculine or anti-feminine traits are behaved such as violence as manly, showing callous attitude towards women and sex, seeing danger as exciting, seeing toughness as emotional self-control or exhibiting other hypermasculinity traits such as the ones listed earlier.

5. Demographics of male characters (In making coding decision about the demographic characteristics of the male characters, choosing “unable to determine” is a safe option when the physical information or attributes of the character is not clear)

a. Age

- i. Child
- ii. Adolescent
- iii. Young adult
- iv. Middle aged
- v. Old/elderly
- vi. Unable to determine

b. Marital Status:

- i. Single
- ii. Married
- iii. Divorced
- iv. Widowed
- v. Unable to determine

c. Educational qualification:

- i. Learned
- ii. Not learned
- iii. Unable to determine

d. Occupation:

- i. White-collar worker
- ii. Blue-collar worker
- iii. Pink-collar worker
- iv. Unemployed
- v. Unable to determine

e. Social status

- i. Lower/working
- ii. Middle
- iii. Upper
- iv. Unable to determine

f. Family life:

- i. Being a Member of a Stepfamily
- ii. Being a Single Parent
- iii. Having a Single Parent
- iv. Being in an Adoptive Family
- v. Community as Family
- vi. Being a Member of a Nuclear Family
- vii. Unable to Determine

Appendix B

CODE SHEET

Code sheet for:

Hypermasculinity in Nollywood Films (2015-2017)

Part A: Film Identification Items

Name of Film_____

Director_____

Year of Production_____

Duration of Film_____

Men playing lead, support roles or any other role of note_____

Presence/Absence of women in the film_____

Part B: Thematic Observations in the Films

1. Frequency of occurrence of traits

a. 1 – 10 times_____

b. 11 – 20 times_____

c. 21 – 30 times_____

d. 31 – 40 times_____

e. 41 – 50 times_____

f. Above 50 times_____

2. Hypermasculinity Traits

a. Violence as manly_____

b. Callous attitude towards women and sex_____

c. Danger as exciting _____

d. Toughness as emotional self-control _____

e. Other hypermasculinity traits _____

3. Hypermasculinity framework expressed

a. biological determinism _____

b. gender role socialization _____

c. Social constructionism _____

4. Equitability of gender traits

a. Gender equitable traits _____

b. Non-gender-equitable traits _____

5. Demographics of male characters

a. Age

i. Child _____

ii. Adolescent _____

iii. Young adult _____

iv. Middle aged _____

v. Old/elderly _____

vi. Unable to determine _____

b. Marital Status:

i. Single_____

ii. Married_____

iii. Divorced_____

iv. Widowed_____

v. Unable to determine_____

c. Educational qualification:

i. Learned_____

ii. Not learned_____

iii. Unable to determine_____

d. Occupation:

i. White-collar worker_____

ii. Blue-collar worker_____

iii. Pink-collar worker_____

iv. Unemployed_____

v. Unable to determine_____

e. Social status

i. Lower/working_____

ii. Middle_____

iii. Upper_____

iv. Unable to determine_____

f. Family life:

i. Being a Member of a Stepfamily_____

ii. Being a Single Parent_____

iii. Having a Single Parent_____

iv. Being in an Adoptive Family_____

v. Community as Family_____

vi. Being a Member of a Nuclear Family_____

vii. Unable to Determine_____

APPENDIX D

LIST OF SAMPLED FILMS

2015

1. Gone too far
2. Lunch time heroes
3. Fifty
4. Road to Yesterday
5. Thy will be done
6. Grey Dawn
7. My Wife and I
8. The Department
9. Holding Hope
10. Out of Luck
11. Falling
12. Ikogosi
13. The Grave Dust
14. 76

15. Heaven's Hell
16. 93 Days
17. Code of Silence (2015 film)
18. Dangerous Twins
19. Gbomo Gbomo Express
20. The Cursed Ones
21. The Visit
22. 4-1-Love
23. A Soldier's Story
24. Taxi Driver: Oko Ashewo
25. Miss Flawless
26. If Tomorrow Never Comes
27. Mum, Dad, Meet Sam
28. Tempting Fate
29. Affairs of the Heart
30. Heroes and Villains
31. Romance is Overrated
32. Miss Taken
33. Last Night
34. Scarred
35. Diary of a Lagos Girl
36. Lunch Time Heroes
37. Forever Within Us
38. Falling
39. Friends or Foes
40. What's Within
41. Luke of Lies
42. Of Bad Faith
43. The Boss is Mine
44. So in Love

45. As Crazy as It Gets
46. The Grave Dust
47. Busted Life
48. Beneath Her Veil
49. Where Does Beauty Go
50. Night For Sex
51. Ikogosi
52. Oloibiri
53. Silver Rain
54. The Guest
55. A Place Called Happy
56. The Perfect Man
57. Superstar
58. 3 is Company
59. Mummy Dearest
60. Diary of The Triplets
61. The Other Side
62. Still Standing
63. The Duplex
64. Yes I Don't
65. While You Slept
66. Hunting 4 Hubbies
67. In the Music
68. The Green Eyed
69. The Antique
70. Grey Dawn
71. Dazzling Mirage
72. A certain night
73. Knocking on heaven's door
74. Brave

75. Iyore (the return)
76. The making of Iyore
77. Royal mission
78. Ugegbe oyibo
79. Nwayi nnewi
80. Iyanu
81. Akan
82. House of gold
83. Itoro
84. The real deal
85. Thy will be done
86. Royal banquet
87. Lies men tell
88. Desperate house girls
89. Hazeezat
90. Happy birthday
91. Matters arising
92. So in love
93. Torn
94. Ebube
95. Maid Michel
96. Birth mark mark
97. Losing control
98. His destiny
99. Love regardless

2016

1. Surul'ere

2. The wedding party
3. Mr and Mrs
4. The Arbitration
5. Okafor`s law
6. 93 Days
7. The CEO
8. Ghana Must Go
9. Couple of Days
10. Beyond Blood
11. Love is in the Hair
12. Elephant in the Room
13. My neighbour`s wife
14. Amuma
15. Lies men tell
16. Husband of lagos
17. Domestic workers
18. Bloodline
19. Delilah
20. Jennifers diary
21. Stolen waters
22. Ima
23. Pot of gold
24. Keeping secret
25. Festac town
26. Misplaced desire
27. When love happens
28. While you slept
29. 3 is company
30. Enemy of love
31. Ibu the campus lecturer

32. 39 steps
33. Baby oku in America
34. Banks chronicle
35. In the cupboard
36. Family man
37. Being single
38. Golibe
39. Life in congo
40. Glass slippers
41. Second chance for love
42. Tears of chimamanda
43. Without heart
44. V republic
45. Our society
46. Soul of a prince
47. First class
48. When the kings dies
49. Royal castle
50. Leave my man alone
51. Tears in the village
52. Circle of trust
53. Stale mate
54. New man street
55. Jacobs mansion
56. Shattered live
57. Ojadili the black magic
58. Fine girl
59. The stone
60. My wife's secret
61. Sense of touch

62. Daughter of the end time
63. The British man
64. A week to my wedding
65. Red line
66. Official affair
67. Confusion na wa
68. Mr. right
69. Three daughters of Eli
70. Save my marriage
71. My forever
72. Twisted destiny
73. Growing old
74. Stolen lives
75. Mummy's girl
76. Light will come
77. One moment in time
78. The revenge broom
79. My soul mate
80. Gbomo gbomo express
81. The banker
82. God have mercy
83. Lady of justice
84. My sixteen birthday
85. Forest daughter
86. The struggle continue
87. The prodigal
88. Shadow of evil
89. The bleeding girl
90. Body of love
91. The ordained

92. The oath
93. Child of the spirit
94. Not all gold glitters
95. Herat of gold
96. Amara rice and beans
97. Sorrows of a sister
98. Touch my heart
99. Untangle
100. Desperate for fame
101. Family pains
102. Home of trouble
103. Rich men association
104. Mr. Ibu loves girl student
105. The prince of love
106. My last joy
107. The gods of anger
108. Bianca and ojuku
109. Unwanted guest
110. Dinner with a friend
111. Millionaire girls
112. The future king
113. Udalaoma
114. Would still love me
115. Ebun
116. Ignorance of the wicked
117. The village tiger
118. Illiterate pool savers
119. Dance of shame
120. Thorns of love
121. Wonderful decision

122. Family cross
123. Foxy lady
124. Memory lane
125. Struggle to survive
126. Affair of the heart
127. Child not bride
128. Yes I do
129. Gold digger
130. My poor heart
131. Pains of a wife
132. Infidelity in the family
133. Household warfare
134. Babes part
135. Sonwa na piccolo
136. My woman my everything
137. Trial by ordeal
138. The wounded girl
139. Love or something like that
140. Jealous husband
141. The animal girls and the king
142. Black val
143. April

2017

1. Isoken
2. Christmas is Coming
3. Celebrity marriage
4. Idahosa Trails

5. Esohe
6. Talking Dolls
7. The Royal Hibiscus Hotel
8. American Driver
9. Sudani from Nigeria
10. Sobi's Mystic
11. Lotanna
12. 10 Days in Sun City
13. The Wedding Party 2
14. Bariga Sugar
15. A Hotel Called Memory
16. Affairs of the Heart
17. Tiwa's Baggage
18. Tough Love
19. Royal Seed
20. Rain of Hell
21. Ojukokoro
22. Slow Country
23. Hakkunde
24. Hell or High Water
25. Picture Perfect
26. Through the Eyes
27. Roti
28. My husband and I
29. My husband and his mistress
30. Wives on strike: The Revolution
31. Banana Island Ghost
32. Omugwo
33. Alakada Reloaded
34. Picture perfect

35. War in France
36. Labour room
37. Soil
38. Gateman
39. Baby boy
40. Rachael diary
41. Heart of the blind
42. Staff of vengeance
43. Friend zone
44. Intrusion
45. Wet
46. Weekend getaway
47. Losing control
48. The single ladies
49. Devils incarnate
50. Beautiful ruins
51. Single ladies
52. Hit and run lovers
53. After party
54. Flaws
55. North east
56. Honey contract
57. My answer part
58. Eternity so near
59. The wannabe
60. The chase
61. Eat me
62. Discontent
63. Teaser
64. Love and illusion

65. Meet our wives
66. Omalicha the carpenter
67. Bounce back
68. Ghetto preacher
69. Madam caitlyn
70. November 12
71. In your arms
72. Wedlock
73. Heart of the blind
74. Rain of hell
75. Last affair
76. Baby shower
77. The wedding
78. The spirits
79. A minute decision
80. Before getting married
81. Tempted
82. Brothers
83. Tears of my bride
84. The visit
85. Perfect
86. Royal seed
87. Tales of the police woman
88. Reconciliation
89. Sex and love
90. Night with the king
91. Scholarstical
92. Espionage
93. The mamas
94. 29 and miserable

95. Coal kingdom
96. Royal choice
97. Frenemy
98. Love triangle
99. Shoot to kill
100. At your service
101. Abuja babes
102. Tangled web
103. Double magazine
104. King of queens
105. It's about your husband
106. His addiction
107. Payback
108. Tiwa's baggage

